

An Investigation into the Innovative Practices Adopted by Female Entrepreneurs in Algeria

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This thesis was submitted to the University of the West of Scotland

Faculty of Business and Enterprise

for the award of Doctor of Business Administration

May 2021

Abstract

The research aims at making recommendations to female entrepreneurs in Algeria on the ways they can use innovative practices to support their business growth. The objective of the research has been to understand the Algerian entrepreneurial environment, female entrepreneurship, and innovation practices in Algeria and the purpose of the use of innovative practices in female-owned businesses in Algeria. To explore the factors that influence the innovative practices positively adopted by the female-owned businesses in Algeria and understand the challenges facing female entrepreneurs in Algeria in the use of innovative practices. Further, research objectives include determining the impact of innovative practices on female-owned businesses' performance and recommending a suitable framework to support female entrepreneurs in Algeria in terms of innovation practices.

For the attainment of research objectives, the selected research methodology was qualitative research. The research utilizes interpretive philosophy along with exploratory nature of research that has allowed the researcher to acquire high quality of qualitative information. The purpose of selecting a qualitative methodology is to gain an in-depth analysis of the research. The research selected both primary and secondary data sources. The sample size of the research includes 15 cases of female entrepreneurial businesses in Algeria. The data was collected using an interview questionnaire that was based on open-ended questions. For analysing the gathered data, thematic analysis was used to present the data in as understandable manners. The data analysis involved Nvivo software that has facilitated in understanding, realizing and interpreting the themes from the research study.

The data findings disclosed several innovative practices that female entrepreneurs can use to enhance the performance of their organisations. The analysis section proposed different themes based on the research findings. The findings disclosed that innovative practices include recruiting and hiring talented employees, training and developing (T&D) employees, technological advancements, cultural change, process innovation, marketing innovation, organisational innovation, technological innovation, and sales innovation are some of the major practices that female entrepreneurs can use to boost their businesses. Besides, the findings revealed that growth expectation is one of the major drivers for the innovative practices, the adaptation of technological programs also considered as innovative ways. The study concluded

that finance and lack of skilled and qualified human capital are the major barriers to the adaptation of innovation. However, through adopting innovative practices entrepreneur could able to increase their performance level.

Acknowledgement

Reflecting on this enriching experience, I am now convinced that the DBA journey is far from being a lonely one. Indeed, I would never have been able to carry out this doctoral work without the support of a large number of people whose generosity, positivity and interest shown in with regard to my research allowed me to progress in this delicate phase of the “apprentice-scholar”.

First of all, I would like to thank my thesis director, Dr Seema Sharma, for her guidance and for all the time she spent helping conduct this research. I would also like to tell her how much I appreciated her great availability and how I was extremely sensitive to her human qualities of listening and understanding throughout this doctoral journey.

All my gratitude goes to Dr Imani Silver Kyaruz, who triggered my passion for female entrepreneurship and helped me shape my topic, Dr Fatima Metaiche Tahir and Dr Boufeldha Ghit who kindly shared their experiences with me.

This work could not have been carried out without the availability and the warm welcome shown by the sixteen Algerian female entrepreneurs, and their employees, who opened the doors of their businesses for me and provided me with valuable material to advance in this research. The many other participants I had the opportunity to interview, Mr Sofiane Bekkouche and Ms Linda, part of the entrepreneurship support agency in Algiers. All these persons allowed me to bring this story to life, I hope.

These acknowledgements cannot end without a thought for my family starting with my first fan: my dad. His encouragement and enthusiasm are for me the founding pillar of who I am and what I do. Another special thought is for my mum, who I lost during the process, even though she didn't make it for the final results but the pride she expressed will stay with me for forever. A heartily thank you to my brothers and their wives Yassine and Meissa, M'hand and Fahima for their continuous financial, emotional and motivational support throughout this journey.

I am grateful to my husband, Lyes. Although he has not shared this entire amazing journey with me, in a small amount of time he made so much efforts for this research to be a priority. Thank you for coping with me, for your prayers and support.

At the end of this journey, I finally thank those who are dear to me and whom I have somewhat neglected in recent months to complete this thesis, Sanae, Yasmine and all my friends. Their attention and encouragement have been with me throughout these years, regardless of the distance.

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1. Chapter I: Introduction

1.1. Introduction

According to Lounsbury et al. (2019), entrepreneurship is mainly referred to as the idea of developing effective management of the business venture to gain revenue and profitability by taking different risks in the corporate world. Entrepreneurship is the capability and readiness to develop, organize and run the organisation along with the uncertainties to meet the business objectives. In economies, entrepreneurship is integrated or connected with labour, natural resources, labour and capital to develop profit. The entrepreneurial vision is described as an indispensable part of the national ability to succeed in the competitive, ever-changing and global marketplace. There are four essential types of entrepreneurship such as small business entrepreneurship, scalable start-up entrepreneurship, large company entrepreneurship, and social entrepreneurship. Based on the budget and resources entrepreneurs could select the most attractive and suitable approach to entrepreneurship (Panda, 2018). Innovation is key to entrepreneurship and critical to contribute to the success of business growth.

1.2. Background

In recent decades, women have been playing a vital role in modern business entities. The proportion of women on senior management positions, globally, has grown to reach around 29% i.e. the highest number ever recorded (Udanoh and Zouria 2018). Consequently, more and more women are becoming the part of labour workforce and more women are now contributing towards entrepreneurial ventures in different industries and various segments.

According to Udanoh and Zouria (2018), female entrepreneurs are the female who effectively manage and organize the enterprise or business. The female entrepreneurship has recently increased across the globe. The first female entrepreneur was Madame C.J. Walker for Sarah Breedlove as self-made female. She launched the hair and beauty products for the customers. Yadav and Unni (2016) argued that female have recently taken an active part in the business. Female entrepreneurship has recently increased at a rate of 7% from 1997. Movahedi and Jalileh (2017) mentioned that female entrepreneurs mainly account for enhanced economic stability and growth with the country. It has assumed that female entrepreneurs effectively inspire other

female to participate. This essentially motivates other female, encourage job creation that essentially supports in overcoming the gender gap at the workplace.

Female entrepreneurship and their contribution to the developing countries are considerably debated among scholars, especially in developing countries (Guilluy-Sulikashvili, 2017). It has been observed that despite a pro-business climate in Algeria, the country is offering equitable opportunities for men and female, female's entrepreneurship remains below compared to men (Neumeyer et al., 2019). According to Denieuil and Madoui (2016), in the last ten years, 3,275 companies took place with female entrepreneurship since 2008 in Algeria, which is a great increase. Female entrepreneurship could become a source of economic change and sustainable development in Algeria (Byrne et al.,2019).Female entrepreneurship represent an opportunity for the emergence and development of small and medium enterprises (SMEs), which are notably the engines that drive economic development (Byrne et al.,2019). SMEs account for almost 90% of the business activity worldwide, in both leading and developing economies through job creations, employment, tax provision, and contribution to Gross Domestic Product (Mines, 2017). In Algeria, small and medium-sized enterprises support economic growth and count as an essential element for integration, economic diversification, and the acceleration of the volume of investment and local industrial development and female entrepreneurial businesses can be a significant part of them (Bouri, 2017).

Ghiat (2018) also accepted that in Algeria, the number of female entrepreneurial activities is increasing due to the increasing economic, social, and cultural transformation in the country. Female entrepreneurship is a new phenomenon in Algeria (Ghiat, 2018). Lounsbury, Cornelissen (2019), also accepted the fact and highlighted that female entrepreneurship face multiple challenges. According to Ghiat (2020), female Entrepreneurship is important in the current business environment of Algeria because it brings diversity in the business environment and helps business to understand doing things differently and bring innovations. Innovation practices can contribute to female entrepreneurial success. Granqvist and Grodal (2019) argued that female entrepreneur encountered several challenges.

According to Brown (2018), innovation practice includes creating value for customers by using novel ways and thinking things with a different mindset. Innovation is the concept of developing and introducing original concepts to boost organisational success (Brown, 2018). It has been

assessed that organizations and entrepreneurs who are focused on innovative practices are capable of determining new opportunities and best approaches to resolve the current issues that help to enhance business sustainability (Guilluy-Sulikashvili, 2017). Innovation also includes the introduction or adoption of new technologies. New technologies are transforming the business process into complex systems. They have a significant and profound influence on entrepreneurial business growth. The needs and expectation of customer change rapidly. The cost is associated with these fast changes in customers' demands and technologies helps to streamline the processes to reduce the operational cost of sudden changes (Muhammad et al., 2019). Hence, to overcome the negative business impact entrepreneur need to bring innovation that is not offered by the rivals. The innovative practice allows the organisation to increase the revenue and profitability in long term.

Brown (2018) mentioned innovative practice as an act of introducing the new ideas, methods and devices. In contrast, Guilluy-Sulikashvili (2017) argued that innovative practice is the introduction of something new. However, Guan et al. (2019) mentioned innovative practice as a method, idea or device and novelty. It is found that innovation is the creation and delivery of the new customer value in the market place with the sustainable business model. Thus, the entrepreneur needs to adopt the innovative practices to effectively develop and increase revenue.

Female entrepreneurship can boost the economic level of the country while innovation practices remain vital to the success of these female entrepreneurs. Aldrich (2017) mentioned, females are dynamic and perfectionists. They tend to implement their innovation plans in a way that can help them in saving time and money for the business. Udanoh and Zouria (2018) mentioned that with the advancement of technology and innovation business the companies have adopted the number of innovative ways to develop and increase the performance. The entrepreneur often brings innovation and new products in the market. According to Kungwansupaphan and Leihaothabam (2016), entrepreneurial innovation is often understood and considered as the product innovation that intends to meet the needs and expectations of customers, which lead to business growth. The innovation is essential in entrepreneurship. Further, Halabisky (2017) highlighted that in a highly competitive business environment, female entrepreneurs need to bring innovative products for their survival and growth. Innovation is a backbone of female entrepreneurship; hence, innovative practices are necessary to consider. Therefore, female entrepreneurs need to come up

with the new product idea to grab the market share and increase revenue. In order to develop innovative products and offering exceptional services to customers, building a strong brand and developing the customer network, female entrepreneurs need to focus on innovation. Innovation is a determining factor in business competitiveness and considered as a key element in the survival, growth, and development of female entrepreneurial businesses (Leghima and Djema, 2014). Further, all over the world, female entrepreneurship has become a vital component of academic and policy conversations around entrepreneurship; still, there is much about the topic that still needs research and understand. Hence, it is mandatory to evaluate the role of innovation practices in the success and growth of businesses run by female entrepreneurs.

1.3. Research Aim and Objectives, and Questions

1.3.1. Aim

The aim of the research is to investigate into the innovative practices by female entrepreneurs in Algeria

1.3.2. Objectives

The study has the following objectives:

1. To conduct a comprehensive literature review to understand the Algerian entrepreneurial environment, female entrepreneurship, and innovation practices in Algeria.
2. To understand the significance of the use of innovative practices in female-owned businesses in Algeria.
3. To explore the factors that influence the innovative practices positively adopted by the female-owned businesses in Algeria.
4. To understand the challenges faced by female entrepreneurs in Algeria in the use of innovative practices.

1.3.3. Research Questions

To reach the ultimate aim of the study, this research answers the following questions:

The primary research question is:

- Q1: What is the role of innovation practices on the growth of female-owned businesses?

- While the secondary questions of the research include:
- Q2: What is the major purpose of using innovation practices in female-owned businesses in Algeria?
- Q3: What are the driving factors for innovative practices adopted by female-owned businesses?
- Q4: What are the challenges female entrepreneurs' faces when they attempt to implement innovative practices in Algeria?

1.4. Research Rationale

Within the business world, women have long faced discrimination based on gender. Consequently, a very few numbers of executives are female around the globe, despite the raising voices of different individuals on different platforms. The situation however is changing as many countries and many business entities now have females as the board of directors. Nevertheless, the issues still prevail and can be observed in different aspects of the business world, specifically in entrepreneurial processes. Women within entrepreneurial aspects, specifically within developing countries tend to face more severe issues and barriers that in turn restrict their potential to have innovative practices that could facilitate their venture to grow and develop. Moreover, male dominated countries like Algeria, the potential of women to innovate is subdued. Algeria is a male dominating society where female entrepreneurs must have been exposed to greater issues (Ghiat, 2016). Further, there is a gap in the literature; several studies have been conducted to determine the entrepreneurship and impact of innovative practices on them in different countries (Sriram and Mersha, 2017; Panda, 2018). However limited research is being directed to determine the female entrepreneurship and challenges to them they are exposed in Algeria. Despite, an increase in female entrepreneurship in developing countries, the research on female entrepreneurship remained an under-researched phenomenon (Panda, 2018). Moreover, according to some scholars, not only female entrepreneurship is an understudied phenomenon but the existing literature itself is limited. Like in any other business, innovation practices are crucial for female entrepreneurial businesses and their sustainability. Rochdi (2017) analysed that innovation practices are strongly associated with entrepreneurial orientation.

The current studies lack in determining the micro-environmental and macro-environmental factors that can influence innovation practices adopted by female entrepreneurs. Though the impact of innovation on business performance has been discussed in the literature, the challenges that female entrepreneurs may have to face in Algeria have not been discussed widely. The present research aims to fill this gap to effectively contribute to the research context. Further, despite numerous efforts in analysing the barriers faced by the Algerian SMEs, the studies lack in highlighting the role of innovation practices more precisely in female-owned businesses and depicting the importance of innovation management. The literature discussing the ways to promote female entrepreneurship and in Algeria through the adoption of innovative practices is missing (Ghiat, 2019). The lack of literature highlighting the importance of promotional techniques to support female entrepreneurship encouraged them to take initiative and overcome the existing gaps. This perspective motivated me to select the topic and conduct research on female entrepreneurship in Algeria. It becomes mandatory to reflect on micro-environmental, macro-environmental and cultural factors that can either positively or negatively influence female entrepreneurs. The research also highlights the factors that enrich the adoption of innovative practices.

Other than the theoretical gap, there is personal motivation towards the research area. Being a part of male dominated country with restrictions on women, a lifetime change has been witnessed within the society. There was a time when females were restricted from being a part of the workforce and then it changed. There was time when females in Algeria were not given enough opportunity to go up on the career ladder and now things have changed and women are opening their stores, online shops, and are starting entrepreneurial ventures. Consequently, it is now necessary to update the literature focusing on the innovative practices of female entrepreneurs to further help the concerned area to develop effective and efficient practices that could help them grow.

1.5. Research Gap

This research has both theoretical contribution and practical contribution. The theory states the factors that influence entrepreneurial growth and innovations. Theories do not remain the same, they evolve with time. This research contributes to the theory by highlighting the factors that influence innovation practices and female entrepreneurship most specifically in Algeria. Algeria

is an interestingly changing country in terms of social and cultural factors, creating a fabulous amount of opportunity for entrepreneurship especially for females, which coincides with the technological and knowledge advancements. These factors make female entrepreneurial research interesting and motivate to look at it with more depth to contribute to the subject, theoretically and practically. This research is a contribution to the practical applications of female entrepreneurship because it highlights the benefits of incorporating female in the business world for Algeria.

The practical application of this research for Algerian female entrepreneurs comes from the fact that it is conducted in the Algerian context. Though some studies have reflected on the barriers and challenges that female entrepreneurs face in Algeria, but the challenges and issues that they face during their adoption of innovation practices have not been discussed.

The current research overcomes this literature gap by shedding light on the challenges and hurdles encountered by female to become an innovative entrepreneur. The study offers recommendations to overcome these challenges. The research enhances the awareness of female entrepreneurs and also contributes to the knowledge of policymakers on the way the external factors such as political, economic, the culture of the county and technological environment, and legal aspects can influence innovation practices for female entrepreneurship. By knowing these factors, policymakers can come up with better practices for supporting female entrepreneurs in Algeria. The research is beneficial for female entrepreneurs to understand the importance of innovation for entrepreneurs. The research contributes practically to the efforts of female entrepreneurs because it offers recommendations on the tool and techniques that can be used to enhance innovations within their businesses. For example, finances are one of the major problems to gain for female entrepreneurs. The research suggests different ways of acquiring finance that can help female entrepreneurs in bringing innovation and enhancing growth. Further, this research holds a practical standing because it serves as a guide to Algerian female entrepreneurs in determining innovative practices. The research is effective and useful for encouraging financial institutions to make investments and help in boosting female entrepreneurship in Algeria. The research reflects on technological innovations as an innovation practice that donates to the growth of the overall economy of the country. The research aims to uncover the innovative practices used by female entrepreneurs.

This piece of work contributes, with its comprehensive framework, to the existing literature and theories surrounding female entrepreneurship in Algeria. So far, studies have been separately discussing female entrepreneurship and the adoption of innovative practices. This research overcomes this gap by discussing female entrepreneurship and innovation practices together. This research using a comprehensive conceptual framework reflects on the micro-environmental, macro-environmental, and cultural factors that influence the adoption of innovative practices by female entrepreneurs. The framework also fills the gap by highlighting the factors that can help to boost innovation within female entrepreneurial businesses. The research also discusses the drivers of innovation practices within female entrepreneurial businesses that have not been discussed in the literature widely. However, this study demonstrates the ways innovative practices can help the performance of female entrepreneurial businesses in Algeria. This study through its conceptual framework contributes practically towards female entrepreneurial businesses. It provides the target audience with various critical success factors that can be used to improve entrepreneurial understanding. Therefore, this report is significant for government institutions supporting entrepreneurship, financial institutions, and female in Algeria. The research has a positive impact on the development of female entrepreneurship in the country. The research by highlighting the role of female entrepreneurship in the economic development of the country and highlighting the role of innovation practices can make a huge contribution to the development of entrepreneurial policies at the government level within the country.

1.6. Outline of the Research

Chapter 1: Introduction: This chapter determines the background of the research context. It discusses the concept of female entrepreneur in Algeria and the importance of female entrepreneur within the country. This chapter covered the research aim, objectives, rationale and contribution of this research to academic and practical fields.

Chapter 2: Literature Review: This chapter summarised the theories and empirical research about the entrepreneur and female entrepreneurs in Algeria. This chapter discussed the theoretical concepts of female entrepreneurship and the factors that can influence them. Further, the chapter also includes the discussion of environmental factors that tend to influence the entrepreneurial activities of female in the country and may create challenges for their implementation of innovation practices.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology: This study utilizes qualitative approach and therefore conducts interview with 15 respondents. The data is represented through the thematic analysis. This chapter discusses the methodological choices adopted in detail. The chapter presents the choices made for to achieve the research objectives and to answer the research questions.

Chapter 4: Background of Algeria: This chapter introduces Algeria's country profile. The discussion comprises of Algerian Economy and Entrepreneurial system. This chapter starts with a general introduction of the country, with the location and all basics. It then gives a brief history of the country in order to highlight the influence of French and Muslim on the country. The later part of the chapter highlights the socio-economic progress of the country and then discusses the current state of SMEs and female entrepreneurship in the country.

Chapter 5: Data Analysis and Discussion: This chapter is divided into two sections. First section discusses the case analysis. The cross case section discusses the opinions, arguments and ideas about different aspects of innovation including issues they have faced. The later part of discussion highlights the findings from the interview sessions. Holistically chapter represents the findings for the research.

Chapter 6: Conclusion and recommendations: This chapter summarises the key findings from the study and data analysis. The conclusion section also covers recommendations for the target audience, highlights limitations, and offers suggestions for future research.

Chapter 7: This is the last chapter of the research that highlighted the key findings of the research and defines the concluding marks that have been drawn from the gathered data and analysis. The chapter includes recommendations for the target audience and defines the ways female entrepreneurship can be improved using innovation practices. The chapter highlights the limitations of the research and also offer suggestions for doing future research.

2. Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1. Introduction

This chapter secures the second position in the research and shared history of SMEs including female entrepreneurial businesses in Algeria. The chapter also discusses theoretical and empirical thoughts on female entrepreneurs and innovation practices. However, before reflecting on the theoretical aspects it was crucial to discuss the entrepreneurial environment of Algeria. Hence, the chapter first discusses the general environment for female entrepreneurial businesses in Algeria.

2.2. General Entrepreneurial Environment in Algeria

Currently, it has been assessed that Algerian youth is getting aware of the benefits of entrepreneurship. The youth is turning to social entrepreneurship and finding creative solutions to eliminate unemployment in the country. In the response of declining revenue related to oil, the country is enforcing austerity measures (Jebari, 2016). The government in the country is unable to offer significant funds for the promotion of education and generous welfare programs. The cuts by the government for housing, education, and healthcare programs are putting the different sectors and population at risks from which the one is the youth of Algeria (Jebari, 2016; Oxford business Group, 2021). In Algeria, the youth represents 60% of the population that represents 40 million. According to statistics, the Algerian youth is three times unemployed in the country which means 30% versus 10% (Jebari, 2016). Though the country continues to develop strategies to reduce the level of youth unemployment in the country such as loans for small and entrepreneurial businesses, they have been extremely unsuccessful and performed poorly due to the incomplete transition of the economy to become liberal private sector from the centralised social economy and structural issues within the economy (Jebari, 2016). However, it has been assessed that youth in the country is successfully realising the causes of unemployment in the country and making efforts to reduce its without depending on the state and this may stimulate the overall reforms of Algerian system. The approach of the country is not effective and a long-standing issue for entrepreneurial initiatives in the country. According to the official statistics of 2016, a slight improvement in the employment level of youth in the country has been observing as the level of unemployment in the country reduced from 11.2% to 9.9% (Jebari, 2016).

Despite moving on from the traditional state of the centralisation, the youth both men and female commented on the difficult situation exists in the country that prevents them to become an entrepreneur. In Algeria, the culture of the country is more negative and the attitude of families is pessimistic. Not only the culture of the country is not positive, but female face significant issue in getting jobs despite putting their efforts and giving their best. Majority of the youth, therefore, has been observed to get employment in the informal sector below their educational level (Jebari, 2016; Tahir, 2016).

However, recently the government, observing the current unemployment situation, has decided to introduce some Algerian entrepreneurship programs to support employment in the country. According to the report of World Learning Inc (2021), these programs will tend to be more demand-driven process for the businesses led by the youth to help these enterprises to grow. These programs will also strive to improve the employment opportunities for supporting the existing youth entrepreneurial businesses. This will be a dual strategy for the country, as these programs will give a boost to the technological sector in the country and will also expand the level of employment and improve economic stability (World Learning Inc, 2021). It is expected that the programs will deliver with the demand-driven training to people so the Algerian have access to relevant and high-quality training opportunities. The introduction of such programs is a depiction of the fact that the country is making progress and attempting to boost the entrepreneurial level for reducing unemployment in the country (World Learning Inc, 2021).

Some goals of the programs include identification of the knowledge and technology-based businesses that contain the high potential to enhance employment. These programs aim to prepare both men and female for meeting the demand of technology and knowledge in the entrepreneurial sector. These programs just not tend to build the skills, but also serve as a bridge between the potential investors and social entrepreneurs (World Learning Inc, 2021).

However, it has been assessed that there is a need to promote the entrepreneurial culture in the country because a long trend in the country for not valuing such activities has left scars that are necessary to remove. The young population face difficulties in getting entrepreneurial opportunities because they are weak in their network building (Salto, 2021). There is a huge gap in communication, leadership, and entrepreneurial skills that is crucial to overcome. Training and skills acquisition programs are necessary to introduce in the country to boost entrepreneurial

opportunities. There is a need to enhance the innovation and non-formal educational programs that can enhance the awareness of people in the country and improve the chances of existing businesses to become successful (Salto, 2021). The current environment of the country with the introduction of some efforts has been a failure to create an entrepreneurial thrust within the country. The social government is responsible for the current situation and lacks in social welfare schemes and could not contribute to the economic development of the country. The country just not lacked in creating entrepreneurial hunger, but problems, and their solutions as well (AtoZ Entrepreneurship, 2021). Though the country gained huge reserves of the Forex money from gas and oil industry that should have been used for building an infrastructure to give rise to diverse industries and expanding the economy, the government lacked in such initiatives that show the lack of interest in developing an entrepreneurial culture in the country. The population of the country is not happy with the slow change and driving the internet businesses in the country due to lack of support to entrepreneurs. Some online entrepreneurial businesses depicting the independent growth of online businesses in Algeria include NetBeOpen, T-Algeri, and Ouedkniss (AtoZ Entrepreneurship, 2021). Currently, it has been observed that transforming the social economy into the private one, is one of the best solutions to the country. This change will drive both national and international fund to the country and will show the opening of the country towards the creation and progress of the business and therefore enhancing the ease of doing the business that currently stands at the rank of 157. These enterprises will in return reduce the unemployment ratio of Algeria and improve the overall health of the economy (AtoZ Entrepreneurship, 2021).

The relationship that exists between the Algerian female entrepreneurial businesses and innovation remains ambiguous in Algeria (Fatima et al., 2014). The innovative behaviour of the Algerian entrepreneur is closely linked to the components of social capital. It is realized that innovation results from a specific and individual hierarchy, first by an accumulation of capital, then a relationship of capital knowledge, finally leading to financial capital (Fatima et al., 2014).

Entrepreneurship encompasses several phenomena that materialize in the interrelationships between a company and its market. According to Swanson (2017), entrepreneurship is a systemic analysis of innovation activities, which can be measured through these three criteria: The ability of a company to control its costs and set its prices, the excellence of its processes of production

(quality, reliability, flexibility, security, etc.), and its skills in the field of human resources management.

It has been assessed that innovation practices in Algerian female entrepreneurial businesses are one of the major contributors to entrepreneurship. For entrepreneurship, companies depend heavily on the local context and the specificities of the situations. But the country lacks skilled staff and the opportunities to train them, to motivate them in mobilizing their competence, did not appear almost in the minds of Algerian leaders (Honeyman, 2019). This managerial behaviour explains the degree of centralization of the decision's actions and the direct implication of the bosses in the conduct of their business.

On the other hand, Nowoswiat and Pokorska-Silva (2020) highlighted a lack of competitiveness as a problem for becoming an entrepreneur. Competitiveness is not put into perspective with the capabilities of the company, the available or potential resources. Several upgrading programs have been deployed to introduce female entrepreneurial businesses to competitiveness through a continuous process of learning, of reflection, information and acculturation, to acquire new attitudes, reflexes, and behaviours of entrepreneurs, and dynamic and innovative management methods. The results of these programs to date remain very meagre, with very low participation of female entrepreneurial businesses (Nowoswiat and Pokorska-Silva, 2020). Baziz (2018) highlighted the institutional and educational programs and their role in building the capabilities of individuals to become an entrepreneur. The study concluded that these institutional programs lack clarity, and there are several reasons due to which the educational system is unable to deliver the country with entrepreneurial skills and these reasons have been mentioned below (Baziz, 2018):

- The lack of support from the institutions concerned in terms of brand studies as well as information on potential markets. The changes and improvements expected from these programs are not felt because they do not deliver with the content that stands out students from the Algerian context (Baziz, 2018). The major failure in terms of providing proper education and providing the environment for entrepreneurship include lack of training of specialized skills for most entrepreneurs, lack of support and managerial assistance from specialized agencies that lead them to non-realistic education lacking in the development of practical professionals. There is an existence of a remarkable gap between female

entrepreneurial businesses, creative aid agencies, and the promotion of entrepreneurial activities by universities. Further, the lack of assistance for companies amid future business aspirants (Baziz, 2018; Boudersa, 2016). Ambiguity noticed in the definition of the theme: upgrading, each organisation has its vision (Chamber of Commerce and Industry, SME Facilitation Centre, University, schemes to help start-ups... etc.).

- Algeria spends less than 1% of GDP on research and development (The World Bank, 2021). This result is not positive; indeed, the Algerian university is lagging in terms of scientific production (Khoualed, 2020). It is agreed that university research is more profitable for female entrepreneurial businesses than for large companies (McGuire, 2019). In other words, female entrepreneurial businesses get a share of the resources they need from external factors such as universities. Many researchers have therefore focused on the relationship between academia and entrepreneurship. It has been observed that that entrepreneurship is a three-way construction: initialization, institutionalization, and integration. Each one can consider and build this relationship according to the required level, according to its objectives and means. The initialization reflects the actions of the state to promote entrepreneurship in part through the university. Institutionalization is continuity in the actions deployed within the university and in this case the university becomes a pillar of economic development. While integration is a reconciliation of actions often scattered within the university to arrive at developing new forms of organisation (Schmitz, 2005; Schmitt, R. and Bögli, 2005; 2008; Sengupta et al., 2018).
- Initialization: Algeria has chosen to include research as well as innovation within the universities and within entities called laboratories, divided into research teams with defined themes. The laboratories depend on a vice-rectorate of Post-Graduation and Scientific Research. Researchers can talk about an initialization, however still weak, in the sense that often the results of the research teams are not transferable (Mezhouda, 2019).
- Institutionalizations: As regards the valorisation of the research, it is framed by the research centres and the national research agencies. They are directly under the supervision of the Direction General of Scientific Research and Technological Development. The latter is more for support, the development of research in the field of

health and to enhance the value of these results (Direction General of Scientific Research and Technological Development, 2021). Departments of Evaluation and Valorisation of Results are also responsible for the periodic monitoring of the progress of research projects, the control of the conformity of the results about the objectives set, the valuation of the results of scientific research through the production of books, scientific reports, the publication of scientific journals and journal articles and participation through papers at national and international scientific meetings (Tebani and Mederbal, 2018). The objective is, among other things, to identify and select the results of the research to promote, to encourage the systems and methods of valorisation, to develop and promote cooperation and exchanges between the research sector and the user sectors, to support and accompany innovative ideas of business creation and participate in job creation. These institutions in the country are supporting the entrepreneurial ideas in the specific sector through offering research and enhancing the awareness of people, which is a weakness of the system.

- Integration: The Algerian National Institute of Industrial Property is responsible for integrating the world of research into economic development. The latter is responsible for the registration of trademarks and patents. Applications for trademark registration with the Algerian National Institute of Industrial Property increased by almost 12% in 2011. In 2015, Algeria registered 47567 trademark applications, compared to 53040 in 2012, half of which were from foreign companies (WIPO, 2016). Regarding patents for inventions, a very low figure of only 125 claims recorded in 2011 against 806 in 2010. This figure reflects not only the decline in the level of inventiveness in Algeria but also that the economy remains dominated by a commercial sector that concentrates most of the country's non-hydrocarbon economic activity (WIPO, 2016). In 2015, the country received more than 3000 patent application and 47000 trademarks annually. It hasn't been disclosed the share of foreigners in patent applications for inventions. However, it should be recalled, that in 2012, the patents were 3025 that reached up to 3357 in 2015. In the country ranking of patent applications filed with INAPI in 2010, France and the United States of America top the list with respectively 133 and 126 applications. Germany with 82 patent applications, China with 79, while Japan with 77 just as Algeria which comes in 5th place. Traditionally, the pharmaceutical industry sector is the most

prolific in terms of patents of the invention whether from foreigners or nationals (WIPO, 2016).

2.3. History of SMEs in Algeria

SMEs have been representative of entrepreneurial businesses including female entrepreneurial businesses. Hence, to understand the entrepreneurial environment of Algeria, it is mandatory to discuss these businesses. Before 2001, SME in Algeria did not have any official definition. An SME was just a business producing goods and/or services and employing no more than 250 persons. In 2001, when Algeria signed a partnership with the European Union, it adopts the official European definition of the SMEs (Mosbah, 2014). In Algeria, SME is a company producing goods and /or services employing one to 250 people. The annual turnover of these SMEs does not exceed 4 billion dinars or and the total of their annual balance sheet do not exceed 1 billion dinars (Mines, 2017).

The Algerian entrepreneurial industry evolved through several stages that have been explained as follow (Mosbah, 2014):

1962-1982: A period characterized by a planned economy where the emphasis was on heavy equipment and intermediary goods' production. After the Algerian independence, left companies have been integrated into national companies. Following its independence in 1962, Algeria was more focussed on heavy industries such as oil and gas (Chelil, 2016).

1982-1988: This period was still under the planned economy but observed some great reforms. Two five-year plans that have been established in favour of the private sector allowing SMEs to access global import permits and to benefice from the free-tax-import system (Korichi, 2015). It was only by 1988 that the country decided to move to the open markets and start relying on and supporting SMEs for strengthening economic development (Chelil, 2016).

1988-2001: This period was characterised by the shift of the Algerian economy from a planned economy to the open market. The ceiling of private investment has been released allowing investment in other areas as mentioned by (Sekiou, 2018).

Since 2001: This period has been characterised by a plan (announced in 2010) aiming to create one million new SMEs during the 2015-2019 five-year period. The focus was on easing the

administrative procedures, abolishing the distinction between private and public investments and reducing taxes.

The growing consideration and importance of the SME in Algeria through its history have been noticeably pointed out in the literature. For example, Korichi (2015) highlights that the creation of SMEs has not ceased to be relevant since the 1980s, while the model from big business for vertical integration is running out of steam. Due to its dynamic status which response to the characteristics and changes in the environment in which it evolves, the small business is more and more considered as a wealth-creating engine, a source of filling economic needs and social benefits in terms of economic growth, regional development, and absorption of unemployment (Korichi, 2015). Due to this increasing perception that SMEs are one of the major contributors to the country's economy, it becomes necessary to discuss them as entrepreneurial entities that represent female entrepreneurial businesses.

2.3.1. Some Supporting Elements for Innovation in Algeria

In Algeria, SMEs were marginalized until the end of the 40s. These SMEs in the country were focused on activities of very low technological intensity. But with the introduction of economic reforms in the early nineties because of the liberalization of the national economy, the public authorities put in place a support and promotion program for SME including female entrepreneurial businesses (Jebari, 2016; World Learning Inc, 2021).

All these measures have the essential objectives of encouraging creativity and innovation, the latter is a response to the problems of national and international competition, for this reason, the public authorities finance many actions to support innovation (IMF, 2017). It is true that this concept is strongly used, to the point where several companies constitute it as a real concern, to know how to develop innovation, what are the factors triggering the process of innovation. Many solutions are available: there are specific funding, methodological guides, skills, and types of organization, but with all the available choices, companies can be lost to choose the most appropriate solutions (SMEX, 2019). Therefore, to assist the Algerian SME including female entrepreneurial businesses and create an environment conducive to the flourishing of its innovation activities, a national policy has been put in place at the expense of the Ministry of SMEs and Crafts which aims to provoke the intervention of the State for the implementation of a systematic policy of promotion and development of technical progress within the framework of a

national system of innovation. To implement this policy, a National SME Development Agency was created in 2005 (SMEX, 2019; Oxford business Group, 2021). However, people cannot judge nor evaluate the actions carried out by the institutions in charge of doing it, since until now no action has been established. National SME Development Agency made significant efforts to support the entrepreneurial enterprises within the country. It is claimed by the secretary-general of the Ministry of Industry and Mines by the year of 2015, approximately 900000 SMEs were operating the country (Oxford business Group, 2021). In 2009, Algeria with the support of the European Union launched 44 million joint initiative programs to support SMEs in the country. Following in 2010, these programs contributed to the development, modernisation, and upgrading of SMEs to boost the competitiveness by 2000 by the year of 2014. The programs are supporting entrepreneurial businesses within Algeria by offering developmental, consultation, and investment support for equipment. The allocated budget for these activities was 3.56 billion. Youth has access to national agencies for having funds, loans, and grants with subsidising interest rate for the projects that worth up to 92000 (Oxford business Group, 2021).

The Algerian state has also created a new division responsible for innovation policies as part of the new industrial strategy at the beginning of 2008 within the Ministry of Industry and Investment Promotion, which is responsible for steering the missions that were awarded by MIPI. For the success of this mission a National System of Industrial Innovation has been set up and which is based on the following:

At the national level

The public authorities should rely on two agencies to implement incentive actions conducive to the development of its industrial strategy; The ANII (National Agency for Industrial Innovation) and ANVREDET which would be responsible for the companies in the creation of results from spin-offs by the university. Also, the creation of a statistical service that can measure and evaluate the expenses whether individual or collective R&D and innovation in each company (Ferrah and Oubelli, 2013).

At the sectoral level

The public authorities should set up Innovation and Technology Transfer Centers (CITTs), which constitute essential sectoral technological support for businesses: they will provide

convenient services to industry, support for innovative technology and information watch, support for the formulation of technology and innovation needs, technology transfer, technical assistance for technological upgrading, certification, and standardization, and specialized training. To this end, three innovation and technology transfer centres have to be created in addition to the two existing ones: the CITT for mechanics and metal processing, the food sector and finally the plastics, paper and packaging sector (Ferrah and Oubelli, 2013).

At the regional level

The ANII should have decentralized own resources in the cities, of which the following eleven groups include 55% of Algerian SMEs: Algiers, Oran, TiziOuzou, Bejaia, Setif, Blida, Chelef, Boumerdes, Constantine, Annaba, Tipaza. University-industry interfaces should also be deployed based on successful experiences in this area. Incubators and incubators will have a prominent place in this system under the coordination of ANVREDET.

In terms of financing

The ANI must have several instruments: financing by a subsidy of 50% of the R&D project submitted by a company or organization, an annual subscription for CITT or CRD on the based on the amount of partnership research services provided with companies. It should be noted that the financing of the CITTs by a tax is not favourable based on inconclusive experiences in the Maghreb countries and that it should be in addition to the recommended subscription to grant the CITTs a basic endowment annual budget of around 30% of their budget. The ANVREDET, in its new configuration, will have the means to subsidize research projects up to 30% of expenses. Finally, the public authorities should tax in the form of a tax credit research spending R&D companies up to 50% at least in the first phase (Tahir, 2016).

The objectives set by the public authorities to make innovation a lever for the development of the country's industry suggests to us that there is a genuine desire to break with past practices.

2.4. Female Entrepreneurship in Algeria

In developing countries, there has been an increasing interest in the promotion of entrepreneurship in recent years as observed by (Minniti, 2010) and (Ennis, 2018). Although female labour force participation tends to grow in developing countries; but, female still have lower rates of labour and force participation (Campaña et al.2020). The emergence of the role of

female as business-owners in the global economy has been reflected by the multiplication of studies looking at female entrepreneurship over the past three decades, with an emphasis on studies examining female entrepreneurs in Anglo-Saxons countries (Bastian, 2018). According to Ghiat (2017), the Algerian businesses and social climate are less discriminative than what we tend to think. The author reflected on the ways the success of female entrepreneurs changed the landscape of entrepreneurship in Algeria and it became obvious to deal with female as clients, managers, and entrepreneurs. In alignment, El-Hamidi (2017) depicts the characteristics of female entrepreneurship among the MENA countries including Algeria. It has been assessed that the working culture of these countries is more favourable for men. He stressed that the culture of a man society is the origin of several socio-cultural problems for female entrepreneurs in Algeria. One can notice, through the existing literature that there are a growing consideration and interest in the Algerian female entrepreneurship. In this sense, the author emphasised the new interest given to female entrepreneurship and the recognition of its importance for the economy. Both facts made it unsurprising that in Algeria, females tend to be attracted by activities that can be managed from home, with minimal capital required. The author confirms the fact that a change in the perception of female entrepreneurs can be noticed in the Algerian society (El-Hamidi, 2017).

In this climate, the female share of early-stage entrepreneurial activity is considerable (40% in Algeria) while the share of men is still 30% higher than the female share among established business owners in Algeria (Tahir, 2016). Tahir (2016) depicts a picture of the Algerian female entrepreneur. The researcher found that most of the female entrepreneurs are found in the capital, Algiers. 46.7% of the female tend to rely on family/friends/husbands for financing their projects, 44.1% of the businesses are service-related, 60.1% of female entrepreneurs own SMEs, 60% of the firms are active for more than 5 years (Tahir, 2016). The author further explained that these Algerian female entrepreneurs still vary in terms of their growth expectations and attitudes.

Sidani (2017) identified important gaps in the present studies conducted in the domain of female entrepreneurs. For one, there is a need for more solid theoretical foundations in the research. Most of the research studies so far have been trying to gauge the situation of female entrepreneurs, understanding their status, and the profiles of their operations. This has been very useful. Yet it is about time for future research studies to delve the factors influencing female

entrepreneurship within the country for building a solid theoretical framework by which a better understanding of female entrepreneurship can be developed in the region. The uniqueness of the region and the distinctiveness of some of the factors that motivate or obstruct female entrepreneurship have the potential to contribute to the general field of entrepreneurship as a whole (Sidani, 2017).

2.5. Theoretical Concepts

2.5.1. The Concept of Innovation

There is no set way to understand innovation, entrepreneurs can understand innovations in multiple ways, but the one aspect that is common in all definitions of innovation and that is defined by common sense include novelty (Hammershoj, 2017). According to Tidd and Bessant (2020) when dealing with the diversity of literature, it is remembering to deal with the basic concept of innovation is necessary to understand the fact that innovation is not an ending, it is a beginning of the processes to produce, introduce, and improve the things and their practical application to gain better results and enhance the organisational profitability. On the contrary, Rosenbusch et al. (2019) emphasized that innovation is a social process that includes the intensity of the creative direction that is dependent on laws, regulations of the country, and institutions that contain an ability to affect the incentive that contains any influence on the financing and the organisation of the shared experiences, research and development (R&D), and desire of making the use of new technologies that represent innovations. Further, Yan and Yan (2016), tinted on innovation and highlighted the difference between the types of innovations that have been rarely discussed in the research. With the interactive and complex nature of different sorts of innovations, it is difficult to define each sort of innovation and its concept clearly.

Damanpour (2017) while reflecting on the concept of innovation commented that novelty is an element of innovation. New products, ideas, processes, technologies, structure, and way of managing things are the factors that come under the header of innovations. The author stated that innovation can be an organisational plan or a program associated with organisational people. Distinctively, Silva et al.(2018), represented innovation as a term that includes the adoption of a new system, means, programs, practices, services, products, expedients that may come from within or outside the organisation. Innovation is not new to the world; it is new to the organisation. This definition of innovation brings diverse types of innovation into the limelight

that includes all levels of organisations from their functions to the diverse organisational activities. According to Lopes et al.(2017), innovation is an idea that require knowledge. Therefore, it can be concluded that innovation can be either new knowledge or new use of existing products or ideas. It is possible that the use of this knowledge and ideas is new to the organisation but these processes have been implemented elsewhere.

On the contrary, Kahn (2018) presented innovation as a process. The results of the study disclosed that multiple organisations are keen to invest in innovation processes and continue to develop culture and resources that help to develop and implementing new ideas within their businesses for the attainment of their organisational goals. However, Verreyne et al. (2019) discussed innovation as a result of diverse activities adopted by the firms. The study highlighted the development of innovation and focused on explaining innovation as the application of new ideas. On the contrary, Zhao (2016) commented that innovation cannot be something old, it has to be unique and a result of the creation of new ideas.

The research aims to investigate the innovation practices adopted by female entrepreneurs in Algeria. For the attainment of these goals, it is necessary to understand the concepts of innovation or the ways different authors perceive innovation.

2.5.2. Joseph Schumpeter: Theory of Innovation

Josh Schumpeter distinguishes invention and innovation in his research. For him, the invention is the discovery of new scientific and technical knowledge. While innovation is "the commercialization of any new combination from new materials and components, the introduction of new processes, the opening of new markets or the introduction of the new organizational form". Innovation most often comes down to holding a favourable position in its field, and its diffusion allows the obtaining of commercial rights which technically allow the entrepreneur to have a monopoly (Ghiat, 2019). Schumpeter (1934) commented that innovation is of five types. It can be an introduction of new products and product quality; it can be an introduction of processes, opening of new markets, new sources of material, or creation of an introduction of new processes (Correia, 2018). These five sorts of innovations presented by the Schumpeter fall into two broader categories of innovation namely breakthrough innovation and incremental innovation. Incremental innovation, which involves introducing small improvements

to increase product performance or reduce production costs, without fundamentally changing customer habits (Correia, 2018).

In agreement, Sriram and Mersha (2017) stated that the minimum requirement for a change in a company's products or functions to be considered an innovation is that it must be new or result in significant improvement. The main impact of innovation on economic activity results from its dissemination to other actors. By "diffusion" is meant how innovations are spread, through market mechanisms or otherwise, among customers or in countries, regions, sectors and markets. Without dissemination, innovation will have no economic impact (Sriram and Mersha, 2017). It has been further highlighted that the new combination of material and resources is not necessary for entrepreneurs to be innovative and encouraged to start the business. Some entrepreneurs are attracted to try to imitate innovation, directly if it is not protected, or creatively when it is protected. Innovation does not only concern about the development of new products but also covers varied fields such as sales, distribution, marketing, packaging, design, production methods, organisation systems and services for changed processes (Sriram and Mersha, 2017).

The theory contributes to the research by highlighting the different ways innovations can be brought to the organisation. Such as by creating new products, designing methods, by changing old processes to new, and by changing the marketing and packaging techniques.

2.5.3. Everett Rogers: Innovation Diffusion Theory

The theory of diffusion of innovation proposed in 1962 by Everett Rogers explains how an invention evolves at the innovation stage. The theory states that an invention does not secure the position of innovation until its diffusion for economic benefit or benefits. The theory defined five principles that determine the diffusion of innovation and show that inventions become innovation. These five stages that transform the invention into innovation including awareness, interest, evolution, trial, and adoption and some qualities of innovations that influence the rate at which innovation is adopted have been discussed below (Brown, 2018; Umberger, 2016):

Relative advantage: is the degree to which an innovation is perceived to be better than those that already exist. This innovation does not have to have many more advantages than the others, but what is important is that the individual perceives it as being more advantageous. The more the

relative advantage of an innovation is perceived, the faster its adoption rate (Guilluy-Sulikashvili, 2017).

Compatibility: is a measure of the degree to which an innovation is perceived as conforming to existing values, past experiences, social practices and user standards. An idea that would be incompatible with current values and standards would take longer to adopt than a compatible innovation. Similarly, in some cases, the adoption of a compatible innovation will require the prior adoption of a new value system, which can take considerable time (Brown, 2018).

Complexity: is a measure of the degree to which an innovation is perceived to be difficult to understand and use. New ideas that are easy to understand will be adopted much faster than others, which require developing new skills before you can understand them (Brown, 2018).

Testability: consists of the possibility of testing innovation and modifying it before committing to using it. The opportunity to test an innovation will allow potential users to have more confidence in the product because they will have had the opportunity to learn how to use it (Shabbir et al., 2019).

Observability: refers to the noticeability of the results of trying the novel ideas. When results of the innovations are visible and products are appreciated and deliver with advantages to people then they are more adopted and accepted by the community (Shabbir et al.,2019).

This theory of innovation contribute to the researcher's knowledge by communicating that innovation is adopted to add value to things; because entrepreneurs consider that existing things are not adding any value for consumers; hence they tend to introduce new things. The theory stated that there is a reason behind innovation if innovation delivers results and contain benefits such as growth, expansion of the business, or uniquely solving problems then it is greatly accepted (Brown, 2018; Umberger, 2016; Guilluy-Sulikashvili, 2017; Shabbir et al.,2019).

2.5.4. Kline and Rosenberg's "Chain Link" Model Of Innovation

Kline and Rosenberg's Chain Link Model conceive innovation as an interaction between skills available and knowledge on the one hand and the market on the other hand (Oyesola, 2018). Hence, innovation does not rely on the research and development (R&D) activities; it includes the integration of all staff at all level within the organisation. Innovation skills are not only relevant to technological skills but with marketing, designing, and productive organisational

skills as well. These Skills enable companies to successfully implement innovative ideas and take full advantage of them (Hosseini et al., 2020). The model highlights the importance of technology and regarded technological advancements as innovation. The model states that the learning process and knowledge are the factors that help companies to exploit technological opportunities (Pearson et al., 2020). The emphasis of this model has been on the knowledge and information and the ways these both can be used to enhance the absorption capacity of organisations (Arora and Gambardella, 2010). The absorption capacity of the organisations should be strong and internal efforts of research have a positive influence on the absorption capacity of external knowledge that organisations may gain from research firms, universities, and other companies. This model stated that information and knowledge management just not benefits large companies but small companies as well. The model highlights technological innovations as one of the major sources of technological innovations besides knowledge and information acquisition (Debref, 2017).

The theory sheds light on the chain of activities that contribute to development and successful application of innovation. The theory reflects on the skills, technological advancement, and information development as factors that donate to the innovation. This theory has been used to reflect on the importance of skills, information and technology in the process of innovation.

2.5.5. Types of Innovation

Multiple studies have been conducted to explore the types of innovations and these innovations were of two types including product innovation and innovation related to the organisational processes (Najafi-Tavani et al., 2018; Kahn, 2018; Wang et al., 2019). However, the concept of innovation is not limited to processes and products. Wang et al. (2019) commented that innovation can be a new service and products that are known as product innovation. On the contrary, Najafi-Tavani et al. (2018) stated that a significantly improved product can also be innovation with the firms' intended characteristics rather than being a completely new idea. Innovation includes considerable improvements in technical components, features, user-friendliness, functional, and embedded software features.

Conversely, Kahn (2018) reflected on process innovation. The author stated that process innovation refers to the application of substantially or newly improved method to deliver the products or services to consumers. Distinctively, Ungerman and Dedkova (2019) emphasised

marketing innovations and stated that the implementation of new sales methods that include different changes in product placements, packaging, pricing, promotion, and designs. However, Eidizadeh et al. (2017) reflected on organisational innovation and stated that the new method of organising things and conducting organisational activities, and new ways of management practices are some organisational innovation practices. The author stated that this organisation of external and internal information and knowledge is innovation. Temel and Drust (2020) commented that companies should focus on technological innovations as this sort of development enable companies to gain a competitive advantage and drive further innovations by helping the firm in identifying opportunities.

Distinctively, Kohli and Melville (2019) commented that information and knowledge are critical for the identification and implementation of innovation. Further, internal organisational knowledge is not enough for companies to drive innovations and for their successful implementation. In alignment, Demirel and Kesidou (2019) tinted that research and development (R&D) are crucial for technological development and external knowledge can be one of the major sources to deliver companies with effective technological innovation ideas. External environmental knowledge is necessary for companies for obtaining new information and for evaluating and adjusting to the changing demands of customers.

The purpose of highlighting the diverse theories and types of innovation has been to understand the multiple nature of innovation and not restrict the research to any certain type of innovation. The theory contributed to the research by broadens the area of innovation knowledge.

2.5.6. Macro-Environmental Theory

Macro-environment refers to the external factor within the industry in which businesses operate. These factors have a significant influence on business activities and their potential to succeed. Caberera and Mauricio (2017) discussed the macro-environmental analysis for considering the factors that can support or create barriers in the way of entrepreneurial activities. These factors are critical to analysing female participation in the country and most specifically macroeconomic factors discuss the voluntary abandonment or their attraction towards business initiation. The research discussed that macro-environmental factors define the country's situation the level of unemployment and alternative opportunities that exist in the business environment of countries. Minniti and Naunde (2016) highlighted that external analysis highlights the market opportunities,

innovation systems, and research and development (R&D). The research disclosed that negative economic situation push females to enter the entrepreneurial world and start with the things they do not even have skills.

Batsin et al. (2017) stated that female entrepreneurship has significantly increased during some years and has a huge contribution to business success. Despite having growth, it has been assessed that female entrepreneurs are lower in all economies compared to men. This is the factor that drives the attention of people towards the factors or possibilities that may influence the female entrepreneurship negatively. The study highlighted that macro-environment of countries play a significant role in the success or failure of female entrepreneurial activities. While discussing the macro-environmental factors the research highlighted that socio-cultural factors are effective in highlighting the gender gap and defining the barriers that female entrepreneurs face in the male dominating societies.

In the same context, Acharya and Pandey (2019) discussed that macro-environmental factors play a critical role and defined these factors through PESTEL analysis tools. The research disclosed that socio-cultural factors play a role of barriers in the way of female entrepreneurship. The study revealed that political uncertainties, lengthy documentation, corruption, non-conducive, and uncertain policies are some of the major factors that donate as barriers to the success of female entrepreneurship.

The theory contributed to the research by highlighting the factors that can encourage entrepreneurs to do innovation and also can create barriers to the ways of innovations. These factors are necessary to understand to ensure successful innovation.

2.5.7. Thorstein Veblen's Theory

According to Thorstein Veblen's Theory, competition is critical in the capitalistic economy to gain success. The theory stated that modern business era due to globalisation contains competition that is necessary to address to be successful (Plotkin, 2018). The theory states that the businesses that develop or innovate can be easily copied by their rivals. The theory considers the market system as contention and pecuniary rivalry because of the competition in terms of money. The theory emphasis on technological development and states that business due to the high competition adopt new technologies that help entrepreneurs to come up with new products

and processes. The theory states that people only buy a thing for enhancing their status compared to others; hence, adding value for customers is necessary to remain competitive (Plotkin, 2018).

The theory contributed to the research by highlighting competition as an important factor that can negatively influence the innovations and reduce the advantage for firm as rivals imitate the concepts.

2.5.8. The Human Capital Theory

HUMAN CAPITAL

Figure 1: Human Capital Theory; Source: Marginson (2019)

The human capital theory states that humans are important for innovations and their knowledge building is crucial. Trained and developed human capital is full of skills and contains an ability to contribute to the implementation of innovation and the generation of an idea. Skilled and qualified employees tend to develop the organisational competitive advantage more frequently than the one that is not experienced and skilled. Hence, it is essential to enhance the skills and competencies of humans (Marvel et al., 2016).

The theory tinted on the importance of human capital a role in the process of innovation. The theory also reflected on the ways human capital can contribute to bring innovations within the organisation. The theory contributed to the research that how human capital can bring innovations to the business and helps them in gaining competitive advantage.

2.5.9. 4-Way Customer Criteria Theory

4-way customer criteria to add value for customers is an effective business theory that helps entrepreneurs to develop and determine four key criteria to help the business to make a decision about adding value to customers. This theory allows entrepreneurs to emphasize four dimensions to increase or create value for customers. The financial value ensures the supply side of the products, functional value enables entrepreneurs to enhance user satisfaction, the energy value require a business to reduce energy and improve indoor comfort to deliver maximum value to customers. The strategic value requires a business to improve investor satisfaction (Barcelo-Valenzuela et al., 2018).

Figure 2: 4-way customer criteria to add value for customers; Source: Barcelo-Valenzuela, et al. (2018)

The theory contributed to the research by highlighting the four criteria on which entrepreneurs can develop and produce their competitive advantage. The theory provides direction to

entrepreneurs and guide them that how innovations can be used for creating energy value, strategic value, functional value, or financial value for customers.

2.6. R&D model of Service Innovation Theory

Figure 3: R&D model of Service Innovation Theory; Source: Wolfe (2016)

Wolfe (2016) argued that companies that heavily invest in R&D can able to compete in the market. The R&D model of service innovation theory proposes that to effectively adopt or use the R&D methods the organisation needs to integrate them into various functional units of business. Hence, there is a significant relationship between theory and research findings. Both perceptions agree that R&D investment could derive from innovation and competitiveness.

The theory highlighted the importance of Research and Development (R&D) for boosting the level of innovation within the industry. The theory contributed to the research by defining that how entrepreneurs can enhance the capabilities of their staff to innovate things through Research and Development (R&D).

2.7. The theory of Experimental Learning

The theory states that experience is one of the major sources of learning. The learning environment that includes instructions, the involvement of people, self-interest, initiation, and evaluation by learners is better for entrepreneurs. The theory states that right skills can be only developed by the programs that can help learners in gaining knowledge according to their needs (Koyana and Mason, 2017). The theory states that threatening situations encourage learning thrust. Self-initiated learning are lasting. The theory states that for the adoption of innovative practices, it is mandatory that learners are interested in. Experimental learning is crucial to develop staff for innovation.

The theory contributed to the research by highlighting the value of experimental learning. The theory helps supporting the facts that individual's interest in learning new things is necessary for building on innovation.

2.8. Hofstede Cultural Theory of Innovation

Countries' determinants related to entrepreneurship have been actively discussed by many researchers who focus mainly on macro-environmental factors, including culture.

Jackson (2020) stated that through time; a lot of efforts have been made by researchers in order to be able to measure culture. One of the most important works is the Hofstede's Cultural dimension, where the basic values are set as power distance, individualism, masculinity, uncertainty avoidance, and long-term orientation. The author sheds the light on two main concepts impacting female entrepreneurship including attitudes and values. Attitudes can be defined as a set of a specific reaction to a specific situation by individuals. Values are set by a group of people for individuals according to their location and status. Oppositely, Crespo (2017) voiced on culture and defined that it is a set of beliefs, values, and expected behaviours that a specific group of people shares in a deeply unconscious and embedded way that shapes the organisation of the social, technical and political system. Rahbek (2018) argued that these sets of values and beliefs affect the way individuals define their behaviours in terms of risk-taking, proactiveness or independent judgment and their willingness to become self-employed.

On the contrary, Hacinoglu (2014) highlighted one of Hofstede's shortcomings. The author stated that Hofstede's work does not demonstrate the connection between culture and

entrepreneurial activity independently and stresses that entrepreneurial culture favours a positive social manner towards the entrepreneurial approach as well as a bigger tolerance for failure. Thus, culture enables the acceptance of the role of the entrepreneurship in the economy. Later studies, based on the mentioned shortcoming, tried to link countries' cultural dimensions with entrepreneurship. El-Hamidi (2017) attempted to demonstrate the relationship between entrepreneurship and the national culture by stating that culture with lower uncertainty avoidance and higher individualism is the most favourable for entrepreneurship activity as well as innovation. In alignment, Hacinoglu (2014) stated that countries with the culture of high uncertainty avoidance have countless legislations and laws for better control, which will result in individuals tending to simply take over existing businesses with existing products and market shares. Such cultures are barriers to innovations and entrepreneurial activities. According to Block and Walter (2017), in low uncertainty avoidance culture, individuals tend to be more risk-takers and at the same time, they would be more innovative in a decentralized hierarchical structure and would benefit more from higher economic growth in culture high in individualism. Conversely, Akram et al. (2017) highlighted the masculine and feminine dimension of culture and stated that in male dominating culture, female struggle to secure entrepreneurial opportunities.

Figure 4: Hofstede cultural dimension theory of Algeria; Source: Hofstede Insights (2020)

The theory contributed to the research by highlighting the importance of culture. The theory contributed to the research by describing the fact that how cultures of entrepreneurs influence their orientation of innovation.

The National Culture of Algeria in light of Hofstede

Berrouiguet (2015) noted and mentioned that the Algerian national culture chart is not available in Hofstede's works. The results of this study indicate that the culture dimensions scores are: Power distance 5.36/10, Collectivism 7.12/10, Uncertainty avoidance 8.6/10. Accordingly, the Algerian national cultural dimensions are medium power distance, high collectivism, and high uncertainty avoidance. However, these dimensions have changed with time, as mentioned by Hofstede Insights (2021), the power distance is high in the country, individualism is low, masculinity culture is high, uncertainty avoidance is more than 55%, while long-term orientation is extremely that indicates extremely difficult environment for female entrepreneurs that contain multiple cultural challenges (Hofstede Insights, 2021). These results may imply that the national culture in Algeria, at the time of the study. The environment of the country is not favourable for female entrepreneurial activity and innovation. However, considering the evolution of

entrepreneurship in Algeria, discussed earlier and the country's changing environment, to be discussed later, the finding out of this specific study may be irrelevant. Moreover, Crespo (2017) demonstrates that empirical studies present mitigated results as per the relationship between the national culture and the entrepreneurial activity. It, further, states that it is not possible to talk about a single that promotes entrepreneurship, but instead several entrepreneurial cultures.

2.9. Importance and Drivers of Innovation within Female-Owned Businesses

According to Audretsch et al. (2019), innovation practice is a mindset or a way to do things in a different way than add value in the organisational products, processes, or services. Innovation practice is the one that is unique and creative to the businesses. Innovation practices are critical to adopt for businesses for their sustainability and competencies. Innovation practices are perceived as a ladder for businesses and perceived as a source of competitive advantage because these practices contribute to increased organisational productivity. According to Biemans and Griffin (2018), services innovation is significantly different from product innovation practices. It has been assessed that in services firms, managers tend to manage less explicitly for innovations as compared to product firms. It has been assessing that B2B service firm is less sophisticated in their practices of innovation. Service firms favour incremental innovations with the increase of radical projects. Innovation is not only the introduction of new products, innovation practices also refer to the practices that are used for improving the manufacturing and services. On the contrary, Audrestch et al. (2019) commented on innovation and defined it as a positive change within the business. The author stated that the purpose behind the implementation of innovative practices is the increment in competencies and long-term performance. Lounsbury et al. (2019) reflected on the number of practices that companies use to drive innovations. The study stated that the use of technology is an innovative practice that companies adopt to share information and knowledge, introduce and idea finding approach, encouraging innovations as organisational culture, and reviewing processes for training people for creativity and novelty. The adoption of innovative practices is a way to be ahead of the competition and stay sustained.

Some drivers of innovations that have been highlighted in studies have been mentioned below:

Growth/Expansion of Business: According to Bianchini et al. (2018), innovation practices include internal and external research and development (R&D), product innovation, process innovation, and external sourcing. The study highlighted that innovation is strongly associated

with organisational growth. Firms adopt innovative practices to facilitate organisational expansion. The study concluded that innovation practices tend to influence organisational growth. Firms for having growth adopt heterogeneous innovation strategies and often choose to adopt a different combination of innovation practices or activities. Similarly, Maradana et al. (2017) tinted on the positive role of innovation practices on organisational and economic growth. The authors reflected that the major reason for innovation practices is to boost organisational growth of companies that ultimately influence the overall economic growth of countries. On the contrary, Lacruz and Jaaskelainen (2018) emphasised on the explanation of diverse growth strategies that companies use to grow or expand the business discussing the Ansoff Matrix. The authors stated that Ansoff Matric is a way to define diverse innovation approaches to expand the business. The authors stated that companies to grow their businesses attempt to adopt the diverse processes and practices of innovation. The study commented that innovation includes the introduction of new products or services, companies may not attempt to introduce new products but improve the version of existing products. Innovation practices may include the introduction of new products for new markets. Loredana (2017) agreed with the concept and adoption of Ansoff strategies as innovation practices for growing the business. The author also highlighted that sustainable or green practices are some innovation practices because they encourage customers to be responsible and buy from socially responsible businesses that enhance the sales and therefore business growth. Khajezadeh et al. (2019) agreed with the concept of Ansoff matrix as innovation practices that companies adopt as growth strategies.

Adding Value for Customers: Kleinsmann et al. (2017) reflected on innovation practices and stated it as a way of adding value. The study highlighted that innovation practices are a combination of diverse innovation activities and a process that is based on four stages such as identification of the opportunity, analysis of identified opportunity, idea creation, selection, and concept and technological development. The results disclosed that one of the major reasons for adopting innovation is to add value for consumers or customers. Distinctively, Barcelo-Valenzuela et al. (2018) highlighted the importance of customers' knowledge and tinted that developing customer knowledge within the organisation is an innovative practice because it allows companies to incorporate things that satisfy the need of the consumer and add value for them. Understanding customers' needs have become one of the major priorities for companies to innovate things to meet the customers' needs and maintaining customer loyalties. In

differentiation, Helkkula et al. (2018) commented on service innovation and stated it as a way of adding value for customers. The study highlighted that innovation practices tend to generate a competitive advantage for firms. Some other practices that help to boost value creation for customers include the involvement of research and development (R&D), planning for better initiatives, and combining the integrative approaches. Siakas and Siakas (2016) reflected on market orientation as an important aspect of innovation practices. The authors highlighted that product and service innovation is a way of creating competitive advantage and adding value for customers. Open innovation is a process of integrating value in the processes that also reflects on customer products and services. It has been assessed that innovation practices rely both on external and internal ideas of creating innovations and value for customers. Open innovation is a practice that communicates that internal ideas can be taken to the market through different channels. Online social networks are specific suitable channels for creating value for customers in the light of open innovation (Siakas and Siakas, 2016).

Gaining Competitive Advantage: Gaining a competitive advantage is a mandatory requirement for companies for assuring business survival. Distanont and Khongmalai (2018) examined that companies adopt innovations to gaining competitive advantage. Entrepreneurial businesses tend to focus on innovation practices because of their competitive advantage. Using the external factors for bringing innovation is crucial that helps companies in generating competitive advantage. The business environment is uncertain and entrepreneurs need to prepare and adapt the changes for their survival. Innovation practices have become a strategic tool for improving competition and creating and enhancing the competitive advantage. The competitive advantage is a driver of innovation practices and sustainable developments. Similarly, Anwar (2018) stated that in the era of globalisation and dynamic business environment, firms look for the competitive advantage and for their survival they use diverse resources and sources. Innovation is a driver of firms' superior performance and growth. Innovation has a significant positive influence on the performance and competitive advantage that lead firms to increased financial position.

Anning and Dorson (2018) agreed with the facts that innovation is a way of generating a competitive advantage and strongly associated with it and organisational leadership plays a mediating role between these two factors. Competitive advantage is a driver of innovation. Companies to stay in the lead of successful businesses need to do something different and this

differentiated advantage helps firms in staying competitive. Therefore, it can be said that companies adopt innovations for having a competitive advantage. Oppositely, Salunke et al. (2019) proposed a comprehensive framework of services innovation that can lead businesses to competitive advantage. The study highlighted a knowledge-based perspective. The study commented that service level entrepreneurship is a driver of external and internal knowledge. Knowledge is an integral part of the overall process of innovation that leads companies to generate competitive advantage.

Solutions to Problems: According to Akoum (2016) shed light on the need for innovation and research and development (R&D). The study stated that the need of finding solutions to the problems is one of the major factors that drive innovation and research and development (R&D) activities. The research concluded technological advancements as one of the major aspects of innovation and presented it as a way of solving business problems and helping in the growth process. Kulikova et al. (2016; 2017) stated that innovation is an introduction of new and competitive products; innovation practices include structural changes, active technical and scientific policy, promotion of advanced research and development activities and breakthrough technologies. The study concluded that these innovation practices can have a huge influence on the scope and production structure of products and services that helps companies in their problem solving as well. On the contrary, Hautamaki and Oksanen (2016) reflected on the idea of sustainable innovation. The study stated that innovation practices include the introduction of constructive ideas which is relevant to the wicked problem-solving. The need for solving problems demand companies is innovative in their practices. As the business dynamics are changing, the drivers of innovation as well. Kahn (2018) stated that organisations need to innovate their processes, policies, and new approaches to uncover the potential of innovation. One of the major transformations that occurred in the concept of innovation is that companies for resolving their marketing and operational problems tend to transform their innovation practices from economic and technological to sustainable innovation. The study presented sustainable innovations as practices that may help companies in balancing the long-term process influence and output with the need of societies, environment, economy, and people. Further, Wolfe (2016) commented that sustainable innovations also encourage the inclusion of all people within the decision-making process that enhance their efficiency in solving business issues and resolving problems for better performance.

The section highlights the drivers of innovations for entrepreneurs. The section contributed to the research in a way that it defined how different factors drive the thrust of innovation amongst entrepreneurs.

2.10. Empirical Studies

2.10.1. Factors contributing to innovation practices adopted by female entrepreneurs

Technology: Technological advancements are one of the key practices of innovation. Technologies are interactive and cumulative. Technology sort and accumulate information that donates to the success of firms by helping them in generating competitive advantage. According to Wage et al. (2020), technologies disrupt industries that result in business innovation. Boitnott (2019) reflected that intelligent systems are designed to create data, use, analyse and observe the data for performing certain tasks. Technological systems are one of the major innovation practices that companies can use to enhance their business performance. Artificial intelligence is relatively a new phenomenon that donates to the success of businesses and helps them in making entrepreneurial decisions. It has been assessed that big companies by using advanced technological systems drove their growth and innovation (Boitnott, 2019). It is essential for the executive that they incorporate innovations and entrepreneurial mind-set in their organisations and for instilling this mind-set the use of AI is a viable and competitive option. Garbuio and Lin (2019) and Valter et al. (2018) in their work highlighted the importance of advanced technologies for driving growth and success. The studies stated that technological advancements are better ways to support innovative practices and lead entrepreneurial activities to gain more results for firms. Inversely, Nowiński and Kozma (2017) in their research highlighted that block chain technologies are critical to driving innovations. The study highlighted the block chain technology role in affecting and disrupting the business model. The study highlighted that this technology may influence the diverse dimensions of the business and prepares companies for the possible disruptions that may contribute and value for customers. Ungureanu and Ungureanu (2016) highlighted the dual perspective of innovation. One is from the perspective of firms that use technology for innovation and the second from the perspective of suppliers who provide knowledge and technology. It has been assessed that innovation management is collective efforts and technologies have a strong association with innovations. Differently, Mills and McCarthy (2016) highlighted the role of technologies in filling the gaps that exist between knowledge and

skills of employees. The study highlighted that technological innovation play a critical role in the success of businesses by helping them on bridging their gaps. Process development and better customers' management for attracting them are some of the key benefits of technological advancements.

Research and Development (R&D): Research and Development (R&D) is one of the major sources of innovations. It allowed companies to produce and acquire new knowledge. According to Sun (2020), R&D is a mandatory part of innovation as it helps to define new ideas and bring technological innovations within the business. The author highlighted the importance of business intelligence systems as a technology that helps companies in their research and development (R&D) activities for encouraging innovations and productivity. The study highlighted R&D as a supporting tool for promoting business performance and generating competitive advantage. On the contrary, Wolfe (2016) highlighted the importance of R&D for identifying the trends and themes. The researcher stated that for sustainable innovations and staying competitive in the industry, it is essential that companies keep their eyes on trend so they can better fill the demand of their customers. R&D activities allow companies to gather information from diverse sources and use this information for making effective business decisions that ultimately lead companies to increased productivity and performance.

Distinctively, Zhu et al. (2016) emphasised on open innovation and stated that this strategy affects the speed of new product development. Open innovation is a practice that supports businesses in their new product development and R&D is a supporter of open innovation practices because open innovation includes the collection of new information and transforming the gathered information into meaningful knowledge development. Guerrero-Villegas et al. (2018) stated that research and development (R&D) facilitates innovation practices and help entrepreneurs in generating new ideas by keeping them aware of the external factors that can influence the business. R&D is critical to better understand the factors that donate to innovation and show the connection between performance and innovation. R&D helps entrepreneurs to understand the sustainable practices and their use for generating competitive advantage.

According to Khoshnevis and Teirlinck (2018), stated that large companies have comparatively had easy access to resources so they have support in the case of innovation failure. The study highlighted the importance of R&D for the development of innovation. The study highlighted

that SMEs may not have enough resources to support their R&D that reflect in their organisational outcomes ultimately. Hence, it is mandatory for being competitive and successful that companies invest in their R&D function. Oppositely, Honarpour et al. (2018) reflected on the need for innovation and emphasised that for survival, companies must not let their competition win and get an edge over them. Innovation is the only way to have a ride and be ahead of the competition. Innovation is an inevitable process and driven by R&D process. In another word, R&D is an antecedent of innovation. In addition, Ferraris et al. (2019) stated that when companies are involved in R&D, they can have an awareness of factors that are influencing the business, awareness of the demands people have in the market, and gaps. These companies take these gaps as opportunities and build their entrepreneurial competencies on those gaps to fill the needs of their customers. Hence, R&D is a mandatory process in the way of innovation because R&D helps companies building their knowledge that lead companies to try something new (Ferraris et al., 2019). It has been recently observed in Algeria that female entrepreneurs are in a position to play a role of higher positions such as managers and entrepreneurs.

Human Collaboration: Human collaboration is often described as essential to the survival of companies, innovation, especially when it is done with external partners, relies more and more on organizational changes but also managerial practices and new tools (Bergeret al.,2019) The authors suggest that organizations develop their innovation capabilities by learning to work better with their partners. According to Bernstein and Turban (2018), human collaboration can only work if it is real within each of the organizations concerned. In light of the latest analyses and good practices observed in the field, the book highlights the individual, organizational, and inter-organizational skills, that facilitate collaboration is better to invent and bring innovation within the organisation.

In the same way, Iglesias and Ind (2017) stated that top-down approaches are not enough to build relationship between brands and consumers or general management and their employees. Collaborative innovation creates new postures to mobilize collective intelligence. By encouraging teamwork and interaction, the company is in a positive dynamic. This approach fully meets the current challenges of designing customer experience and employee experience. It is no longer just a question of selling a product or providing a service, it is necessary to propose something more. The authors commented that the integrated environment is a source that

enhances relationships, reduces conflicts, and increase creativity and innovation within an organization. Employee communication and coordination help most of the employees to be motivated to give their best and to be honest. Motivational employees tend to give their best and contribute to the innovation process (Iglesias and Ind, 2017).

Differently, Khawam et al. (2017) highlighted the role of team work and commented that for the success of the project, the teams play a key role. Individuals are no longer expected to play a role that teams can. Teams through collaboration contribute to the development of the innovation culture through their actions, their collective behavioural qualities, and their know-how. In the logic of co-construction where people with different profiles, skills, and motives meet, the teams are attentive; create a climate of goodwill to encourage freedom of expression (Khawam et al., 2017). Collaborative Innovation is a creative approach that, however, responds to specific project management methods. The challenge is to put in place the organisation that facilitates teamwork, thereby increasing cohesion while channelling energies to avoid a too intense proliferation that ultimately is not productive. There is no single method; each company must organize itself with the help of reference systems, for example, to find its proper functioning (Khawam et al., 2017).

According to Rasiah (2019), the benefits of collaborative innovation are valued not only in socio-economic performance but also in the tremendous capacity for openness and synergy of skills that are useful for transforming organizations and associated managerial practices. The process of merging back together is first of all internal; too many companies still work in isolation.

Liao et al. (2017) commented that organisations by collaboration and coordinating with stakeholders can bring as many relevant reflections as possible and can enhance the innovations within the organisations. The Collaborative Innovation allows combining the different approaches, each one shifts his point of view of the prism and can propose an innovative idea and can help firms implementing innovations.

Stegen and Wankier (2018) commented that collaborations are not affected by gratitude interventions. Collaboration and coordination enhance the amalgamation of different qualified and skilled employees. These employees share their perspectives about the problems and present their ideas for solving the existing problems. The teams provide a pool of ideas that can help businesses in the contemporary world, to enter into logic of co-competition.

2.10.2. External Factors Influencing Innovations

Some of the external factors that can significantly influence entrepreneurial activities include political factors, the economic situation of the country, socio-cultural environment of the country, technological factors, and legal factors.

Political factors: The Algerian socio-cultural change is to be observed through political changes bringing more democracy, educational changes resulting in the country investing heavily in education and economic changes such as the open market. Those factors shifted the socio-cultural life, attitudes as well as behaviours of entrepreneurs. These statements can be confirmed through the work of Tahir (2016), stating that by the '80s traditional, cultural, social, political and legal barriers made entrepreneurship mainly a men's activity. Further, Warrick (2017) commented on the political environment of Algeria. The authors stated that for female entrepreneurial activities, the political culture of Algeria is not supportive. There is a strong relationship between political forces and entrepreneur's adaptation for innovation. Strict regulations of Algeria and low measures to support overall entrepreneurial activities in the country are some of the major barriers to the entrepreneurship. Isaac et al. (2018) agreed with the fact that the political environment of countries has a strong influence on entrepreneurial development. There is a need that governments to support the entrepreneurial environment checkmate and monitor the policies and development environment.

Financial Factors: It is agreed upon the literature that long-term growth and productivity have a positive correlation with investment in innovation. However, because of the nature of innovation activities and their uncertain outcomes, it is often difficult for entrepreneurs to deal with it (Isaac et al., 2018).

A study conducted by Efthyvoulou (2016), on 40000 innovative firms across Europe has shown that the ones facing financial constraints have considerably more chances to be less successful. This study, furthermore, precise that the financial constraints are having a heavier impact on the ability to innovate mainly when they consist of internal funds rather than the availability of external sources of finance.

Samoilikova (2020), distinguished that the financial constraints impacting the ability and success of innovation in business. The study stated that the financial system of the country has a strong influence on innovation processes. The study highlighted that the financial systems to deal with

innovations differently when it comes to the productive sector and service sector as the first ones are said to be more sensitive to these types of constraints. Financial support is required to encourage innovations within the country.

Randhawa and Scerri (2015) stated that due to the nature of innovation, service sector can rely on collaboration with other organizations for example -which doesn't require internal funds- whereas the production sector needs to have a certain investment in research and development - which requires internal funds. The countries that do not invest in their entrepreneurial environment, their organizations may have smaller productivity and financial performance, which puts them in a sensitive position to surmount the retrospective costs of innovation.

On the contrary, Tian et al. (2019) highlighted the importance of finance and put financial factors as one of the top list elements impacting a business's innovation. In this sense, a study suggested policies should be put in place to promote access to external sources of finance to organizations especially when they have limited internal funding such as the service sector, on one hand, and provide some incentives to promote the use of innovation and the collaboration.

Similarly, Manresa et al. (2018) reflected on the importance of finances and stated that countries to develop entrepreneurial activities in their country should focus on developing effective and efficient financial policies. Further, Duque-Grisales et al. (2020) highlighted the importance of training and development (T&D) and stated that these activities demand a high budget to train employees. Firms with financial constraints are unable to train their people; hence, lack of entrepreneurial activities.

Economic factors: According to Boufeldja (2014), the overall literature generally agrees on the fact that Algeria is experiencing a deep socio-cultural change since the 20th century. This well-investigated change is a result of a succession of events. In 1830, Algeria knew French colonialism that lasted for 132 years. In 1962, following its independence, Algeria had experienced an economic crisis leading to a suppressed socio-economic situation considerably impacting on the working culture (especially regarding female and their role). Later, until the '70s, the country knew an economic expansion followed by an economic crisis due to the oil prices' drop which led to the closure of numerous enterprises. To arrest the situation, Algeria adopted the strategy of promoting and encouraging entrepreneurship. In this sense, Crespo (2017), confirms the U-shaped relationship between the economic development and the

entrepreneurial activity, economic development can foster and support entrepreneurship activity only when combines with certain sets of national dimensions. This view supports that the economic development state would affect the entrepreneurial motive: necessity/opportunity. However, the actual changing climate, as depicted previously, is changing views and attitudes towards entrepreneurship in Algeria.

Mosbah (2014), highlights that Algeria -as well as several MENA countries- has opted for new laws and initiatives to support entrepreneurship and SMEs have grown significantly but still not to the expected extent. The majority of the recent literature agrees on the challenges facing SMEs, nowadays, in the Algerian environment, as established by Korichi (2015) related to informal businesses creation, financial constraints, administrative constraints, barriers linked to the availability of information, and managerial/institutional challenges.

Socio-Cultural factors: Cheraghi et al. (2014), tried to work on this exciting gap through a comparison between female entrepreneurship in traditional cultures and secular-rational culture. The study looked at female entrepreneurship as related to growth expectations through two dimensions: Micro-level, including networking, and macro-level, including culture. The finding out of this study validates that culture indeed affects entrepreneurial behaviour and the fact that entrepreneurship is mainly opportunity-driven, however, female entrepreneurs tend to be less educated in traditional cultures –such as Algeria-, than in other secular-rational cultures. On the contrary, Felipe et al. (2017) found out that female tend to have extensive capabilities in this particular culture. As a result, considering the relationship between those variables, the study concluded that female in traditional cultures have higher growth expectations for their businesses. The study highlighted that male and female are equal and contain similar capabilities to innovate and become entrepreneurs. Abadli et al. (2020) argued that Algerian culture is mainly dominated by the traditional approaches that might not allow female to easily participate in society and perform their activities as an entrepreneur. Aldrich (2017) discussed the fact that majority of female in the country are young and tend to be involved in the entrepreneurial activities the age of these females is less than 40 years which is a positive sign for the country and the country and will contribute to the entrepreneurial success of the nation. In alignment, Udanoh and Zouria (2018) concluded that the majority of female in Algeria is not more than 40 years and fall between 25 years to 35 years. The study highlighted that there is a need to build a

culture and political environment to support female entrepreneurship because despite having significant development in the ratio of female entrepreneurship, female participation in the country is extremely low that must be improved (Udanoh and Zouria, 2018). Hence, the government needs to develop strategies and design approach that can effectively enhance the female entrepreneurial activities in the country.

Maha El-Swais (2017) found that female behaviour and attitude are highly affected by the local culture linked to the Arabian traditions and Islam that hinder the freedom for female as compared to males. Furthermore, being an entrepreneur female need a strong capacity and personality to manage the attitudes and behaviours of individual in complex situations. The psychological qualities such as perseverance, patience, communication, decision making, and human, material and technical issues along with adopting the unforeseen changes are highly required by the female entrepreneur.

Lounsbury et al. (2019) found that female in Algeria are essentially known for the sentimental characteristics. They are mainly affected by others and recognize their challenges or difficulties to encounter the issues that are often left for the men. The evidence that the female become the entrepreneurs in Algerian society mainly determines that there is a change in their personality as the modern female. The study found that female need to focus on developing the characteristics of the entrepreneurs to effectively start their business and contribute in the economy through creating jobs. This concept support research in understanding the current innovative entrepreneurs practices to increase the business performance.

Human Capital: Human factors play an important role in the adaptation and implementation of innovative practice. Innovation happens mainly through people producing ideas and knowledge in their surroundings, yet it is hard to set up a relationship that links a set of skills to the success of innovation. Humans play a critical role in the success of companies and serve them as an asset. Defining innovation is a challenge without human capital; human capital is a source of competitive advantage for companies and tends to inform innovations (Marginson, 2019).

Although the literature distinguishes a link between education, skills, and innovation performance, this correlation is not causation. It is not formally affirmed yet whether poor skills lead to poor innovation and development, or whether poor development leads to poor education and skills. For the sake of shedding light on this matter, Berger et al. (2019) suggests a further

study to take place, using surveys on entrepreneurs to question the skills required by employees and their relation to the firm's performance.

Adom et al. (2016) distinctively highlighted the optimization of the use of innovation activities; one of the major conditions is to have a great amount of educated human resources. This is even more emphasized in middle/low economies countries where an "innovation gap" needs to be caught up -by duplicating innovation activities carried out in ore advanced countries for a beginning. The latter fact puts a bigger emphasis on the importance of a large well-educated workforce that would be able to replicate the existing technologies and transfer them.

Similarly, Fix (2018) affirmed that an amelioration of the human resource by educational means along with R&D activities enhances the company's ability to absorb which leads to better know-how in terms of innovation. Furthermore, despite the unconfirmed link between education, skills, and innovation performance, it has been observed that weaker economies tend to focus on technology transfer rather than R&D which could be completely abortive in case the required human capital is not present. This leads to the conclusion that weaker economies are prone to this chain of circumstances where, on one hand, there are no incentives for the youngster to carry on higher education and develop their skills but, on the other hand, poorly educated and skilled employees' disadvantages companies in terms of innovation, impacting on their growth, leading to slower economic growth.

Competition: The debate on the link between innovation and competition began in 1943 with the thesis of Schumpeter, which states that competition reduces the monopoly rent and therefore the incentive to innovate (Singh and Gaur, 2018). However, many economists are against this theory, including Arrow who, twenty years later, shows that the incentive to innovate is stronger in a competitive market.

Sicard (2017) highlighted the thought of Schumpeter (1934) and stated that the author considers that innovation is temporary. Once its cycle ends, a fundamental innovation appears, and around it develops a cluster of incremental innovations, which together will create a new good or a new process. This explains the term "destructive innovation". In other words, one innovation replaces another. The innovator who invests in research and development (R&D) is hoping to obtain a monopoly, allowing him to recover costs incurred and make a profit. Following this reasoning, according to Schumpeter, competition is bad for innovation because it will reduce the monopoly

situation and therefore the incentive to innovate. Schumpeter's vision "legalizes" in a way the monopoly and thus goes against the politics of competition (Sicard, 2017). For him, the monopoly is the form of enterprise that can encourage the most entrepreneurs to innovate. In other words, competition does not promote innovation because the entry of competitors reduces the monopoly rent that an innovator expects to acquire to recover costs and make a profit. Naranjo-Valencia et al. (2019) demonstrated that the incentive to innovate is greater in a competitive market than in a monopoly market. Indeed, the greater the intensity of competition, the more companies will be encouraged to innovate to survive and stay in the market (Naranjo-Valencia et al., 2019). The "replacement" effect presented by Arrow states that the monopoly has less incentive to innovate than a competing firm because the profit differential is smaller. In other words, competition favours innovation. This vision is opposed to that of Schumpeter.

Many economists will try to demonstrate the true form of this relationship. Negassi et al. (2019) discussed the framework of analysis. They assume that a firm in place where they face the entry of competitors. A major difference between these models is the definition of the discovery process. Negassi et al. (2019) assume that leading to the conclusion that monopoly has more incentive than a potential entrant to innovate and goes even further. Crowley and Jordan (2017) assessed that innovation and competition are strongly related to entrepreneurial activities. More recently, it has been set that the effect of increased competition on firms' incentives to innovate depends on their behaviour, whether they are confident, impatient, rather combative or discouraged. The behaviour of a firm is determined by its level of efficiency relative to that of its competitors. Crowley and Jordan (2017) demonstrated the existence of the effect of selection and adaptation of competition on innovation. The authors stated that competition encourages innovation. In other words, an increase in competitive pressure increases the investment of each active firm in process innovation, to improve their productivity and remain competitive. However, if competition induces more process innovations in the industry, it reduces the number of product innovations present in the industry as a whole. Finally, Tallman et al. (2018) stated that competition is not good for innovation as it discourages entrepreneurs by reducing the monopoly. The entrepreneurs are motivated by profit maximization; it would seem possible to argue that increased competition can stimulate incentives to innovate in product and process innovation. However, the threat that intense competition reduces the profitability of discourages entrepreneurs to enter the industry and make innovations. On the other hand, Cusumano et al.

(2019) reflected on unfair competition and stated that this is one of the major limitations to innovations. For encouraging innovation the competition must be fair and there must be some standards that should be followed so the fair competitive environment can be encouraged.

2.11. Further barriers to innovation

Tahir (2016) mentioned that most of the previous works have been looking at the barriers and difficulties facing entrepreneurs -including female entrepreneurs- in their entrepreneurial journey, particularly the financing difficulties. An emphasis is made on the fact that female are more likely to face barriers during both the creation and development of their businesses. Kevehazi (2017) accepted that female are naturally present at the highest levels of social and economic hierarchies, their power and security are still secured by men and men-managed structures. The reasons behind this limitation in the previous works on female entrepreneurship have been studied and researched. Campaña, et al. (2020) agreed on the fact that the focus on entrepreneurship in developing economies is for the promotion of growth, the effects on household welfare, and the reduction of poverty. Female entrepreneurship has evolved from the 1970s to present and a series of events pushing them to fight for their rights, for their place in the workplace, and their recognition as entrepreneurs (Minniti, 2010). According to Cabrera and Mauricio (2017), entrepreneurial activities of female have increased over the past decade to about two-thirds the level of men.

Despite this willingness to play a role in the business world and the increasing number of female entrepreneurs, according to Kevehazi (2017), the extension of female roles, which occurred in the last century, did not bring along the transformation of male roles. The necessity or need to earn money is still a secondary social expectation in the cases of female in several countries, in addition to the compliance with the family obligation. Furthermore, according to socialization and some stereotypical views, female are emotional beings that are not enough for a business, incapable of making rational decisions, are impressionable therefore unsuitable for an executive role and/or they prioritize private life. Kazumi (2017) confirmed these views and found out that general social expectations linked to the role of female in a society largely affect their self-assessment. In the same way, the regarded social legitimacy can, indeed, impact the entrepreneur's competence; thereby enhance the venture's performance.

Further, Kazumi (2017) also confirmed and stressed on the female entrepreneurship and characterized it differently by highlighting the differences from men's entrepreneurship. Moreover, in different communities, it can also distinguish alterations within female entrepreneurs themselves as well as between female engaged in entrepreneurship as compares to the ones who are not. It can be concluded, from the above, that female entrepreneur is a complex and versatile phenomenon and that the study of its uniqueness and efficiency is still convoluted.

2.12. Benefits of Innovation Practices to Female-owned Businesses

The role of female entrepreneurship has been studied multiple times and their contribution to economic success has been discussed significantly (Block et al., 2017; Garba and Kraemer-Mbula, 2018). However, developing countries lack such knowledge. Therefore, it is necessary to highlight the potential benefits of innovation to entrepreneurial businesses. According to Rosa and Sylla (2018), female entrepreneurs having low profitability compared to male employees, but it is a fact that females are more likely to be innovative compared to male entrepreneurs. It is a fact that entrepreneurship tends to send a positive influence on the economic development of countries because entrepreneurial businesses contribute to innovation, productivity growth, and job creation. Entrepreneurs succeed in the business world based on their innovations and these innovations are of diverse types such as technological innovations, product innovations, services innovations, and process innovations that open new market for companies to take advantage of opportunities. Innovations enhance the productivity of female businesses by enhancing their competitive level in the market. On the contrary, Jabeen et al. (2019) highlighted the factors that support female entrepreneurship and innovation practices. While discussing the factors of innovation practices the researchers disclosed that financing is one of the major criteria that influence their decision of innovation practices. The reason for investing in innovations is the introduction of practices that can enhance organisational productivity and growth. Innovation practices contribute to the competitive advantage of companies that motivate them to innovate things. Wang et al. (2019) stated that innovation practices are critical for the business and deliver them with the benefit of competitiveness and sustainable development; entrepreneurs adopt innovations for boosting their profitability. According to Paul et al. (2017), entrepreneurial businesses can take advantage of product and service innovation for gaining and competitive edge over their rival and achieve global recognition. Innovation practices enable entrepreneurs to have further opportunities in the business world to sell their products. Verreyne et al. (2019)

commented that entrepreneurial businesses have fewer resources than become a barrier to the way of their innovation. Malik et al. (2016) stated that innovation practices promote companies to adopt new and modern technologies and produce better services and products. The increased level of product enhances the supply and delivers firms with improved productivity and therefore profitability.

Pashaeypoor et al. (2016) commented that the thrust of innovation allows companies to enhance their knowledge and human capabilities. The efforts that companies do for getting the innovation culture within their firms are some of the major pillars to firm competitiveness. Innovation serves as a driver of many other competitive things within the entrepreneurial business that reflects enhanced entrepreneurial competencies. Innovation builds an environment that encourages positive employee attitudes that helps satisfying customers. However, the incremental knowledge of employees enables companies to overcome the challenges. Mohammadi et al. (2018) highlighted the completely different aspect and emphasised on the adoption of evidence-based innovation practices. The study disclosed that in the adoption of evidence-based practices, the chances of innovation failure are less. Innovation influences the employees' behaviour, their attitude, and their knowledge. By influencing the employees, innovation make them capable of doing things that can help companies in overcoming their challenges. On the contrary, Adam et al. (2017) reflected on the pricing and promotional innovation and stated that with effective marketing strategies, pricing and promotional innovations tend to deliver companies with a competitive advantage. The study also highlighted that marketing innovations tend to benefit female entrepreneurs more quickly as they may help them in promoting the quality of their products and services. According to Lee et al. (2019), creativity and innovation are the factors that help businesses in enhancing the customer's satisfaction by improving the quality of products and services. Marketing and management innovations allow companies to improve their processes that help companies in gaining positive customer feedback.

Shi et al. (2016) stated that innovation delivers companies with a sustainable competitive advantage by helping them in improving their product and services quality. Innovation practices affect both normal and active quality. Innovation practices tend to improve the product quality and therefore the market performance of entrepreneurs.

2.13. Potential Actions to Improve Female Entrepreneurship

Pashaeypoor et al. (2016) highlighted the importance of developing the entrepreneurial spirit and stated that companies must focus on building an entrepreneurial environment. The study highlighted that for building an entrepreneurial spirit, there is a huge need that corporative efforts are done and employees are encouraged for their innovation efforts. In consent, Jebari, (2016) stated that organisations need to build an innovation and incentive culture. It has been assessed that the support for technological advancements and recognition of cultural factors on which niches can be developed are the ways to boost innovations and encourage female entrepreneurship and growth of their businesses.

Distinctively, Ungureanu and Ungureanu (2016) commented that on the broader level the awareness of entrepreneurial technologies should be enhanced. Besides McGuire (2019) commented that the incorporation of appropriate subjects in the Institutions of educations can be a one of the biggest support for encouraging entrepreneurial activities. Pearson et al. (2020) stated that technological awareness should be enhanced between people so they can better use the technology to enhance their productivity and profitability. The positive outcomes may encourage more female to take initiatives and enter in the entrepreneurial world. Mosbah (2014) for boosting innovation suggested strengthening the partnership between companies. The study suggested that companies alone may not come up with the solutions and they may need more resources. Building an effective partnership can be one of the major factors that may donate to the innovation process and help them in making successful.

It has been assessed that training and development (T&D) are important entrepreneurial aspects. For making female entrepreneurship successful and encouraging the innovation skills for their success and development, T&D is necessary for companies. Hence, T&D programs to train people should be designed and introduced (Panda, 2018). It has been assessed that female entrepreneurs in Algeria lack in the entrepreneurial spirit. Hence, to overcome the issue entrepreneurial programs should be introduced at the national level and universities to improve the entrepreneurial culture and encourage future innovation projects within the country (Panda, 2018). On the contrary, Anand et al., (2018) highlighted the importance of recruiting the right talent and hiring skilled and educated people for making entrepreneurship a success business. The study emphasised that entrepreneurs alone do not run their businesses, human resources is

an important factor and recruiting and training employees play a critical role in the success of such companies. Skilled employees are crucial to take the advantage of technological innovations and run entrepreneurial enterprises successfully. The research also highlighted the importance of research and development and stated that it is important to provide employees with training and development program so employees can able to implement the technology and understand the innovation.

According to Mohammadi et al. (2017), entrepreneurs need skilled, educated, qualified staff and diversity can help in achieving these goals. Recruiting diversified workforce is determinant of innovation. Stegen and Wankier (2018) highlighted that lack of skilled employees are one of the major barriers to the success of entrepreneurship. Hence, employees must be trained and developed. Katsantoni (2019) supported the fact that skilled employees are critical to bringing innovations in the workplace. Buffart et al. (2020) highlighted that selection is a crucial function and donate significantly to the firms that encourage innovation. It has been assessed that formal selections ensure that businesses receive sufficient support that help firms addressing entrepreneurial growth objectives. There is a need that the participants are encouraged to participate collaboratively and willingness. The study highlighted the entrepreneurial support at national level provided by the government. The study outcomes suggested that government to promote entrepreneurs should promote the skill development plans and should introduce policies to boost innovations. On the contrary, Hotho et al. (2018) highlighted that favouritism in recruitment and selection as one of the major problems that can be a significant barrier to the success of entrepreneurs and may not let them reach to effective innovation. The study highlighted that some strategies to cope-up favouritism should be adopted by entrepreneurs to reduce favouritism.

The overall literature generally agrees on the fact that Algeria is experiencing a deep socio-cultural change since the 20th century. This well-investigated change, as developed by Boufeldja (2014), is a result of a succession of events. In 1830, Algeria knew French colonialism that lasted for 132 years. In 1962, following its independence, Algeria had experienced an economic crisis leading to a suppressed socio-economic situation considerably impacting on the working culture (especially regarding female and their role). Later, until the '70s, the country knew an economic expansion followed by an economic crisis due to the oil prices' drop which led to the closure of

numerous enterprises. To arrest the situation, Algeria adopted the strategy of promoting and encouraging entrepreneurship. In this sense, Crespo (2017) confirms the U-shaped relationship between economic development and entrepreneurial activity, economic development can foster and support entrepreneurship activity only when combines with certain sets of national dimensions. This view supports that the economic development state would affect the entrepreneurial motive: necessity and opportunity.

Tahir (2016) stated that the Algerian socio-cultural change is to be observed through political changes bringing more democracy, educational changes resulting in the country investing heavily in education and economic changes such as the open market. Those factors shifted the socio-cultural life, attitudes as well as behaviours of entrepreneurs. The research indicates that by the '80s traditional, cultural, social, political and legal barriers made entrepreneurship mainly a men's activity. However, the actual changing climate, as depicted previously, is changing views and attitudes towards entrepreneurship in Algeria. Mosbah (2014), highlights that Algeria -as well as several MENA countries- has opted for new laws and initiatives to support entrepreneurship and SMEs have grown significantly but still not to the expected extent. The majority of the recent literature agrees on the challenges facing SMEs, nowadays, in the Algerian environment. Further, Korichi (2015) established statements related to informal businesses creation, financial constraints, administrative constraints, barriers linked to the availability of information, and managerial/institutional challenges.

2.14. Conceptual framework

The research conceptual framework has been designed based on the literature review. This conceptual framework illustrates the way female entrepreneurs evolve with their enterprise and the way they can reach their growth expectations with efficient use of innovation. From the literature review, the basic notion of business creation can be summarised as follows: For being entrepreneurs some specific attributes are crucial. The entrepreneurs themselves evolve and develop in the micro-environment through networking, considering the culture on a macro-environment level. It has also been established in previous research that female entrepreneurs have high growth expectations, as it has been accepted that innovation helps entrepreneurs grow and develop and female entrepreneurs tend to show new ways to resolve issues and provide opportunities to their employees to show their entrepreneurial sides compared to males.

Here is where this framework is linking all these pieces of work, and highlighting how the entrepreneurs, with their attributes in the micro and macro environment with their high growth expectations, can use innovative practices (through factors including finance, technology and human resources) to achieve their potential growth.

Figure 5: Conceptual Framework: Source: Self-made

The conceptual framework presents the variable of research. It illustrates both the dependent and independent variables of the research. The above theoretical framework presents the micro-level entrepreneurial attributes; networking and culture are the key factors that affect the innovative practices. The explanation of some variables is discussed below:

Entrepreneurial Attributes: Brown (2018) mentioned that entrepreneurs should have a certain set of skills and competency that help them in grabbing the innovative practices and opportunities. The key attributes of entrepreneurs include risk-taker, motivator, creative, persuasiveness, versatility, risk tolerance, flexibility and decisiveness. These attributes mainly contribute to supporting and adopting innovative practices (Neumeyer et al., 2019).

Networking: According to Panda (2018), the successful entrepreneur is often based on developing relationships and networking to determine the current trends and innovative practices. The networking can be obtained through developing a relationship through social media such as Facebook and Twitter.

Culture: Organisation culture is an important element that encourages adaptation and implementation of technology and innovative practices (Neumeyer et al., 2019). For example, the decentralised organisation structure and positive workplace behaviour, employee empowerment is likely to quickly adopt innovative practices as compared to an organisation with a complex culture.

Innovation Practices: Technological advancements, process advancements, introduction of new products, new services, marketing strategies, and operational procedures.

Byrne et al. (2019) mentioned that to successfully adopt and implement the innovative practices entrepreneur need to determine different sources. It is the dependant variable of research. The innovative practices include entrepreneurs to assess and determine financial resources, availability of resources. It essentially requires human capital, growth experiences, targets for growth and technological capital to implement innovative practices.

2.15. Chapter Summary

The purpose of this chapter has been to reflect on the innovation theories and practices adopted by female entrepreneurs to support their business growth. It has been assessed that the Algerian entrepreneurial industry evolved through several stages from 1962 and still evolving. The general entrepreneurial environment of the country is not supported for entrepreneurial activities despite having multiple efforts. The country needs to cross a long bridge to be a sufficient country for encouraging entrepreneurial level in the country. It has been assessed that the Algerian youth is getting aware of the benefits of entrepreneurship and interested in opening their businesses, but the country's government is not supportive as the government in the country is unable to offer significant funds for the promotion of education and generous welfare programs. Though the country has moved from a traditional state to the centralisation, the Algerian culture of the country is still negative and the attitude of families is pessimistic for female entrepreneurs. Considering the increasing level of unemployment, the government of Algeria is making significant efforts to promote entrepreneurship within the country, but major steps are still required. The chapter discusses theories to guide female entrepreneurship and reflected on the concepts of innovations. The chapter discusses Joseph Schumpeter's Theory of Innovation, Everett Rogers's Innovation Diffusion Theory, and Kline and Rosenberg's "Chain Link" Model of Innovation. The chapter discusses multiple types of innovations that

entrepreneurs can use to enhance their entrepreneurial business growth such as product innovation, process innovation, marketing innovations, organisational innovation, and technological innovations. The chapter highlighted information and knowledge as critical factors to boost innovation. The chapter highlighted the importance of Macro-environmental factors to encourage innovation and identifying the opportunities and potential threat for female entrepreneurs. The macro-environment of the country includes a social culture that influences entrepreneurial businesses significantly. To highlight the cultural aspect, Hofstede Cultural Theory of Innovation has been discussed that define the weak culture of Algeria for female entrepreneurship. It has been realised that female entrepreneurs are more innovative than men and some major reasons of adopting innovation practices include growth and expansion of the business, adding value for customers, finding solutions to problems, and gaining competitive advantage.

The empirical part of the literature reflected on the innovation practices that influence female entrepreneurs and it has been identified that technology, research and development (R&D), and human collaboration and coordination are some of the supporting factors for female entrepreneurship. Some barriers to female entrepreneurship can be a negative political environment, financial constraints, economic situation of the country – it can have both negative and positive influence on female entrepreneurship, social environment, and lack of human skills. It has been assessed that non-skilled and unqualified people are some of the major barriers to the success of female entrepreneurship. Increasing competition has both negative and positive influence on entrepreneurial efforts. The literature also suggests some potential actions to improve innovations and entrepreneurial landscape within the country including effective recruitment and selection practices that do not include favouritism, the introduction of training and development (T&D) programs, building an incentive culture to promote innovations, and research and development (R&D).

3 Chapter 3: Research Methodology

3.1 Introduction

The fundamental purpose of the research methodology is to discuss the research activities and the adoption of the adequate research methods to be integrated into the research.

Therefore, this chapter will include the description of the chosen research design and the different research stages and methods, through engaging the research onion. The adequate justifications will also be provided based on the selected research tools and methods, followed by the development of the research strategy, data collection techniques, sample size, and the ethical considerations.

3.2 The Research Onion

According to Cronholm & Hjalmarsson (2011) research onion is one of the frameworks available to adopt research methods and techniques to accomplish the research objectives and to answer the research questions. In other words, it is known as the methodological framework, describing the major processing layer, which is to be present in the research performance, i.e. the research philosophy, the research approach, the formation of the research strategy, selection of the research choices, and the declaration of the time horizon. It also supports in providing range of data collection and analysis methods, which further comprehend the research identifications (Gast and Ledford, 2014).

In order to carry this study, the methodology has been designed based upon an adapted research onion, illustrated below, as the different aspects of the research methodology have been studied, and have been organised into layers accordingly.

Figure 6: The Adapted Research Onion; Source: Saunders (2009)

3.3 The Research Purpose

De Langhe and Schliesser, (2017), state the significance of the research purpose and believe that research purpose actually sets the stage for the entire research. Whether the researcher is exploring the phenomenon or describing the concept, the purpose of the study helps in deciding on the other important aspects of the research methodology.

The exploratory research as seen by Hair (2015), is initiated based on the theoretical or the hypothetical ideas, resulting in the formation of new knowledge paradigms. Ang (2014), furthermore considered it to be used as groundwork for a specific subject where little is known or studied. This type of design is used to generate qualitative information through an in-depth level investigation of a set problem. In this study, the focus was on a firm and deep understanding of female entrepreneurship in Algeria and the innovation practices related to it (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). As it has been understood from the literature review, this specific subject is still under studied in Algeria; therefore, certain amount of flexibility is required in order to be able to conduct the research objectives in this kind of situations. Furthermore, the exploratory research design allows the creation of new ideas and theories through the use of reviewing the available literature and data collection involving interviews, questionnaires and case studies (Yin, 1994).

Explanatory and conclusive research purpose was not required mainly due to their nature. According to Gast and Ledford, (2014), the conclusive research design is integrated when there is a practical need for a decision making. For this sake, it is based on a quantitative approach and a deductive thinking through the gathering of data from a large sample. Also known as causal research, the explanatory research is used when the focus is on the investigation of cause/effect relationships between variables (Mertens, 2014). In other words, it is used to measure the impact of a change in a variable on a controlled variable. In order to achieve such results, explanatory research relies on a quantitative approach through the use of experiments.

3.4 The Research Philosophy

In simple words, as stated by Vian Ahmed (2016) the research philosophy is the researcher's representation of the ways data should be collected and used in a particular research. This data, primary and/or secondary, will be collected for the purpose of knowledge creation by answering the research questions.

O’Gorman et al. (2014) illustrated that there are four types of research philosophies, which are mainly based on the nature of the goals and the objectives of the research: Pragmatism, positivism, realism, and the interpretivism philosophies. This research utilizes interpretivism philosophy. Al (2013) states interpretivism is allowing a focus on qualitative rather than quantitative knowledge with the involvement of the interpretation of elements of the study. According to Carson (2001), the main principles of interpretivism are that the researcher is linked to his research and cannot be isolated as well as the world cannot be anything else but meanings and understandings on different social and experiential levels.

Interpretivism is believed to be the most appropriate approach as it relies heavily on naturalistic methods (interviewing and observation and analysis of existing texts) and therefore held in aligning the nature of the study with the adequate data collection methods (Tumele, 2016).

The desired outcomes of the proposed research dealt with the effectiveness of the innovative practices adopted by female entrepreneurs in Algeria which coincides with the essence of this philosophy: To look at what are individuals' actions, what barriers are they facing and how do they deal with it. Through this research we aimed to understand a phenomenon which female entrepreneurship as linked to the use of innovation practices. Also, knowledge to be generated

through the outcome of this research was more about meanings rather than set laws which implies an interaction between the researcher and the subjects. This particular knowledge is also relative, as the researcher needed to consider factor such as time and culture (Marshall, 2016).

There are authentic reasons for avoiding other philosophical stance. As stated by Mark Saunders (2009), pragmatism philosophy only supports concepts that are related to actions. This research philosophy doesn't believe in a single way of generating knowledge as only one point of view would be limited and provides a narrow picture. Realism, on the other hand, is based on the fact that the world exists independently from human mind (Sekaran, 2016).

3.5 The Research Approach

The different research approaches are differentiated on the basis of the relationship of the hypothesis to the research. An inductive approach, as defined by Karen Soiferman (2010), enables the generation of new theories which process would imply observation, set patterns and then establish a theory. According to Cho and Lee (2014), the inductive approach is mainly involved when there is the performance of the qualitative research and it involves the open grounds for the formation and the acceptance of the new theories.

Furthermore, in term of strategy, this approach owes more to phenomenology and the research approach can be inductive when the data is collected, and theory is developed as a result of data analysis (Saunders 2000). In this study the research questions were developed, research strategies were designed, and research questions were answered accordingly to generate untested conclusions which coincides with the logic of the inductive approach. The latter allowed the researcher to generalise from specific to general for theory building, which fits the presented research's purpose (Eriksson and Kovalainen, 2015).

Also, the intended use of the data collected in this research is to discuss a phenomenon – set as female entrepreneurship-, establish themes in order to elaborate a framework. This purpose fits in the principles of the inductive research approach.

A deductive approach, as per Gratton and Jones (2009), allows the researcher to test hypothesis that have been pre-set. In other words, the process of a deductive approach would imply set hypotheses, test those hypotheses and then confirm/reject those hypotheses. Also, this research

approach owes more to positivism and it is emphasised when the theory and hypothesis are developed, and a research strategy is designed to test the hypothesis (Houghton, 2011).

3.6 Research strategy

The presented piece of work aimed to investigate a certain phenomenon – the use of innovation practices- within a certain group of people -Algerian female entrepreneurs-. The case study allowed an in-depth and real life understanding of the situation through the diversity of data collection tools that can be used when conducting a case study such as observation, interviews and document review. This is an important research strategy which allows the focus on individuals or group of people to gather the data required, generally used in case of infrequent situation. It is also usually put in place to gather a qualitative type of data (Johnson, 2014).

It has been largely warned not to associate this research strategy with researches meant to follow a scientific approach as it is said to be non-scientific. This strategy has also known critics mainly based on the doubt that the results can be generalised, or to which extent it can be done. In the same way, it can be challenging to set an exact and precise causal relationship when using this strategy.

Despite all the criticism around it, case study is still an asset when it comes to collect detailed, rich and in-depth data. It is generally conducted when it is challenging or impossible to have a large sample of participants with the exact same characteristics.

3.7 The Research Design

Based on the work of Guba and Lincoln (1994), there are two methods of research available for researchers: Quantitative and Qualitative. The most crucial difference between the two approaches is the use of numbers and statistics. The choice of research approach naturally depends on the defined research problems and the data needed for solving these problems (Hammersley, 2009).

The qualitative approach emphasizes on processes and meanings that are not measured in terms of quantity, amount, intensity or frequency. It provides a deeper understanding of the phenomenon within context (Guba and Lincoln, 1994). When there is little theoretical support for a phenomenon, it may be impossible to develop precise hypotheses, research questions, or operational definitions. In such cases qualitative research is appropriate because it can be more

exploratory in nature (Sullivan, 2001; Cited by Darabi et al.), and this is the main motive towards the adoption of a qualitative method for the current research.

Researchers using this quantitative approach emphasize the measurement and analysis of casual relationships between variables. According to Cochran and Dolan (1984) that relate the differences between qualitative and quantitative research to the distinction between exploratory (qualitative) and confirmatory (quantitative) analysis.

3.8 Data Collection

This step of the research consists of the gathering of information from the different available resources in order to provide answers to the research questions. There are two types of data to be collected: secondary data and primary data.

Secondary data

This type of data relates to any information that has been previously published around the topic. This could be in books, journal articles, magazines and online documents. Certain set of criterions have to be met in order to insure the reliability and accuracy of those published information such as date of publication, quality of the information and peer reviewing (Teddle and Tashakkori, 2003).

The secondary data will be collected from various sources such as published articles, books, official websites, official statistical websites and other online resources. While collecting the secondary data, researcher will ensure the validity and reliability

Primary data

We can distinguish between two main data collection methods as far as primary data is concerned, and the choice of one of them for a specific research heavily relies on the nature of the research aim and objective as well as the research questions (Forthofer, 2003).

The proposed research is explanatory in nature, as justified previously. It was, moreover, dealing with individuals and real-life business situations which cannot be supported by a quantitative method. Hence, it was supported by case studies and more specifically exploratory case studies. This method allowed the researcher to illustrate the complexity of the female entrepreneurship in a particular environment, set as Algiers, at a specific time. This has been achieved through the

exploration of the organizational practice of the organizations, in this case focussing on innovation practices (Onwuegbuzie, 2004). This type of data collection method deals with non-quantifiable aspects such as meanings and emotions. Qualitative data collection insures the researcher to reach an in-depth understanding of the subject through means which the most popular are interviews, case studies and focus group.

Moreover, interviews have been used and more specifically semi-structured interviews. This allowed detailed information to be collected as there is a chance to correct and redirect the flow of the interview through its process. Careful precautions were, however, taken to avoid any kind of bias that would be misleading as the researcher needed to have a neutral reaction to answers, respect privacy of individuals involved, and stay open minded (Creswell, 2003).

The interviews were audio-recorded, and a field notes folder created to be able to store notes about the impressions and non-verbal information along with details about observations. It is believed field notes were a strong reminder of the situational factors.

3.8.1 Population and Targeted Population:

The population for this study accumulates Algerian female entrepreneurs. The population for the study remains unknown, due to the fact that there cannot be a definite number for female Algerian entrepreneurs in the country. Nevertheless, the overall targeted population encompasses only those female entrepreneurs who are available on the social media and can be contacted easily (Lombardo, 2016).

3.9 Sampling Method:

According to Richey and Klein (2014), the sampling is defined as the strategy to select the sets and subsets of the population which are under observation and review in the research. Hence sampling is an essential phase in the research strategy which acts as the research tool to diminish the population so that the resources could be effectively managed. There are two various kinds of the sampling technique, that comprise non-probability and probability sampling techniques (Gentleset al., 2015).

According to Bernard (2012), probability sampling technique has high utility whenever the population is known and is easily accessible. Unknown population is the situation whenever the researcher can realize that population comprises of a specific and definite number. In the

situation where the population is unknown or cannot be easily accessible, then the non-probability sampling technique is applied. Unknown population represent the Algerian Female entrepreneurs that can be in hundreds and thousands across the country and since the size of the venture is definite, therefore the population remains unknown. Consequently, researcher has applied non-probability sampling technique (Morgan, 2007).

In this research, the researcher has used random sampling technique that is depending on selecting the subset of the statistical population through which each respondent has equal chances of being chosen. This is highly effective and simple technique that does not include any difficulty. In order to ensure the validity and reliability or making research error free Respondents has been selected randomly from the population (Richey and Klein, 2014) as long as they fit into the sample criteria. This approach ensured the unbiased representation of the group. Moreover, the random sampling is simple and cost effective. The random sampling technique has been used through considering the disadvantages (Tayloret al.2015). A systematic sampling technique was implemented to select the female respondents from Algeria that constituted the sample type as well. It must be pointed out that the limited financial resources at the researcher's disposal cannot be allowed and permitted for maximum sample (Brannen, 2005).

3.10 Sample size

The sample size is determined through there aspects, the margin of error that could be tolerated the level of certainty which the characteristics of the data gathered show the population, the type of analysis to be carry out. In addition, the final sample size is a concern of judgment as of calculation because of the limitation above (Neuman, 2000).

In order to meet the objective and purpose of the research, the researcher has selected the sample of 15 cases of SME organizations created and owned by female in Algeria. The target was to spend a minimum of two days in each organisation in order to get access to documents, observe everyday working process and to interview at least two persons in each organization, aiming one to be the CEO and the other one to be an executive or an employee. This amount would allow in-depth and information rich cases and assist in evaluating and analysing the significant and negative influence on female entrepreneur (Campbell, 2002).

Contacting sample respondents

The sample size for this study is restricted to Algerian female, as the matter of fact, number of diverse ways shall be used to contact them. First, social media shall be used to contact respondents. Social networks including, Facebook that has been used to search for Algerian female entrepreneurs' groups or associations and get in touch with them. Furthermore, Algerian female present in researchers' universities and who are active in the academic research about female entrepreneurship have been contacted through their e-mail or platforms such as Researchgate. Moreover, a database provided by the Algerian Ministry of Commerce has been used to have the list of established SMEs.

Each time, the potential participant was contacted via email, with an introduction to the researcher and the study. A brief description of the process was giving along with contact details and an invitation for a telephone conversation. During the telephone conversation, more details are given, and plans are made for the organisation of the data collection.

Another technique that has been combined is snowballing method where female entrepreneurs that have been conducted were referring other potential organisation that could take part in the research (Gill and Johnson 2010).

There have been many issues in contacting the respondents. First of all, acquiring database from the government agency was a difficult task itself. Due to the pandemic, the time constraints, online processing, and waiting process took lot of time. Secondly, contacting the participants and asking them to participate in the research was automatically a hefty job. Many of the respondents did not respond, many respondents responded that they have stopped working and venture is not alive anymore, few told that they have sold their venture to a third party. Some of the sent emails went to email addresses that were not working anymore. Nevertheless, the technique that actually worked was the snowballing technique through which most of the respondents were asked to participate in the research. The process of sending email and Facebook messages allowed the researcher to acquire around 4 respondents, rest of the respondents were contacted through the snowballing technique (Gill and Johnson, 2010).

3.11 Data Analysis

Aforementioned that this research acquires qualitative data that is in the shape of opinions, arguments, ideas, concepts and expressions, therefore relevant software is used for data analysis

i.e. Nvivo. This is the software that requires the researcher to put in the transcript of the interviews and then it facilitates in realizing the themes from the words that are put in the software. Nvivo also helps the researcher in identifying the main clauses in terms of sentences, words, or phrases that the researcher has then used in the findings and analysis. Nvivo has aided in overall findings and analysis (Gill and Johnson, 2010).

Data transcription

Converting all the gathered data into a written form in order to make sense of it and end up with coherent and meaningful information. As the interviews were mainly in French or Algerian dialect, a translation also needed to be made from these languages into English.

Data organization

This step eased the analysis and help in time management. This can be possible by always going back to the research objectives and organizing the collected data accordingly. An optimum way of realising this step in by creating tables, with columns dedicated to the research objectives and data to be placed accordingly. Nvivo software has been used in order to facilitate the data organisation process.

Data coding

This step implied the categorization, or the labelling of the data into themes and ideas. In other words, attribute titles to sets of ideas using Nvivo software. Then, the researcher identified common patterns and themes according to those codes using his own critical thinking and analytical skills.

Data summarization

The last step consisted of linking the findings to the original research objectives and presenting the overall.

3.12 Time Horizon

We can distinguish two types of studies in terms of time horizon: cross-sectional studies and longitudinal ones. Some studies do require the researcher to collect the data over different period of times or two points of time in order to be able to achieve the research objective, and in this

specific case, the study is longitudinal. However, when the research is to be completed in a one specific period of time, it follows an across-sectional time horizon, which is the case of the proposed study which is to be completed between (Gill and Johnson, 2010).

This research was conducted as partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of Doctorate in Business Administration with a restricted research phase. Indeed, this study is to be carried on between November 2017 and November 2019. This is a reason why it is considered as across-sectional.

Activities	Time in Months							
	1 - 3	4 - 6	7 - 9	10 - 12	13 - 15	16 - 18	19 - 21	22 - 24
Deciding on the topic								
Constructing literature review								
Finding the Gap								
Deciding on the research methodology								
Acquiring data								
Writing Transcript								
Findings								
Conclusion								
Revision								

3.13 Ethical Consideration

The current research was concern to few ethical issues. As discussed in research strategy and sample size selection, all respondent reported their acceptance in written form that addresses

their participation in the research. At the same time, the data collected from secondary sources such as journal articles and publishers were also confirmed that the data was real and ethical.

Next to this, the participants were also fully informed related to the research objectives, while there were not worrying that their answers were managed as confidential and can be used for the academic research purpose only. In addition, except from the above, the participants were not forced, abused or harmed, both psychologically and physically, during the research conduction (Black, 2006).

3.14 Methods for Ensuring Trustworthiness and Authenticity

Researcher has assured trustworthiness by complying with credibility, transferability, dependability and conformability. Considering the credibility, researcher has sought the respondent validation (Creswell, 2003). Researcher after the transcript and running the transcript through the Nvivo, sent the findings to the relevant respondents in order to acquire the respondent validation. Researcher has also maintained thick description. Thick description is the rich details of the data acquisition processes, the raw form of interviews, the transcript, the details of how the respondents was approached, emails and replies of emails in order to have a rich account of the details. This has allowed the researcher to acquire the opportunity to acquire possible transferability of findings to the other relevant areas (Morgan, 2007). As far as the dependability is concerned, researcher has kept the complete record of the study. Feedback received from the supervisors, transcript, interviews, drafts made and rejected and other important relevant data has been kept safe. Moreover, researcher throughout the research processes has remained unbiased and did not allow the personal values or theoretical inclination towards the research. The questions prepared for the interview was made sure that there are not leading; they are not double barrel and are simple and easy to understand by the respondents. Researcher through remaining mostly silent during the answer recording has assured being unbiased (Gill and Johnson, 2010).

4 Chapter Four: The Algerian Economy and Entrepreneurial Environment

4.1 Introduction

The people the Democratic Republic of Algeria is a predominantly Muslim country located in Northwestern Africa and shares borders with seven distinct nations in that region. Algeria was founded on 5th July of 1962, before that country was experiencing French oppression and colons as they possessed significant status and incomes. French colonialism developed intense consequences that significantly influence the Algerian economy as a country involved in trade activities. A brutal fight and war of independence that lasted more than eight years gave Algeria fundamental rights and freedom. Algeria is renowned for its unique and distinctive characteristics as it is the largest country in Africa and the ten largest worldwide. The considerable country size enables people to live in their desired position. Most of the population lives on the Mediterranean Coast, which is approximately 91% of the total population in Algeria (Oxford Analytica, 2020). Algiers is the capital city of Algeria which is possessed a total population of approximately 2.8 Million. Algeria contains unique culture, history, customs, and Islamic Heritage, making it sophisticated and an integral part of the most prominent Arab world, including the Maghreb Region of Africa. The Sizeable population of the country is highly associated with unique traditions and cultures. The total population of Algeria is approximately 42,927,878 as per the 2020 statistics. The total area of the country is more than 2.4 square kilometers which also included a sufficient proportion of desert (Kadi&Khelfaoui, 2021). The dominant religion of Algeria is Islam, as a large extent of the population is comprised of Arabs people.

Mihi, Nacer&Chenchouni (2018) Algeria possessed the hottest earth surface and was substantially renowned for intense and high temperature. Sahara desert covers approximately 90% of the total land of Algeria and provides only 12% for inhabitation. On the contrary, the country's debt circumstances are sustainable compared to other nations in Africa. Algeria is a country that possessed no liability and external debt burden. Algeria earns a significant proportion from its exports of fossil fuels and natural gas because it is the world's sixth-largest nation that captivates sufficient reserves. Algeria generates revenue that adds value to the country's GDP. The country was also recognized as a malaria-free nation in 1973 in the whole

world (Springer Nature Limited, 2021). Algerian economy provides numerous opportunities because of its diversified structure. Algeria is a developing nation that is determined to prevail in the entrepreneurial environment as it will assist in enhancing business activities and establish new job opportunities for individuals. Dhahri and Omri (2018), entrepreneurship is the fundamental pillar and emerging trend globally, and nations are adopting this phenomenon for long-term growth and development. But Algeria is still striving to provide specific access to individuals.

In contrast, a debt-free nation also participates in Olympics since 1964 and has won numerous gold medals. The largest country of Africa and the Arab world contributes to Africa as it is the largest nation with higher oil reserves. Algeria's dynamic economic structure allows them to gain certain privileges over other countries in Australia.

4.2 Influence of French and Muslim on Algeria

Algeria's history penetration was complicated as the nation fought against foreign invaders various to protect their freedom and rights. European powers struggling to access and control the Mediterranean Sea of North-South Africa which includes the largest Arab population (Goumrasa et al, 2021). Ottoman Empire implemented tactics to a greater extent to cover the region of North Africa. Among European countries, France developed the foremost foothold to occupy Algeria. France seized Algeria in 1830 and captured access to most areas. Kettor (2019), the Algerian economy experienced severe circumstances because of the invasion of France in the early 1830s. Algeria was ruled by France for more than 50 years. France imposed new regulations and involved Algerian countries to produce commodities that can export to France in the larger context. Additionally, French colonialism affected the industrial system of Algeria as the French was concentrated to produce the cash crops and neglected the major mineral resources of Algeria. The exploitation of these resources was performing to stop the evolution and significant progress of the Algerian people. MacMAster (2020), French government and colonialism system ruined Algerian's economic structure and developed the critical crises for people as torturing people became common. On the contrary, a large amount of the population was forced to leave their houses and moved to the mountains to spend their lives, whereas the traditional democratic system and political leaders were eliminated by the concerned France Authorities to hold Algerian Muslim people's rights. Subsequently, France included Algeria as the province of the

country but no citizenships rights were delivered particularly for the Muslim community (The Guardian, 2021).

France developed their subjects for Algerian people and made complex rules that emerged inferiority complex among the population. Algerian people witnessed devastated crises because of food scarcity and no jobs for citizens. On the contrary, these people were not allowed to live in cities and share a part with France. Davis (2020), Algerian community suffered a lot during France ruling decades because of persistent oppression and higher power influence. Poverty was continuously growing and people starved to deaths. The dominant religion Islam and the education system was also lifted and changed to the Christian French education system. The consequences started to emerge as people were brutally treated by the France authorities. The independence war began in 1954 to fight against France and gained their land back. Algeria gained independence in 1962 after the brutal and hard fight with France rulers. Thousands of Algerian people were died and slaughtered in a dirty war. France claimed that only 5000 Algerian Muslims were killed during and they faced a major loss of lives (El-said, 2018). This major revolutionary situation allowed Algerian people to obtain freedom and fundamental rights of citizenship. France influenced on Algeria was catastrophic as terrorism, poverty, and torture were prevailing in their ruling time. Currently, it's more than thirty years but Algeria and France's relationships developing more complex circumstances for both nations. France's invasion of North Africa was considered as the first colonization of Muslims of the Arab world which shocked the other Arab nations. Algeria is the ten biggest nation in the country which included large Arab population (Vince, 2020). After independence, the Algerian economy recovers the major prospects including the political system, education system, and country's religion.

Islam is the national religion of Algeria as most of the population contained a higher proportion of the Muslim Community. The native of Algeria also practiced Islam as their religion in every prospect of life and circumstances. Muslims of Algeria promote the teachings of Islam that create a significant positive impact on society. The tolerance ratio of religious activities is quite higher in Algeria which gathers people. Algeria is the third-largest country with a higher rate of approximately 99.7% of the Muslim population. Muslim possessed a significant impact on Algeria as state operations and rules have been followed by the Islamic teachings. In contrast, the

political leaders of Algeria always considered the Islamic approaches to control the consequences. Islam plays a major political role to sustain the country's position. The major three views of Algeria's prospects are to consider the Islamic point of view and embrace the teaching of Islam in both public and private aspects of life. The second view is comprised of secular prospects to follow the Islamic guidelines and instructions in convinced and positive deviations. The third view implies perceiving the traditional values from Islamic teachings for rural and elderly communities (Zoubir, 2018). Muslims influence the other communities in Algeria and most of them transmitted to Islamic socialists (Esri, 2021). Muslim practices and Islamic teaching have established a greater influence on Algeria.

On the other hand, the bitter independence struggle and colonial France rule influenced the Muslim community for more than 130 years. Arab Muslims also observed the critical consequences in France's ruling era as these people were treated inadequately with no appropriate division of rights. France's revolution on Algeria's land in 1948 eliminated the business and jobs opportunities for Muslims. Additionally, Islam was also replaced by Christianity which disheartened people as they are not allowed to perform their religious duties. France colonial authorities developed the law that stated the rights of citizenships through excluding the Native people and Muslim community from every sort of rights. The authorities tended to generate the legal category which did not involve the Algerian Muslims. Racial discrimination was promoted by targeting Arab Muslims. Muslims rights and benefits were taken and provided to the other religious people (Vince, 2020). The whole scenario remained identical till the beginning of the independence war. Despite the uncertain consequences, Muslims positively impact Algeria. In contrast, France's influence on Algeria remained negative as Algeria suffered a lot from France's ruling and colonial system implications (Brwon, 2018).

4.3 Socio-Economic Progression in the Country

The economy of Algeria is projected to partially recover in the year 2020 from economic and health crises caused by the corona virus pandemic. As an effect, the hydrocarbon sector is projected to rebound in the year 2021. The economy of Algeria is currently suffering from earning losses and a lower level of business and consumer confidence. The Algerian authority introduces the socio-economy plan of recovery for shifting the economy towards the private sector and sustainable model of business. Algeria is transitioning towards renewable energy for the protection of the livelihoods of the population (Maouche, 2021).

The corona virus pandemic results in the depression of the economy of Algeria in 2020. The real growth of GDP is projected by reduced by 5.5% because of stringent measures of lockdown because of reduction in the production of hydrocarbon where the output of oil reduces below the OPEC quota of Algeria. For instance, the labor-intensive sector, construction, and service across the informal economy, are more profoundly affected and lead to loss of jobs permanently or temporarily (Boufatah, 2021). Furthermore, the reduction in prices of oil is coupled with a reduction in the volume of export and caused a steep reduction in revenue of export of hydrocarbon. Moreover, poverty increases due to the consequences of coronavirus. The other causes of the economic crisis are based on five consecutive slow growth of GDP during 2015 to 2019 across Algeria. It is mainly driven by the shrinking sector of hydrocarbon, and the public-led growth model. The private sector of Algeria is struggling to emerge as a new economic growth engine. The hydrocarbon sector is accountable for 20% GDP, 94% earning from export, and 41% fiscal revenues by 2019 are continuously experiencing a structural decline (Boutayeba, & Ramli, 2019).

Algeria, as other oil-exporting state across the MENA region, is required to progress towards a more diversified economy for lifting the prospects of jobs that are critical for the young profile of the demographic. The present reduction in hydrocarbon recommends that present public spending levels are unsustainable, and designed policies are required to generate additional revenue for maximization of efficiencies and fair spending of the public. The success of structural reforms will hinge upon its abilities for restoration of macroeconomic stability and enacting decisive policies for supporting the development of the private sector, and continuously protecting the highly vulnerable population segment (Nwani et al 2021). In the last two decades,

the boom of hydrocarbon enables Algeria to make advancements in human and economic development. The multilateral debt of Algeria becomes cleared in 2008, and the country invested in the different infrastructural developmental projects for supporting economic growth followed by deployment of redistributive social policies for alleviation of poverty and lead to massive enhancement in indicators of development of humans. Algeria aimed to attain a 97% net enrolment rate in primary education by 2015 with gender parity and lifted the enrolment rate in the higher education field (Benramdane, 2017).

The HCI or Human Capital index provides the baseline on the education and health of children. The HCI value of Algeria is remained constant from 2010 to 2020 with a value of 0.53. This value is greater than the average of lower-middle-income states and far below from average of North Africa and the Middle East region of the World Bank (Boufatah, 2021).

As Algerian authorities decided to take external borrowing, the public debt of Algeria is inevitably domestic. A sharp increase is found after 2016 for financing the deficit born to increase spending and reducing the prices of hydrocarbon. The projection of different macroeconomic indicators is summarized in the below charts.

Figure 7: Macroeconomic indicators

Source: AFDB, 2021

Figure 8: Export Trend of Fuel and Merchandise

Source: AFDB, 2021

The export of fuel and merchandise experienced a fiscal deficit that is estimated to reach 14.8% by 2021 because of the lower revenue obtained from the export of hydrocarbon. The reduction in oil prices further exacerbated the situation. The less demand on export fuel is subjected to a reduction in price and is expected to deplete the foreign exchange reserves of Algeria. It is expected to reach to \$ 44 billion by the end of 2020 with a downward slope as from 2014, as shown in the below chart.

Figure 9: Export Fuel Demand

Source: AFDB, 2021

In 2020, the Algerian government postponed its different social and economic indicators. The Algerian government in 2020 announced the 50% reduction in spending of public and also postponed some socio-economic projects. Certainly, Algeria is suffering from multilevel disparities regarding the region, gender, income brackets. The total unemployment of males in the past few decades has leveled across 10%, while for women, there is 26% unemployment.

Particularly among young females, unemployment levels are continuously rising and widening the gender gap. In addition, Algeria female that aimed to enter in the labor market has minimal chances of being recruited as compared to male counterparts. The unemployment rate in Algeria is shown in the below charts.

Figure 10: Unemployment Rate in Algeria

Source: AFDB, 2021

Algerian state is trying to enrich the regulatory framework of business in favor of females. The Women Business score of Algeria is increased by 17 points in the past few years. However, this score is continuously lagging behind Tunisia and Morocco. The state has shown enhancement regarding the distribution of income. The income inequality has reduced as compared to its neighbor states. With respect to consumption inequalities, the gap between poor and rich reaches up to 28%.

Nevertheless, Algerians are still facing disparities among urban and rural areas. Even though the gap with respect to accessibility in terms of utilities and infrastructure has reduced with the passage of time, some other disparities are still prevailing. People living across the Saharan region in Algeria are suffering from the triple average of national poverty (Bousboua, 2019).

With restricted fiscal space for coverage of financial, national projects, and expenses of government, there is little option for the state to reduce spending and increased more debt financing by means of the central bank. Social unrest is also fuel with the ongoing political crisis. It can be addressed by seeking loans in the long term from foreign lenders. For the achievement of change in the long term, the state of Algeria has been required to priorities in-depth reforms for restructuring of economy away from the dependency of oil and gas (Adler, 2019).

The export of non-hydrocarbon is equivalent to about 2% of overall export. It shows that it is one of the most dependent states of hydrocarbon across the globe. Nonetheless, existing reserves of oil and gas will be depleted by mid of 2050 respectively. Algeria has established the phase of a massive plan of diversification; however, the regime still contains some space for making reforms for delaying such dates of depletion. A probably profitable sector is a tourism that can be worked as an alternative source of a foreign state (Bakari, 2018).

In order to make the state as a lucrative destination to reinforce investment, Algeria is required to heavily invest in accommodation, security and introduce some reforms in stringent rules of visa. Strategic growth can be attained by the promotion of a private-sector model of growth. Recently, the economy of Algeria is following an oversized public-driven model of growth. It has restrained the environment of business for private sector development (Abada, & Bouharkat, 2018).

Souag, & Assaad, (2018) argued that different social constraints that can restrain the opportunities of entrepreneurship and provides the chances for survival of start-ups are critical for the development of sustainable growth of the private sector. It will enable the absorption of the incoming cohort of young graduates for assurance of effective contribution in non-oil and gas-related growth. In the moderate term, the states required gradual diversification across revenue streams, rebuilding fiscal buffers, and ongoing reorientation of non-preference spending.

With respect to the index of Ease of Doing Business, Algeria shows a poor ranking and score as compared to its neighboring state by 20 to 25 points. Algeria is also short with respect to accessibility of credit, having score 181 out of total 190 economies. The score for a business start-up is 152, registering property is 165, and protection of minority investors is 179 (BTI, 2021).

Figure 11: Status Index of Algeria

Source: BTI, 2021

4.4 The current State of SMEs in Algeria

SMEs have become one of the most important aspects for the economies and a hot topic for academic scholars to research on. Internationally, SMEs are accounted for 94% of the businesses with value-adding to the worldwide economy of at least 50%. SMEs are known for driving growth, advancements, and changes in the business sector and provide industries with more innovative solutions. The growth of SMEs is dependent on the knowledge transaction and the creation of critical and planned development events. Economic diversification in the country is the main challenge. The country has been based on the oil industry for many years now. Therefore, diversifying the whole industry is not an easy aspect. The population of the country is more expert in dealing with the oil sector than any other aspect.

The Algerian small and medium-size firms were dealing with various restrictions in the past which limited their growth. Bouazza, (2015) mentioned in their research that the SMEs were not able to borrow more than 30% of the capital investment from the banks which prevented the establishment of small businesses. However, the state of SMEs in the country started improving after 1999s. Bouazza et al., (2015) also mentioned that SMEs constitute 94% of the business networks and generate 52% of the total production of non-oil products in the country. The significant role of SMEs in the economic growth of the country was the reason for increased governmental interest in the sector. In 2013, the number of registered SMEs in the country was 748000 which is at least 99% of the total business ratio in the country. The graph below shows the number of public SMEs in Algeria by sector.

Figure 12: number of public smes in algeria 2019, by sector

(source: Saleh, 2021)

It can be evaluated from the graph that the agriculture industry is more of an interest for the entrepreneurs of the country. It has been stated by Ahmed, (2021) that SMEs in Algeria are operating as the backbone of the economy of the country. However, a considerable number of companies are not big enough to hire more than 10 employees. Of the 1m SMES in existence at the end of 2016, 56.3% were incorporated, while only a small minority of these – just 390 companies – were state-run. The remaining 43.7% were sole traders. The SMEs in the country are supported by the government. In 2011, the government launched a program worth ad380bn (\$3.2bn) to revamp the sector. In 2017, the growth of SMEs increased at least 4% which resulted in 2% of the GDP growth in the country. However, in the last five years, the share value of the industry has seen some fluctuation. In 2016, the share value reduces to 6% from 5% of the previous year. 2018 was the growth of the SME operating in the shoe industry of the country. SMEs are playing a significant role in the growth of the employment rate in the country. In 2016, the sector employed at least 2.5 million people (Yasser & Abdel madjid 2021). In 2018, 4000 new projects were started by SMEs with the potential to create 140,000 jobs in the country. The banking sector is playing a considerable role in the growth of SMEs in the country. The banks are offered financing services in a more commercial and Islamic manner. However, a large number of businesses are interested in gaining benefit from the Islamic finance policies offered by the banks. At the end of the first half of 2018, the number of SMEs becomes 1,093,170, of which 1,092,908 private and 262 public SMEs. After the opening of the economy in 1999s, the number of SMEs actually started growing in 2002 (Haddad et al., 2019). The changes in the business law of the country also contributed to the growth of the SMEs in the country. Algeria businesses are using initiatives supporting employment and youth of the country.

The Algerian government has been investing in export promotion programs to encourage SMEs to enter and be competitive in export markets. The growth of SMEs is also amid the concept of internationalization. However, to adopt the new ways of businesses, SMEs require external support with human expertise and skills which is lacking in the country currently.

4.5 Female Entrepreneurship In Algeria

Women entrepreneurs are an essential part of the business sector globally. There are 252 million who are working as entrepreneurs and 153 million of these women are leading well-established businesses. The rate of female entrepreneurs has increased at least 114% in last 2 decades. In countries like the United States, businesses run by females are contributing more than 1 trillion in economic growth (World Bank, 2021). Algerian culture has not been very much open in terms of women. The country has wanted women to remain at home for many years. Therefore, it is not easy for the female population of the country to suddenly become part of the business sector. The century however has shown a considerable change in the role of women in the Algerian business industry. The number of female employees in the senior positions of the country is increasing. In the view of Ghat, (2016) the Algerian society has gone through social and cultural changes leading to the improvement of women's status in the country and the opening of more opportunities for the female population. One reason for the increased number of women in entrepreneurship was the lack of employment opportunities in the country. There is no doubt that the economic conditions of the country have changed significantly. However, there is still a lack of work opportunities that motivated women to start their own businesses. The hardships of life of Algerian women have motivated them towards education so that they can improve their occupational position. The rate of female students increased in Algerian universities. Women have become so much motivated in the country that they want to have authority and be empowered which leads to the adoption of entrepreneurship. It has been stated by macmaster (2020) that being an entrepreneur required a strong personality and will and the ability to deal with any kind of challenges. Business owners require competencies like patience, perseverance, communication abilities, decision-making, and confrontation of administrative, human, technical, and material problems. The mentioned skills are badly needed for women entrepreneurs.

Women entrepreneurs also require understanding the unforeseen aspects. It has been stated by Anyansi-archibong & Anyansi-archiving (2021) that entrepreneurship became a necessity for women in Nigeria created by the constraints of the socio-cultural environment. Research conducted by Ghiat, (2018) states that most of the women who are involved in the business are married and motivated by the activities of a family member or personal tendencies. It has been stated by Osmani and beloucif (2021) that women are mostly establishing a business in a non-formal environment. For example, 30 percent of women have business in the non-agriculture sector. Home-based businesses are also dominated by women entrepreneurs. It has been stated by Ghiat (2017) that women in Algeria are open to socio-economic and cultural changes and that is due to their proximity with Europe. However, the overall society of the country is not yet very much open towards women-owned businesses. Women are being looked at in pity even when they are working in managerial positions. It is a fact that the culture of Algeria is changing but there is still a long way to go.

There is no doubt that women have become more powerful in running their businesses. However, there are still some obstacles restricting the growth of women in the business sector. The major issue women face when considering their business establishment is the capital. There are various countries in the world that still have negative perceptions of women's ability towards business. Women do not have financial resources and are dominated by men of the family which also prevents them from starting their businesses. On the other hand, women's enterprises are also dealing with limited time and skills. It has been stated by Osmani and beloucif (2021) that there are laws regulating the private sphere specifically those regarding marriage, inheritance, and land. The laws cause a hindrance when it comes to women's access to assets that can be used as collateral when securing a loan. It has been stated by Ghiat (2019) that in a male dominant society, it can be very much difficult for women to deal with men. Men subordinates do not like to take orders from females which make it very hard for women to get the work done. The majority of businesses by women is owned in hiding and has no human resources. Entrepreneurship activities require open communication and mobility which can be difficult in Islamic culture.

5 Chapter 5: Data Analysis and Discussion

5.1 Cross Case Analysis

The interview sessions from different entrepreneurs revealed in-depth and critical knowledge rendering a holistic view of female entrepreneurship in Algeria. The findings from the interview sessions are categorised into different aspects. Each aspect is then analyzed by combining answers from different respondents portrayed as case. The discussion below provides the detail of different themes identified from the basic interview while establishing the cases for the entire research study.

5.1.1 Contribution of Female Entrepreneurs:

While talking to the case one, it is realized that female entrepreneurs contribute to the development of the country. The entrepreneurial environment of Algeria has evolved and become favourable as compared to the past and this statement reflects on the interviewee stated that when she came up with the idea of the school 15 years ago, there were no regulations to support the idea. The changing environment has helped in gaining success in the entrepreneurial journey. Nevertheless, case 2 revealed that women entrepreneurs have faced huge difficulties in a men dominating society like Algeria. Though, there are some ways of getting loans and finances in Algeria for manufacturing businesses and stores, but the ratio of discrimination and corruption is high, these opportunities tend to turn into barriers to the success of businesses. Case 3 has agreed with the stance and claimed that entrepreneurs in Algeria are facing challenges in different industries and sectors. They need to continuously focus on innovation and development to meet the changing needs. Case 10 however, claims that female entrepreneurs face issues on deploying theory into practices that clearly defines the issue of lack of training and development opportunities. The results revealed that financials, societal acceptance, and lack of training opportunities are some of the core challenges that Algerian female entrepreneurs face in the design and art industry. The company can still improve its profitability if the funds are available for training and developing staff at an appropriate rate.

5.1.2 Female Entrepreneurs' Ideas about Innovation:

From the cases, it is understood that different female entrepreneurs have firm believe that innovation is the key for future success. Female entrepreneurs have reflected on different aspects

of innovation in an effective manner. For example, case 16 reflects that Innovation required a persistent approach and subjected to intensive resistance that is highly exhausting. The main obstacles faced during entrepreneurship are incompetent caseworkers, bureaucratic negligence, slow and delayed process and extensive blockages. The female entrepreneur is more open towards the innovative side of the candidate. A lack of follow up is observed after acquisition of credit. In addition, a lack of follow-up projects and other official programs are found. A small team is responsible for in charge of innovation. However, delegation is challenging and not allowed by the kind of present human resources. For transmitting of innovative practice, briefings are taken into account instead of meetings two times in week in the beginning and end of meeting.

Case 15 also referred the same. The main obstruction encountered during deployment of innovative practices. The fewer obstructions are based on governmental and legislative requirement that possess highly rigid framework. It is not pertinent to essence of craft industry. The other issue come across by Algerian female entrepreneur is employees that mostly use their own rules and practices or that seek for comfort and denied to embrace training. A lack of training is observed specifically in craft sector as majority of people considered it as the wastage of time. For persuasion of dream, female entrepreneur worked a lot and also sacrifices their family life. The entrepreneur of craft business never gives up its project.

Case 10 went in details to discuss the different aspects of innovation. It is realized that Innovation is necessary to be successful in the industry. For innovation, it is essential that you do something different that has not been done by anyone else before. However, staying with status-quo is not an option. Imitation is a reality and as rivals copy the ideas, the organisations do not remain unique. Hence, it is essential for pedagogical organisations that they continue to search for new options to expand on them. Findings disclosed that innovation itself does not bring success, training, and development of staff is one of the critical factors that assure the victorious implementation of new ideas. For gaining success in the competitive business arena, innovation has become a common process. It is pivotal for companies to focus on in-demand things. In other words, only customer-oriented innovations can bring positive results for companies. Reacting to customers' demands is necessary for keeping the business ahead of others. It has been assessed that innovation does not occur in isolation, it is mandatory to vista ns analyse the world from a

different lens. Collaboration and strong communication are two of the critical aspects of innovation that facilitate businesses in the process. The introduction of new ideas is not enough, the implementation process is more critical. It is essential that the change is communicated and the staffs are trained. Coaching should be a continuous process after the introduction of innovation.

Case four also added that the innovation is related to everything, but it is not related to structure alone. The innovation practices that the female entrepreneurs adopt are to offer change opportunities to their clients in their marketing and communication processes. It has been extracted that innovation is not a one mind process. Female entrepreneurs need assistance to implement innovative practices. Launching alone is a challenge and female lost their energy in this process. Female entrepreneurs work in teams and contain the ability to deliver better results. The best practice of female entrepreneurs is to keep changing things because remaining stagnant is not an option to stay long in the market. Case 4 also concluded that the innovation is related to everything, but it is not related to structure alone. The innovation practices that the female entrepreneurs adopt are to offer change opportunities to their clients in their marketing and communication processes. It has been extracted that innovation is not a one mind process. Female entrepreneurs need assistance to implement innovative practices. Launching alone is a challenge and female lost their energy in this process. Female entrepreneurs work in teams and contain the ability to deliver better results. The best practice of female entrepreneurs is to keep changing things because remaining stagnant is not an option to stay long in the market.

5.1.3 Innovation's Dependency on Workforce

Cases also revealed positive practices to assure that environment for innovation is fostered and developed. Different entrepreneurs have focused on the development of employees, training and development, and providing them with an environment where the innovation and creativity are fostered. Case three revealed that recommended that the teamwork and collective efforts of the employees can help in bringing changes. The level of internal communication can be managed by conducting meetings. The goals and targets can be introduced and shared with the staff to keep them motivated and satisfied. Training sessions can be organised to help to improve the teaching methods and the teacher exchange programs can be integrated to provide a platform to exchange ideas. Special classes can also be organised to facilitate students with special needs. To

manage these classes, doctors and specialists can be consulted. Case four revealed that in the consulting business, the major challenge to the implementation of innovative practices is the recruitment of honest and efficient people. Employee meetings play major role in keeping employees honest, informed, and motivated towards the professional goals. The obstacle for female entrepreneurs in Algeria is that few banking associations are interested in female entrepreneurs. Case five also revealed the importance of human resources and training and development. Training is offered to the teachers to enhance their skills and capabilities so that they can perform competitively. The success of business relies on how effectively the human resource is managed. Therefore, the school has associated with Educ France to provide training to the teachers so that the internal competence can be managed. The business started with a small initial investment that was managed using personal savings. It grew with time and consists of around 200 to 300 staff and teachers.

Case 6 also revealed the same; the training programs for entrepreneurs were also now available. It is important to keep the documents formally organised so that the organisations can deal with the authorities. Loans and finances must be used efficiently by planning and organising activities. To manage the organisation, it is important to focus on the human resource aspect. Hiring trained and skilled teachers and providing them with training can help in meeting the needs of the children and their parents. To innovate, new ideas are gathered, which helps in making the kindergarten a progressive place. They have associated with 'the white sisters' to manage the training and take advantage of the growing opportunities. Innovation has helped in emerging and evolving, which has facilitated the learning and development in many ways.

Case 15, on the other hand, revealed that the exchange of opinion leads to stimulation of creativity. The main innovative practice was related with the introduction of glass painting and later entrepreneur introduces other products for instance ceramics. The performance indicator in view of female entrepreneur is sales. If collection sales well, collection will continue. The female entrepreneur believes that creative side is more important for recruitment. The Algerian female entrepreneur prefers to maintain excellent communication level with workshop employees and provide opinion and recommendations with respect to team effort. The Algerian female entrepreneur conducted frequent meeting with frequency of two weeks with in charge person of workshop. The other activities are related with visiting exhibitions, stores and galleries for

observation of raw material innovations. This process can be perceived as continuous market study. Case 13 similarly, added to the stance that the entrepreneur prefers to become adaptable with situation, people and other environmental factors. The innovation skills are also considered during recruitment. There is no rigidity and hierarchical functional perspectives. It is challenging for female entrepreneur to accommodate the entire schedule. The entrepreneur emphasised on providing special training to coaches for differentiation of mode of teaching for coaching sessions. The main issues faced by entrepreneur during deployment of innovation are based on personal apprehension with differentiated nature of work based on offering different courses and activities for girls.

The entrepreneur overcomes this obstruction by inviting people to attend different workshop and encourage the staff for explanation about the nature of courses. All people including coaches, employees and teacher can access the different social media pages. A most vital thing is to observe the reaction of parents and people and specifically their extent of satisfaction. The female entrepreneur is continuously reviewing the methods and other activities and after compare the present situation of establishment with past conditions. The female entrepreneur adapted an innovative and unique approach that will provide help to adolescent's girls to develop their skills and growth mind-set approach that is required for on-going success. The environment of tuition centre is providing inspiration to adolescent girls that can provide enthusiasm and a greater level of confidence.

Case 9 focused more on the training and development of employees. From the findings, it is found that every employee is different and every employee works differently. Training is offered to the employees as enhancing their skills and capabilities can significantly benefit the organisation. She sends two to three people for training, which is carried out by the nuns. It boosts the confidence level of the staff and helps them in developing skills and capabilities. The school relies on taking both short-term and long-term strategies. The organisation involves recruiting employees and focusing on redevelopment of the schools space. The finances are managed in a way to support the adoption of new practices. However, the school cannot afford major changes due to lack of finances. It negatively affects the organisational facilities. As the organisation is operating in the service sector, there is no source of external funding. Personal funding is used to manage the changes and developments. The staff members are trained so that

their skills and capabilities can be enhanced. The training is managed according to the budget so that the costs can be controlled.

Case 8 also presents their opinions in line with the case 9. From the findings, it is revealed that that organisations need to evolve and bring relevant changes in their products and services to compete and grow. It is important to value employees and hire them on the basis of their skills and capabilities. Designing the training programs and providing training to enhance their knowledge and skills can help in improving the internal strengths of the business. Innovative practices can help in meeting the needs of people. It is important to conduct research and analyse the external environmental factors. In Algeria, it has been identified that the businesses are required to focus on innovation and development. The competition level is increasing, which makes it difficult to attract and retain customers. The business environment of Algeria has become highly competitive in the past few years. The opportunities are increasing constantly. However, the female entrepreneurs are still facing challenges in terms of introducing products, bringing innovation, and entering the markets. The entrepreneur had experience in the same field, which helped in gaining conventions in the field and allowed her to diversify her products. Signing agreements and developing associations helped in growing and improving the products and services. The customer services helped in specifically dealing with the customer needs and issues. The innovation was also brought in the marketing functions, which helped in enhancing the image and reputation in the market. It helped in contacting and communicating with the customers. The colleagues and employees are influenced to share their ideas to enhance their association. The association with the general agents have helped in defending rights and solving problems, which have helped in improving the business.

Case 5 similarly believed that training the staff members is essential. Managing the school, the case 5 reveals that Training the teachers and enhancing their skills and capabilities can help in improving the teaching process. As technology is advancing, it has become essential to integrate technology so that efficiency can be enhanced. The adoption of innovative practices has not only helped in managing processes and carrying out activities, but has also helped in attracting finances and managing resources. The female entrepreneurs in countries like Algeria face more challenges and complexities as compared to others. Case three also being the part of education system said that the educational sector is going through various changes globally. The schools

have now become responsible not only for educating students but also participating in their growth and development. The teachers are taking different training courses to enhance their skills and capabilities to play their roles and responsibilities effectively and efficiently. The role of teachers has evolved and developed with time. In consideration, the schools are required to use innovative ideas to design their curriculum and plan activities for children. The integration of extra curriculum activities has become crucial for the development of children.

Case 1 also reveals the similar findings both the entrepreneur and the educational team agree that every single innovation has the purpose to benefit the child, first. That is the reason why everybody in the organisation is welcome to make any suggestion that they think is suitable. These suggestions are shared during monthly meeting organised with the employees. It has been noted that some extra meetings are scheduled in case a problem arises or something needs to be changed. An example of these is a pedagogical meeting that took place after the entrepreneur noticed that there were no specific success criteria for the art class, so a meeting has been called to discuss the matter.

5.1.4 Innovation for the Sake of Better Quality:

For female entrepreneurs, customers and the clients have been the main attraction to bring in the innovation. For example, case one whose main dealing is with children claims that it is very clear that the main parameter considered when introducing any change is the children. Throughout the decisions and the innovative process, the needs of children and students are given high priority, for the organisation¹, it is important to create a positive learning environment. Furthermore, before the implementation of innovative ideas, it is important to focus on the feasibility so that the decisions can be integrated especially when it only relies on personal investments. Therefore, it is important to consider the financial feasibility. Similarly, case 4 revealed that female entrepreneurs are focused on offering unique solutions to their clients that count as innovation practices. moreover, Case 5 who is also involved in the school sector revealed that as the education sector is improving, the schools are required to adopt and procedures that meet the standards. The school constantly focuses on meeting the needs of the children as well as their parents. It is found that now the parents demand more effectiveness. So, innovation can be brought in terms of enhancing the curriculum and facilitate in progressing the knowledge provided to the students. Moreover, case 7, being a part of healthcare system, claims that

considering the changing needs of the clients and patients can help in advancing and improving the procedures. Taking feedback and utilising it to bring changes and developments is the most appropriate way to gain competence and success. Case three also added that the constant introduction of new things based on the observations and demands of customers. The innovation practices of female entrepreneurs in the educational sector also include the implementation of hygienic practices and safety measures. The school also includes the boards and data-show. Despite all these practices, the other innovation practices that female entrepreneurs are intended to implement in the educational sector include the inclusion of dancing classes and improving extra-curricular activities. The results disclosed that some of the innovative practices that include the introduction of a bus system, video surveillance system, staying open and serving as a holiday club to facilitate parents who are busy attending their events. The buses are added as value-added services to deal with the increasing traffic problems locally. The parents often face issues in managing their schedules to pick and drop their children. So, the buses intended to provide ease and enhance their satisfaction level. The mission of the school is to enhance the schooling systems in Algeria by providing a platform for learning and developing skills. The integration of technology supports the idea and innovation brought at different levels. The financial aspects increase constraints, which are managed by adequately focusing on the integration of changes and developments. However, it has been assessed that finances and lack of assistance as major barriers in the implementation of these innovation practices. People are not aware of the funding bodies, and if they are, they do not prefer to take help from those financial institutions because they find the mechanism difficult. Female entrepreneurs face challenges in training the staff regarding the change implementation. The financial constraints were managed by complying with the law and managing the safety and other elements of the schools. The earnings from the school were used for investments, which helped in bringing time to time changes.

Increased numbers of returns of teachers, students, and parents are some of the major success indicators of female's innovation practices. It has been extracted that research and development (R&D) has been a major source in identifying the gaps and offering innovative solutions to the parent's and students' problems. The introduction of new things or bringing changes in the observations and demands of parents and teachers is the best way to succeed with innovations. Feedback has been one of the best ways of improving the successful implementation of

innovation practices. Not falling to the same problems and learning from experiences donate immensely to the success of female entrepreneurs.

5.1.5 Issues Faced by Female Entrepreneurs:

Cases also revealed several issues faced by female entrepreneurs. A number of different issues from different cases have been noticed. Lacking the financial support and difficulties in the e-banking system has also been identified as a challenge in organisation 2. Many innovative ideas and opportunities have emerged for this sake, but the financial barriers along with the uncertain political and economic climate are creating challenges. To overcome these types of constraints, the management focus on assessing the environment and bringing timely changes. They enhance the product lines as well as the store infrastructures to attract and cater more customers. The outcomes of the interview with case three unveiled that woman entrepreneurs also face challenges in complying with laws and standards. Some of the measures that female entrepreneurs consider monitoring the success of these innovation practices include enhanced satisfaction of parents and blossoming of students.

Case four also revealed more insights about the challenges and issues faced by the female entrepreneurs. The interviewee concluded that the results disclosed that female need assistance in their entrepreneurial activities by they do not gain from anywhere that create barriers in the implementation of innovative practices. Some companies give loans to female entrepreneurs but leave them alone when they need guidance. The financial bodies do not provide any assistance and lack in taking follow-ups that create challenges for female. Finding appropriate employees and getting young blood is also a challenge. Training employees and getting young people out of their courses is also amongst the biggest challenge for female entrepreneurs. Another challenge that female entrepreneurs find in Algeria is that people prefer to take advices from foreign consulting companies and value foreign degrees and courses they do not have trust on Algerian private sectors most specifically when any woman is running the firm. Case 6 also focused on financial constraints for female entrepreneurs. Case 11 also adds to the stance, it has been assessed that entrepreneurs are not even aware of the bodies that can support them financially. Hence, there is a need to spread awareness of the financial sources that are available to entrepreneurs. It has been assessed that the delayed administrative processes, expensive loans, and government pricing are some of the major issues to innovation. The government

administrative must be quick in the ways of giving approval and responding to the extension requests. The resistance to change in Algeria is high, which makes it more challenging to plan and integrate innovative practices. For instance, as reported by interviewee 1, the school management identified issues related to the overload of school bags carried by the students as the school is using other involved different books in addition to the usual national curriculum. So, to overcome this issue, entrepreneur 1 has decided to design booklets for pupils. The idea was adopted from the Canadian's models for pupil's individual books, which consists of personal books including all the subjects and progress of students on a weekly basis. It has been designed in an effort to save time and energy, and to make it easier to manage the load. In this particular case, a lot of resistance was identified from the teachers, who are used to their routines, as well as the parents, who questioned buying the booklets as they preferred books they already bought. The discussions have continued to date, but the school is working on making it a successful project.

Case 5, on the other hand, added that the practical training provided to the teachers can improve the internal environment of the schools. Evolution and changes are a critical part of the organisation, which can help in dealing with different constraints and limitations. It is impossible to survive without integrating timely changes. In schools, it has become essential to offer value-added services to meet the changing needs of the parents and students. As the parents are demanding for more, linking up with different associations help in meeting standards and enhancing the communication with parents. As an SME, the school has emphasised on diversification and integration to meet the needs of the parents and students.

Case 12 has been highly critical in highlighting the issues faced by female entrepreneurs. Coming to female entrepreneurs, females face difficulties to even present themselves as an entrepreneur in the business world. The acceptance of female entrepreneurs in the business society is an issue. People believe that female cannot start their businesses or they do not have capabilities to run an enterprise. Due to the culture of male dominating society, people in the business world do not take female seriously that proves as a significant challenge to businesses. The female entrepreneurs face difficulties in proving themselves and making people agree that they can also provide quality and creative art and design services. People hardly believe that female entrepreneurs can provide quality services or may have a reasonable organisational

structure. Hence, female's acceptance as an entrepreneur is one of the biggest challenges that female face in the occupational domain.

Case 7, further revealed that biggest problem faced by the business along with problems of competence and entrepreneurial spirit. Using the technological aspects of the projects into consideration helped in developing a technological ecosystem. It helped in attracting more customers and clients. The commercial aspects were complicated, as the product was not well defined. They faced a tough time in arguing with the customers to answer questions and convince them to accept the changes proposed by the organisation. Meetings are conducted with doctors and professionals to convince them to use the platform for making appointments. When bringing innovation, it is important to consider the acceptance level in the market. It is important to build a trustworthy relationship with the customers and clients. The door-to-door marketing and collaboration has helped in managing the market presence. The company required higher investments in the initial phase for the development and integration of technology.

The findings revealed that collaboration with the government agencies has been a challenge. The government institutions consider the products as gadgets and have failed to realise its importance and impact. However, the thoughts and ideas are changing with time. Since the beginning, the company has been involved in making appointments and managing the waiting rooms. The consolidated view has helped in improving the services by helping the patients in giving their feedback related to the health services. The changes and developments are continuous and agile methods are integrated to manage step-by-step changes and developments. The trainings are managed internally to enhance the overall performance and ability to compete.

The research outcomes unveiled that changing location is one of the major obstacles in the way of business progress. Female entrepreneurs find difficulties in finding out any fix and suitable location for their business. However, social media presence is an outcome of the obstacle that makes female entrepreneurs more accessible to the target audience. Female entrepreneurs find opportunities from their surroundings; they consider the weakness as a chance to innovate. The study disclosed that female is not technical compared to men; hence, they face challenges in adapting things. It has been assessed that female entrepreneurs are not financial persons; hence, they lack in calculations. Female entrepreneurs find difficulties in training and they do not have

any support from the government side, as the government does not contain any sustainable strategy.

5.1.6 Recommendations provided by different Entrepreneurs

Different cases have provided with different suggestions to assure innovation within the organization. For some organizations, communication has been highly important. For example, case one, a school, believed that communication with the employees along with the stakeholders is important before changing any element. The entrepreneur suggested that communication should be strong between the management and teachers. Teachers must be trained and educated for the implementation of change, as it would help to reduce the resistance from staff. Communication with teachers may not work alone; hence, it is critical that all changes should be communicated to parents before the implementation of any change, and the benefit of those changes for students should be communicated as well. For being successful and evaluate the success of the practices, it is essential to monitor the practices and results gained from the implementation of these innovation practices. Improving research and development (R&D) activities can help in enhancing access to finances and incorporating innovative practices into the educational setting. Similarly, case 5 also emphasized over communication and is now struggling to enhance the communication through the technologies. The entrepreneur stated that the organisation is investing in technology to improve the level of communication. As technology is advancing rapidly, it is important to invest in technology and provide relevant training to the staff. Reviewing the pedagogical aspects, the importance of training teachers to support and structure their work has been identified. The school does not involve any external financial help, while the business owner has taken bank loans to purchase and finance the school equipment. The investments have increased by 10% per year depending on the economic changes and developments.

Few of the cases revealed that the country wide assistance from government agencies, chambers of commerce and from different authoritative bodies is necessary. Interviewees believed that many female entrepreneurs lack the opportunity to acquire knowledge and skills to compete in the business world. For example, case two revealed that to be successful, entrepreneurs' need some guidance and support, but it has been felt from the overall organisation 2 that no institution is actually providing assistance to female entrepreneurs. If female entrepreneurs face any

difficulties or they have any issue related to their business, they have no source or institution that can assist them in this regard. The uncertain political and economic environment of the country poses significant challenges to female entrepreneurs. Finding employees that are ambitious and can bring something extra are difficult to find. Even, organisations like CNAC who claim to provide assistance are failed in taking follow-ups. Even the Algerian female entrepreneurs' association does not do anything for female entrepreneurs to provide them with assistance. The results disclosed that there is a lack of training that proves to be a barrier in the way of implementing innovative practices introduced by female entrepreneurs. However, the success indicators that help to monitor the success have been customer satisfaction and profitability of the company. Case 15 and, case two also required help in terms of networking and personal contacts to acquire important information and knowledge. Lack of networking is amongst the major barriers to innovation, especially when the innovation practices consist of delivering new products. Relying on product innovation and testing of every new product are two of the major innovation practices that female entrepreneurs use in the manufacturing and distribution sectors. Networking is the key to implement such practices. Case four also believed that partnership with local firms is necessary to foster innovation within the business. The entrepreneur recommended that collaboration and partnerships with other consulting companies can help in this regard. Results disclosed that research and development (R&D) is a mandatory factor to consider while thinking on innovation. Employee motivation and competence are critical to maintaining in the consulting industry for female entrepreneurs to deliver quality services and ensure innovation practices. The measure of success in the female entrepreneurial consulting industry is customers' loyalty. Case one also added in this particular case study, the entrepreneur only relies on internal funding to be able to invest in innovation through a very basic and primary budgeting. Lack of research and development (R&D) is also a barrier to innovation, it can be noticed that in this particular case study the R&D department is completely non-existent. Furthermore, it has been noted that there is no indicator of success and no proper mechanism to evaluate the performance of innovation practices. On this latte, female entrepreneur 1 states "we will be really professional the day where, as you say, we will establish the criteria for success".

Case 11 also added that entrepreneurs are innovation handlers. Entrepreneurial businesses do not remain the same; they find ways to explore things. It is indispensable for entrepreneurs to linger flexible, as it is the only way to stay competitive and sustainable. The conclusion cleared the

importance of external factors in driving innovations. The study outcomes ended with the fact that change in culture, industry trends, political, and social environment forces companies to innovate. The change in the mentality of people is one of the encouraging factors to create something new. The political demand to bring the healthcare quality to the international standards motivated the clinic to improve services.

It has been assessed that with human resources, finances are also the aspect that creates hindrance in the application of new ideas. It has been realised that the technological advancements in the Algerian medical sector are not limited because of the limited human and financial resources. The mindset of people that technology will replace humans is also a major issue. Entrepreneurs believe that technological advancements will close the doors of employment to multiple people.

The study clearly defined the lack of research in terms of finding the sources of finance that create hindrance in innovation. Expansions or innovations are critical for business survival. However, they need funds that are hard to gain in the country like Algeria.

Changes bring significant issues for employees, breaking the status-quo cause stress to employees. Quality services are only possible if employees are trained. It has been detected that entrepreneurs lack in understanding the importance of training and development (T&D) of employees. However, it is essential to reflect on the pros and cons of innovations before their implementation, but T&D is still necessary for employees to assure the quality and successful implementation of change.

Case 14 suggested the involvement of government and its agencies to help the female entrepreneurs grow. The results recommended that the government must focus on providing professional and financial support to the female entrepreneurs because Female struggle to convince people that they can deliver good products and services and they have plans and sound strategies. Female as compared to men face significant issues in Algeria when they come to entrepreneurial activities. However, they are not behind men when coming to innovation and creativity. Female entrepreneurs know to turn the weaknesses into opportunities and successfully manage to progress the business. Female entrepreneurs are keen to find ways to make success in the global business arena. Financing female can help them raise their talent bar and benefit society. Case 12 also wanted the same, Governmental institutions support and advises public

healthcare organisations and does not deliver private clinics with advice. Competition is one of the critical factors that must be considered while innovative services, practices, and procedures. However, entrepreneurs do not consider competition. Hence, it is suggested that entrepreneurs to assure successful implementation, must consider gaining support from the government, think of the competition and focus on the T&D of employees.

As many entrepreneurs believed that for innovation training and development is necessary. Many of the entrepreneurs suggested having training and development of workforce to assure that the business is growing through innovation. Case 10 believed that the results recommend training and development as a mandatory part of innovation. The study disclosed the importance of teamwork in reaching the goals. The research outcomes disclosed that innovation demands changes and introducing change is not a piece of cake. People do not accept change easily, they are not ready to leave their comfort zone and create barriers in the implementation of change. However, for successful change implementation, the management is required to communicate the alterations to employees and support them throughout the way of change application. Case 8 further added that the training and development can facilitate in improving the internal procedures. Along with human resources, it is essential to pay attention to managing the financial resources and capabilities of the business. The decisions must be taken to improve relationships with the customers. Conducting formal meetings, assessing, and monitoring the performance can help in ensuring that the performance is managed adequately. Moreover, the changes and developments must be planned and integrated effectively so that the business can grow and can respond to the increasing challenges and complexities. For the finances, personal finances were used. A proposal was submitted to the headquarters for approvals. It helped in gaining approvals from CNAC to receive the required funding. Case 7 also recommended that research results highlighted the importance of measuring the success of innovation and highlighted the critical success indicators. The outcomes suggested that numbers of patients, quality of care, and maintenance of supply and demand are some critical factors to identify performance. The research disclosed the importance of innovation and highlighted the need for measuring the performance of the institution because of innovative measures. It has been learned that collaboration and teamwork are critical to be innovative, as two minds are better than one. The research revealed some loopholes that must be considered while thinking about innovation. For example, entrepreneurs are not concerned about training and development (T&D).

5.2 Thematic Analysis

Objective 2: To understand the purpose of the use of innovative practices in female-owned businesses in Algeria.

5.2.1 Theme 1: Growth expectations are one of the key drivers of innovation practices.

Growth expectation is a strong driver or contributor to the efforts of innovation that lead business will grow. This theme is all about highlighting the innovation practices for business growth. The studies found that companies that look for growth essentially seek success through innovation practices. The majority of Respondents believe that the growth expectations of entrepreneurs are one of the key drivers of innovation practices.

Total 3 respondents stated that innovation is core to the success of entrepreneurship and a way of satisfying customers that lead to business growth. Respondent 1 stated:

Customer satisfaction is one of the core aspects of entrepreneurial success and the purpose of innovation practices is to satisfy customers by thinking differently and anticipate the results.

The statement means that businesses seek customer satisfaction and adopt innovative practices because they know that customers' satisfaction is a key to profitability. When customers are satisfied they tend to buy more and recommend to others that result in business growth.

Respondent stated that innovation is necessary to gain success and overcoming challenges posed by the external environment (competition) by providing customers with exceptional quality and exceeding their demands. Respondent 6 also agreed with the fact that female entrepreneurs use innovation to help to evolve the businesses while dealing with external challenges. Respondent 5 and 6 stated innovation practices as a way of gaining success, financial support, and business growth in all seasons are the major drivers of growth. Gaining success and financial support is evident from the data analysis for Respondent 5:

We have learned to compensate and create their material.

The statement disclosed that the business has learnt to compensate their customers by creating the material they demand from business, this helps in enhancing business growth.

On the contrary, respondent 9 commented that:

“Delivering humanity is a reason to continuously come up with innovations.”

The statement disclosed that entrepreneurs continue to have innovative products to satisfy the needs of people that lead them to improved business success, as satisfied customers tend to buy more and recommend the brand to others that force businesses to enhance the production of services to deliver the extended needs that result in business growth.

Respondent 8 and 10 agreed with the concept and accepted that innovation practices are core to meet the needs of people and to overcome environmental challenges and female entrepreneurs use innovative practices to deal with the challenges. Respondent 11 and 12 also agreed with the fact that the world is changing and the demands of people as well; hence, entrepreneurs to break the status-quo and meet those new demands of customers choose to innovate that helps them in business growth. Respondent 14 stated:

Progress, do something ourselves, create something. There are a lot of things that push us to move forward.

The statement means potential growth is not the only driver of innovation, but other factors drive innovation practices as well. Female entrepreneurs are motivated towards innovation because they seek financial gains and continuous growth.

These results are supported by (Campaña et al., 2017). The authors stated that companies adopt innovation because they want to grow. Companies use entrepreneurial (innovation) practices because they seek success. Further, Brie et al. (2010) and Michel Bundock (2013) supported the finding that innovation is necessary to increase spending power and improve financial stability.

Sub-theme 1: Innovation practices include adding value for customers

Adding value for customers is to provide customers with the services that they value against the price or for which they are ready to pay the price. It has been assessed that majority of organisations believe that innovation add value for customers. However, some say that innovation is about creating new things to remain competitive.

Few of the organisations accepted that product innovation is to add value for customers by introducing the products that deliver their needs. They stated that management to deal with the

external challenges brings timely changes and these changes are known as innovation practices. Respondent3 stated that:

Value addition is a solution to customers' problems.

The statement means that innovation practices add value for customers in products and services that motivate them to buy things. Value addition to the products and services prove to be a solution to the existing problems of customers. Customers tend to buy from the business that provides solutions to their problem and offer additional value. Hence, value addition is a growth driver for businesses.

Respondent 5 stated that:

Innovation is adding value for customers by improving the quality and information of products and services it is a further progression from the current stage of the products or services.

The statement tinted on the fact that innovation is a value addition process to existing products and services. Innovation helps businesses in improving the quality of their products and services that support them in transforming the current condition of the business to the future. The core driver of these innovations is the value-added to products and services to satisfy the thrust of enhanced business growth.

Respondent 8 contradicted and stated:

Innovation practices are about the creation and introduction of products and services that can be used in the marketing process to creating a positive image of businesses.

The statement highlighted the positive image as a driver of product or service innovation. This means that businesses introduce new products and services in the market because they want to improve their positive image in the market. The positive image ultimately leads to enhanced business growth.

Respondent11 and 12 agreed with the fact that innovation is not about being new every time, it is about making different offers to customers to fill their needs.

Respondent 11 explained innovation differently by highlighting that innovation is not necessary to introduce a new idea that does not exist before; the idea may not be new to the world but

should be new to the organization. Respondent stated that the expansion of services and products can be an innovation for businesses because they are new to them no matter how old they are to the world.

Innovation is about adding value by creating things and adding value for customers is supported by Safoulanitou (2013) and Michel Bundock (2013). Innovation fills the needs of customers and helps to resolve the issues of customers are the facts supported by (Korichi, 2015).

Sub-theme 2: Innovations is about providing unique solutions to problems

Unique solutions refer to the services and products that are not easily available in the sector. Majority of the entrepreneurs believe that providing unique solutions to customers is one of the key drivers of innovation practices. When a business develops the unique solutions it helps in increasing the number of new customers in the market because customers often look for unique products and features. However, some said that innovation aims to remain stable and do not quit.

Most of the organisations stated that innovation is the practice of delivering products to customers that are not easily available. Innovation practices include providing unique solutions to customers for their problems. They stated that innovation expertise provides new ways to resolve issues and differentiate companies from rivals; it is about introducing new facilities, programs, and activities. Respondent 7 stated:

Adopting new processes and solutions is necessary for companies; innovation introduces new things to bring about relevant changes.

The statement reflected in the unique solution provided as a driver of innovation. This means that business has innovative things because they want to deliver unique solutions to the customer problems.

Algerian female believes that innovative ideas and strategies act as key to the success of entrepreneurs, but these innovations must be planned. Respondent 8 and 9 agreed with the fact that innovation is about bringing new things to the market that do not exist at all or do something different that has not been done before and continuously developing products. In alignment, Respondent 10 and 12 also showed their belief that innovation is about breaking the status-quo; entrepreneurs do not limit themselves to old things, they make progress. Entrepreneurs do not

quit, they find solutions to the problems and find ways to remain stable. Female entrepreneurs find opportunities in their surroundings and take the gaps or weaknesses as a chance to innovate things. Respondent13 also highlighted innovation as a unique approach to develop skills. Respondent 16 stated product innovation as a way of promoting the products in novel manners.

Innovation is about introducing new products and gaining a competitive advantage by differentiating from rivals and these findings are supported by (Bali, 2015). The author stated that companies must be innovative otherwise they must be outperformed by rivals and disappear. The theme and sub-themes satisfy objective 2, by highlighting the factor that motivates female entrepreneurs to adopt innovative practices. The theme concluded that value-added services, the thrust of providing customers satisfaction and expectations for business growth are some of the key factors that donate to the motivational level to adopt innovation practices.

Objective 3: To explore the factors that influence the innovative practices adopted by the female-owned businesses in Algeria.

5.2.2 Theme 2: Technology defines innovation

Advanced technologies are the way to innovate things; technological advancements are one of the key drivers of innovation. It is found that companies that adopt technology could effectively contribute towards innovative process or product. Approximately all respondents believe that technologies are important to success and innovations.

Sometimes entrepreneurs do not use technologies to make innovations, they consider technological; advancements as innovation. For example, respondent 4 stated: technology itself is innovation and innovations influence technological advancements. Respondent 7 stated:

Technological advancements are innovations as they help to make progress and attract customers because more people will be able to use the facility.

The response highlighted the importance of technological advancement as a factor as an innovation that positively influences the innovation process because it facilitated people in the application of innovation and attracting more customers.

Respondent11 commented:

Technological advancements are important innovations and necessary to deliver quality care to customers. Technological advancements replace humans and reduce costs. In the year when we have profits, if we can re-invest them in equipment or other then we do.

This communicates that Respondent considers technology as innovation and invest in technological equipment as they find a chance. Technological advancement itself is innovation and contributes immensely to improving the organisational services and enhancing customer experience.

The research outcomes are supported by (Damanpour 2008) and (Miller, 2013). They supported technological advancements as an innovative initiative that organizations take to improve their quality and services to better meet the needs of their customers.

Sub-theme 1: Technology meets the needs of innovation

Technology helps companies to meet innovation needs. Integration of technologies helps companies to enhance their communication and share ideas that boost innovations. The majority of Respondents accept the fact that technological integration helps companies in innovation. It is acceptable that technological innovation is not always the reason for innovation, but it provides support to the process.

It is not necessary that technology itself deliver as an innovation, the majority of organizations use technology to facilitate innovation practices. Respondent 3 tinted on the fact that integrated technology helps meet the needs of innovation; it supports the innovative idea implementation at a different level. Technological advancements also help to reduce financial constraints by focusing on changes and developments in the existing system. Respondent also highlighted innovation needs collaboration and sharing of ideas. Technology enables employees to provide an integrated platform that helps employees in exchanging ideas. Respondent5 also believes that technological advancements are critical to enhancing the overall effectiveness and quality of the firm and helps to bring innovations to companies. Respondent stated:

Technological advancements are helping us in innovation and improving our communication and collaboration that is mandatory to be successful in innovation. We are making significant investments in technology due to our ability to help in the innovation process and training and developing employees.

The statement highlighted that innovation demands open communication and collaboration, technological advancements facilitate collaboration and communication that help in the process of innovation and train and develop employees for the required skills.

Respondent 7 stated:

Technological advancements are critical for fulfilling the further needs of innovations such as for generating technological ecosystems. Making significant investments in technological advancements is important for continuous innovation. It's our ambition to make information portals for people. We are operating in the technology sector and believe that only technology can deliver people with their innovation needs.

The statement communicated that technological advancements may not be the innovations always, but these advances provide organizations as a supporting source. Organizations consider technological skills and advancements as a way of supporting innovation practices and meeting the needs in the process of innovation.

These facts are supported by (Ingham2001) and (Arora and Gambardella 2009). These authors also highlighted that technological advancement make the innovation process easy by enhancing communication and collaboration between organizational employees. The easy flow of information and knowledge sharing allows firms to come up with multiple and unique ideas.

Sub-theme 2: Research and development (R&D) is decisive for appropriate technology and innovation

Research and development is an activity of collecting data and gathering information for innovating and introducing new products. Lack of research and development is one of the critical factors that can influence the process of innovation negatively. Approximately all respondent accepted the fact.

Respondent 1 stated:

The lack of research and development activities creates hindrance in the process of innovation. The R&D is necessary for the appropriate application of innovation by enhancing access to finance and technological advancements.

The statement communicated the fact that organisations bring technological advancement within organisations to facilitate innovations, but the advantage of these technologies can be only gained if an employee knows to use these technologies effectively and efficiently. T&D enable employees to develop the skills necessary to use these technologies and take advantage of them.

Respondent 3 stated:

R&D is a source of doing marketing research for finding gaps and opportunities to innovate solutions to satisfy customers. I always try to research to see what is done at the competition to improve myself, which defines that how important it is to research to improve the effectiveness of technology and innovation.

Respondent 11 stated:

Research and development are decisive for the appropriate application of technology and bringing innovation. In-depth research is critical to know the performance of the implemented technology. Research helps in evaluating the things that are required to further improve the performance technology and reach the ultimate aim of delivering quality products or services. Research and development (R&D) is important for the effective and useful application of technology and improve the ways of bringing innovation in organizations.

The statement disclosed that research and development (R&D) is one of the core factors that donate to the success of technological advancements. R&D enables entrepreneurs to know diverse ways of deploying innovation and proved to be decisive for the appropriate application of new technology.

The above-mentioned research outcomes are supported by (Nonaka et al., 2004) and (Julien 2008). These authors mentioned that R&D activities are core to the success of technological advancements as they help to identify better technological options and evaluating the progress of implemented technologies. They stated that R&D allows organizations to have feedback from employees and customers that encourages institutions to bring improvement in existing technologies and better implement the solutions. The themes and sub-themes satisfy objective 3, by highlighting the factors that influence female entrepreneurial practices of innovation. It has been extracted that technological advancements and research and development (R&D) are two of

the major factors that contribute to the adoption innovation practices adopted by female entrepreneurs.

5.2.3 Theme 3: External factors influence innovation practices

External factors such as political, social-culture and economic factors influence female's entrepreneurial factors. Below are the themes that communicate the influence of external factors individually on female entrepreneurial innovations. Majority of the female entrepreneur believes that cultural environment has a strong influence on innovation practices and stated Algerian culture as a barrier to female entrepreneurship. The second and third factors that have been highlighted include politics and competition.

Sub-theme 1: Culture influence innovation practices of female entrepreneurs in Algeria

Culture is an important part of the business. The adoption of innovation and technology mainly depends on the organisation structure and culture. It is found that companies with performance-centric and customer-centric culture could essentially increase the performance and lead towards innovation.

Respondent 9 commented that,

The culture of the country has a strong impact on the overall entrepreneurial process of countries. Algerian culture is a barrier to the adoption of entrepreneurial practices. The culture of Algeria is male dominating. Though the country has some financial bodies to support innovation they do not deliver their purpose and left female entrepreneurs financially unstable. The administrative culture of financial bodies makes the innovation process complex for female entrepreneurs.

The statement communicates that culture is an external factor that influences the innovation practices of entrepreneurs by influencing their approaches to innovation and Algerian culture is a barrier to innovation, as the government does not support female entrepreneurs in terms of finances.

Following respondent 9, respondent 12 also highlighted the male dominating culture as one of the key resisting factors that influence innovation practices for female. Respondent stated:

People in Algeria in the business world do not take female seriously that creates challenges for female. People hardly believe that female entrepreneurs can provide quality or have a responsible organizational structure. Hence, the acceptance of female in the entrepreneurial world is one of the key challenges.

The response disclosed that Algeria has a male dominating culture due to which female entrepreneurs are not perceived as productive business person that creates hurdles and barrier towards motivation for females for innovation practices.

Respondent 11 voiced that,

The cultural change of the country is an important factor in female entrepreneurship. The entrepreneurs must understand the importance of external factors in driving innovation and the changing culture of the country is core to the female entrepreneurial actions. The changing mentality is one of the key factors that donate to the success of female entrepreneurs.

The statement disclosed that changing Algerian culture is support to female entrepreneurs as people have started realising the importance and capabilities of female entrepreneurs.

The section concluded that Algerian society is a male dominant country and the culture of the country does not allow men to take female seriously. The female entrepreneurs stated that though the financial bodies in the country exist to support entrepreneurial businesses due to the dominant male culture these institutions completely fail to guide female, entrepreneurs. On the contrary, it has been observed that the trends and culture of the country are changing rapidly that contains a positive impact on female entrepreneurship. The male dominating culture is a problem for female entrepreneurship are the outcomes that gain backed by (Ghiat, 2017). The author stressed men dominating culture as a problem for female entrepreneurs in Algeria. Algerian culture is dominated by traditional thinking that does not allow to accept the female easily and taken them seriously are the facts supported by (Cheraghi, 2014).

Sub-theme 2: Political factors of Algeria influence innovation practices of female entrepreneurs.

Respondent 2 expressed the relationship between political factors and innovation efforts. The entrepreneur stated:

The financial barriers along with the uncertain political environment are some of the major reasons that create barriers to the success of female entrepreneurs and do not allow them to adopt innovative practices. The political environment of the country is not certain that poses significant challenges to female entrepreneurs.

However, on the contrary, Respondent 11 stated:

The political environment is supportive for making innovation and this is because the entrepreneur was working in the healthcare sector. With the help of governmental policies the innovation of operating rooms was made possible that was an innovation and supported by the external environment. The political environment demands to improve the healthcare system to the national standards was a motivational factor to bring innovation in the clinic.

The political environment of the country is not certain that creates barriers for female entrepreneurs. However, some policies encourage innovative practices for female working in the healthcare sector. Tahir (2016) backed the facts that political factors are one of the major reasons that make entrepreneurship men's activity in Algeria.

Sub-theme 3: Increasing competition influence innovation practice in Algeria

To effectively operate and survive in competitive business environment companies are expected to focus on innovation. The innovation practice support companies to meet customer needs and offer a product that is not launched by rivals. In distinction to others, respondent4 highlighted the importance of competition as a critical external factor that encourages innovation and female entrepreneurs to believe that to remain stable they have to introduce something new. Respondent 5 stated:

We use our skills and knowledge to perform competitively because we know that competitive performance is critical to success.

Respondent 8 also agreed with the competition as an external environmental factor that influences female's innovation activities. Respondent stated:

The competition level is increasing due to which, attracting and retaining customers is becoming difficult. The business environment is becoming highly competitive in the past few years that

influence the female entrepreneurs' ability to enter the market with new ideas. We always try to see what the competitor proposes as an advantage to try to improve ourselves.

This means that female entrepreneurs use competition as an advantage to improve their offerings. Respondent 9 mentioned:

Innovation is critical to remain competitive and meet the needs of customers. The competition in Algeria is not fair that creates challenges for female entrepreneurs in the way of adopting innovative practices. I look at the competition, how I position myself in the competition to try to always be ahead and to have a competitive advantage.

The statement is a depiction of the positive thoughts of Respondent 9 gained competitive environment. Respondent 10 communicated:

Increasing competition is a critical external factor that provides ground for innovation and encourages female entrepreneurs to adopt innovative practices. An innovation is a way to remain stable in the business arena and increasing competition is a threat to the stability of female entrepreneurs. This external factor makes innovation practices compelling to them.

Respondent 11 specifically mentioned that while adopting innovation practices, entrepreneurs must consider the competition. Respondent 14 highlighted:

In Algerian business society, competition is prevalent and unfair competition is making it difficult for female entrepreneurs to enter the market with new things.

The response reflected the unfair competition culture of Algeria that negatively influences the adoption of innovative practices of female entrepreneurs.

Respondent 16 also agreed:

More unfair competition is increasing in the business world of Algeria. It is difficult to do a real market study or a business plan because the information in Algeria is either inaccessible or erroneous. Besides, competition is unfair in Algeria in the sense that companies do not succeed by doing better but by having a substantial network. So it's true that competition is a lever, it is a motivation, but unfortunately, there is this unfair competition and favouritism.

Competition is an external factor that encourages innovation in female entrepreneurship. Increasing competition gives reason to female entrepreneurs that they innovate to remain stable in the market. However, competition doesn't need to leave female with positive hopes, it may discourage them. Further, the section also highlighted unfair competition and influence on female entrepreneurship and their innovation practices. Competition is negative for innovation in Algeria because it is unfair. Further, the statement disclosed that information and market research is crucial for innovation, but having access to accurate information is difficult in Algeria that creates barriers to the adoption and implementation of innovative practices.

is a fact supported by (Schumpeter, 1934). Schumpeter's (1934) mentioned that competition is bad for innovation because it reduces monopoly and discourages entrepreneurs from come-up with further innovation. Djeflat (2012) supported the fact that unfair competition is a barrier to innovation because it is outside the regulatory standards. The themes reflected on the external factors that influence innovation practices negatively. It has been assessed that the male dominating culture of Algeria, political environment, the increasing unfair competition, lack of market research, and lack of access to the information necessary to develop business plans are some of the key factors that create barriers to the creation and implementation of innovative practices.

Objective 4: To understand the challenges facing female entrepreneurs in Algeria in the use of innovative practices.

5.2.4 Theme 4: Finance is an important factor that influences innovation practices

Finance is a broad concept that is associated with money, it is a process of acquiring required funds for the business, and getting finance to start a business is one of the biggest challenges in Algeria for the female entrepreneur. About all entrepreneurs highlighted finance is one of the major hindrances in the way of innovation.

Respondent1 and 3 agreed with the fact that financial stability is important for innovation practices; lack of financial support to female entrepreneurs is one of the key barriers to innovation practices. Respondent 2 voiced the importance of finance and stated it as one of the major barriers to continuing with her operations from the beginning. The majority of the organisations found finance acquisition as one of the key barriers to innovation practices and

stated that loan and finance must be used efficiently. Respondent 10 and 11 also highlighted that finance has been one of the key hindrances in their innovation process.

The section disclosed that finance is an important factor and donate to the success of entrepreneurs by offering support to make innovation and also proved to be one of the biggest barriers to the way of innovation. The findings are supported by (Efthyvoulou, 2016); the author stated that companies with a lack of finances have fewer chances of success because financial constraints have a heavier impact on innovation abilities.

Sub-theme 1: Due to lack of finance training and development are rare that create hindrance in innovation.

Lack of finance creates barriers to the success of companies and does not allow companies to pursue the activities that are critical for innovation such as research and development. The majority of the organizations accepted the fact while some stated that due to lack of finance they lacked in training and development of employees.

The 4 respondent voiced that innovations demand research and development (R&D) but female entrepreneurs do not have the finances to do research; hence, females face challenges in training employees. According to data analysis, Respondent 1 stated that:

Yes, you know, honestly, today we do not do exactly what we wanted at the base. We have a little deviated from our first goal. We have saved some parameters such as the development of the child, even if it is not always easy because for a child to be fulfilled with all this workload, it is very difficult. We have major difficulties such as teacher training; we are in a country that lacks teacher training. We have students or retired teachers in the market and in both cases, it is not ideal. Students lack the knowledge and retired teachers are too influenced by old practices and do not accept novelties easily.

The statement highlighted multiple challenges female entrepreneurs face during the adoption of innovative practices and these challenges include increased load, lack of T&D, knowledge, resistance to change and association to old practices. All these problems are strongly associated with the lack of finances because lack of finances does not allow female entrepreneurs to train their employees and enhance their skills and knowledge and help them in making a trade-off

from old practices. Hence, it is proved that they lack in T&D and mentioned in her interview that it is due to financial limitations.

Respondent 4 and 7 in the alignment highlighted that training and development are critical to have a talented staff and technological advancements to have success, but after investing in these activities they left with less profitability. Respondent 5 stated that the organisation used finance in training and developing her employees that further help in managing finance and innovations. According to data analysis, Respondent 6 stated:

We end up paying for the training for the educator, and we must always inquire and look for some interesting and relevant ones. The entrepreneurs must have money to finance the training of their employees and they must gain financial support from reliable sources.

The statement means that female entrepreneur to have a successful implementation of innovation practices must have a good amount of finances to train and educate employees for building relevant skills.

This means the entrepreneur was available with adequate finance to train her employees and gained support from a financial institution. The findings disclosed that training and development are critical to the success of companies as the successful implementation of ideas is dependent on trained and developed people and due to the lack of finance, companies lose their ability to train people and therefore innovating things. These findings are supported by (Berkouk and Watan, 2013).

Sub-themes 2: Financial institutions play a critical role in supporting entrepreneurial practices

The financial institute is the place that provides financial support to the business. When the competition is high and companies want to develop and improve they often consider the financial institutes. Lack of support from financial institutions is visible when it comes to female entrepreneurs. The majority of entrepreneurs highlighted that they did not have access to finance and they had to use their assets and resources to start a business. However, one entrepreneur stated that she gained assistance from CNAC and invested in the innovation process.

3 of the organizations stated that the lack of access to finance is an important resisting factor in innovation practices and due to the lack of finance they are compelled to use their finances. Though the availability of finance from external sources can help, the financial institutions do not support it in this regard and they end up borrowing money from relatives or invest their money. According to data analysis Respondent1, stated that

We use our own money to train our employees and the training is supported by the association of private schools.

This means they were not available with the support of financial institutions and developed their employees for innovation practices by having an association with other private schools.

According to the data analysis, Respondent2 states:

It would be really difficult to stick to a proper budget; hence, the entrepreneurs must be flexible in terms of their budget. The extra finances provide entrepreneurs with an opportunity to focus on multiple ideas.

The statement shows that after investing the personal amount entrepreneurial female does not leave with an adequate amount to spend on other activities. Female entrepreneurs must have an adequate amount of finance so they may not leave with few to spend on making the ideas reality.

The majority of the organisations commented that the institutions that claim to support entrepreneurs such as CNAC, completely lack in providing support; financial bodies do not provide any assistance to female entrepreneurs and do not take the follow-up. They stated that for innovation practices either they had to use their finance or asked from their family and friends.

Respondent 15 also stated:

Financial institutions as useless facilities as they do not offer any support to female entrepreneurs for innovation practices.

The respondent meant that financial institutions do not provide any support to female entrepreneurs and they had to end with investing in their finances.

Respondent 5, 6, and 8 contradicted and highlighted financial institutions as a source of gaining finance and used to invest in innovation practices. On the contrary, respondent 6 gained financial assistance from CNAC and invested in the innovation process. Data analysis for respondent 9 include two statements,

The service sector cannot benefit from a bank loan, for example” and “the state does bring no guarantee for the investor. No external funding was available for a service business that they could use for operating in the service sector.

The statement mentioned that service businesses are more in trouble and badly influenced by the lack of external funding that leads them to inappropriate funding.

The fact that financial institutions do not support female entrepreneurs and refuse to finance female entrepreneurial businesses investments that ultimately influence their capabilities to have access to innovations and being creative is supported by (Berkouk and Watan, 2013) and (Djeflat, 2012). Djeflat (2012) commented that Algeria lacks in benefiting from the innovation system due to a lack of coordination between state institutions, innovative companies, and private partnerships.

5.2.5 Theme 5: Human capital is one of the major sources and barriers to innovation

Human capital refers to employees. The majority of female entrepreneurs believe that human capital is critical to success and innovation and lack of human capital is one of the key barriers to the way of innovation. To take advantage of employees, human capital must be trained and developed.

Most of the Respondents claimed that human capital is critical for innovative practices and ambitious employees can help organizations to bring something extra that is not easy to find. Staff members are one of the major sources of innovation that helps introducing innovative ideas and assure the victorious implementation of ideas. They are involved in the process of introducing new practices because they share innovative and unique ideas. However, not properly trained staff becomes a barrier to innovation practices.

They stated that innovation itself does not bring success to the organization, training and development are critical for them to implement innovation successfully. They stated that staff

can be motivated to implement innovation practices by training and exchanging programs. Respondent 8 stated:

Human resources are important for having innovation in organizations. With organizational capabilities and financial resources, the management of human resources is equally important to introduce innovation practices. Human resources are critical to organizational performance and bring change within firms.

The statement highlighted human capital as an important factor for innovation and reflected that its management is equally important as other resources. Human capital must be managed and trained for innovation and employees are assets and play a key role in innovation.

Respondent 9 stated:

Human capital plays an important role in adding value to organizations and services. The professional and experienced staffs are necessary and trained employees are more skilled and have more capabilities compared to the non-trained employees. Hence, they have an ability to contribute to the success of the business.

The statement reflected on the role of trained and educated employees in adding value to organisational services. Hence, it is proved that human capital donates to value addition of product and services.

Respondent 11 stated:

Human capital is one of the key barriers in the way of innovation practices if not properly trained. Hence, training and development are critical.

The statement reflected on the importance of training and development and highlighted that untrained employees cannot make any difference and even can be a barrier to the business success due to their lack of skills to adopt new practices and take advantage of them.

Respondent 16 commented:

Human capital is key to the success of an organisation and as a source of innovation practices, but not properly trained employees are barriers to innovation practices. There is a small team in

place but I am in charge. I would have liked to delegate, but unfortunately, the type of human resources available does not allow it.

The statement communicates the whole story that if employees are not trained or educated they resist change and managers alone unable to implement change. Hence, employees must be trained and ready to accept change.

The section concludes that human capital is critical to the process of innovation. Employees are critical for finding new ideas and for the successful implementation of innovation practices. However, the section also mentioned that human capital can become a barrier to the effective implementation of innovative practices if employees are not trained properly. The findings emphasized the training and development (T&D) of employees for better innovation and application of practices. The results that human capital is critical for the implementation of innovative practices are supported by (Michel Bundock, 2013) and (Insee, 2013) while lack of training and development (T&D) can turn the human capital into one of the most common barriers to the successful implementation of innovative practices is another fact that is backed (Tabet, 2011).

Sub-theme 1: Skilled and educated employees have a positive influence on innovation.

Skilled and educated employees contain the knowledge and information that is critical to make innovation. Recruitment is important to attract and hire new talent and companies to understand the fact that hiring Skilled and educated employees are critical to the success of companies.

1 of Respondents pronounced,

Skilled employees are in a better position and contain capabilities to fill their responsibilities effectively. Skilled and talented employees are key to innovation and hard to find and they understand the importance of skill development.

The statement reflected that trained employees hold capabilities to implement innovation effectively so success can be attained.

Respondent 6 stated:

Skilled teachers contain capabilities to learn over time and grow that ultimately benefit organizations in terms of innovations. The employees with skills and capabilities perform

competitively that helps companies to bring innovations. The skilled employees find innovative ways to satisfy the needs of customers and by finding growth opportunities.

The statement concluded that skills employee hold capabilities to be innovative things and satisfy customer needs in a unique way that help businesses in gaining competitive advantage.

Respondent number 4 articulated:

Organizations have their focus on recruiting skilled and educated employees because they know that their expertise and knowledge can help to improve the internal strengths of their organizations. Educated and skilled staff contains huge importance in innovation practices. The skilled staffs make a huge contribution to the process and introduction of innovation by participating in the idea generation process that supports managing expenses and saving cost. While recruiting the staff to evaluate their innovation skills is critical because these skills can help companies in developing innovation mindsets further and can help in an ongoing process of success.

The section disclosed that innovation does not occur in isolation, it is a complicated process, and only skilled and educated people can facilitate the innovation process by taking part in idea generation. The section also highlighted that lack of skills and educated people is one of the key challenges and barriers to the successful implementation of innovative ideas.

Skilled and educated employees are key to innovation are the findings supported by (Cohen, 2008) and (Schaaper, 2014). The authors tinted on the fact that having a great amount of educated and skilled workforce is a success to innovation. The studies also highlighted that poorly skilled and educated employees always put companies into disadvantageous positions in terms of innovation.

Sub-theme 2: Human collaboration and team working skills are critical to the innovation process.

Lack of collaboration and working skills is also a barrier to the process of innovation. The active participation of talented and skilled workforce helps companies to meet the innovative practices. Approximately all companies agree to the fact that innovation is not possible without collaboration and teamwork.

Respondent 4 stated:

Collaboration and teamwork are critical to the success of innovation practices. Employees bring innovation to organizations by keeping themselves involved in the collaborative and teamwork efforts. Integrated environment and improved internal communication motivate employees to suggest new ideas and participate in the innovation process. Employee communication and coordination through meetings contribute majorly to keep employees honest, motivated and informed toward innovation and professional goals. The female entrepreneurs working in teams contain the ability to deliver better results. The possibility of having an ability to collaborate between private or/and private-public communicates the importance of collaboration.

The statement highlighted that teamwork and collaboration are key to keep employees involved and build their loyalty and honesty with work. Collaboration and team working enable employees to deliver the best results by overcoming the weaknesses of each team member and making the team full of required capabilities to implement innovative practices.

Respondent 7 stated:

Collaboration within organizations is not necessary; employees collaborate with others outside the organisation well to bring innovations within organizations.

The statement disclosed that for bringing innovations, collaboration at the firm level is not necessary; employees' collaboration with other innovation businesses can also benefit businesses in adopting innovation.

Respondent 10 stated:

Employees help companies to collaborate with related entities that encourage innovation. The importance of teamwork in reaching the organizational goals of innovation is critical to understand. Innovation demands changes and bringing changes are not a piece of cake and calls for employees collaboration and teamwork. Innovation is a process of collaboration and survival is nearly impossible.

The response clear that fact that innovation is a process that demand firm multiple capabilities and teams enable businesses to overcome the lack of capabilities by having members in a team each with unique skills and qualification.

Respondent 12 supported the concept by stating:

Collaboration and teamwork are critical to implementing innovation practices successfully because two minds are better than one. Female entrepreneurs in Algeria do not surround themselves with people and lack teamwork that brings limitations in the way of becoming innovative.

The statement cleared that female entrepreneur understands the importance of teamwork and do not recruit and hire people who lack in team working skills because they perceive such people as a barrier to the attainment of the goal of having innovations.

Respondent 14 stated:

Employees' teamwork is a better option where employees engage and provide each other with sound suggestions to make innovations. There is no collaboration between the private sector and the state, it is much more seen as a competition, and it is a shame. Before, when schools weren't accredited, everyone worked as they wanted, but not anymore.

The statements indicated that the lack of collaboration between people, employees, and companies is one of the key factors negatively influencing innovative practices. Respondent 15 remarked that,

Teamwork is critical to exchange the opinions and ideas that lead companies towards creativity and innovation practices. I have always had good communication with my employees in the workshops, to have recommendations and opinions. It's a team effort. Respondent stated that communication and team efforts are critical to the success.

Theme 4 and 5 satisfied objective 4 by highlighting the challenges that female entrepreneurs face in Algeria while thinking or making efforts to adopt and implement innovative practices. The results disclosed that lack of training and development (T&D) due to shortage of financial resources, lack of knowledge and skills, association with old practices, and poor role of a financial institution in providing support to female entrepreneurs are some of the key challenges in the way of innovation practices adopted by female entrepreneurs in Algeria. It has been assessed that human capital can become a barrier to the effective implementation of innovative practices if employees are not trained properly. Theme 5 concludes collaboration of employees

within organisations and with other public and private organizations is a way to make innovation practices possible and effective and deploy them to create a competitive advantage. Further, theme 5 concludes that human capital is an asset for businesses and positively contributes to business success, but if employees are not trained and lack certain skills then they can be one of the biggest barriers. Collaboration is crucial for innovation is the outcomes backed by (Roy, 2010) and (Idrissi, 2012). They realized collaboration as an important means to promote innovation.

Objective 5: To determine the impact of the use of innovative practices on female-owned businesses' performance.

5.2.6 Theme 6: Impact of innovation practices on business performance

Innovation is important for business performance. The significant innovation contributes to increasing the profitability, market share, customer based and competency. Innovation practices have a positive influence on business performance and how these practices influence business performance has been mentioned below:

Sub-theme 1: Innovation helps to overcome challenges and improve customer satisfaction

Respondent 1 stated:

Innovation helps in overcoming challenges and improves organizational success by meeting the needs of customers. There are no factors that can help in evaluating the impact of innovation on business performance.

The statement disclosed that the ultimate aim of the businesses is to satisfy the needs of customers and innovation practices help businesses in achieving this goal. Customer satisfaction is the only measure to evaluate the impact of innovation on business performance and no other factor can be used to evaluate innovation.

Respondent 2 mentioned that,

Customer satisfaction is a key to organizational success and innovation is a way to encourage customer satisfaction that leads them ultimately to the profit generation. Female entrepreneurs by adopting innovation practices ensure the return of customers and encourage their craving for further new products.

The statement disclosed that innovation motivates customers to get back to the organisation by offering differentiated products. Retained customers deliver businesses as a source of profitability.

Respondent 3 commented:

Innovation is a way of attracting customers by improving organizational practices. Innovation is a practice of satisfying customers and improving their return rate. Improved registration is the way of evaluating the success of innovation and measure of organizational performance. Hence, it can be said that innovation is key to overcoming the challenges of competition and satisfy customers.

Innovation improves organizational performance by overcoming challenges and satisfying customers. Customer satisfaction is an antecedent of customer loyalty and keeps customers retained that ultimately helps improving sales and financial performance of organizations.

Innovation is highly important to overcome challenges and satisfy customers are the results supported by (Schumpeter, 1934).

Sub-theme 2: Innovation improve quality of products and services

The quality of product and services is important for the company to attract customers. It is found that the number of organisation compete with each other based on quality. The customers often prefer to purchase products that are high in quality as low in price. Therefore quality should be the top priority of the company. Innovation helps the company to enhance the quality of the product.

Respondent 4 emphasized that,

Quality is a priority of customers and innovation practices are ways to improve the quality of products and services and differentiating from rivals. The companies struggle for customer loyalty and innovation practices by improving organizational performance to help organizations, winning loyal customers.

The respondent meant that improved quality of services is a competitive advantage through which businesses create differentiation and attract customers. Innovation practices help businesses in gaining loyal customers.

Respondent 7 highlighted that innovation practices have a significant impact on organizational performance in terms of finances as returns are rather positive.

Theme 6 satisfies objective 5 of highlighting the impact of innovation practices on business performance. The results unveiled that innovation practices improve business performance by satisfying customers -using differentiated products and services - and improving the quality of products and services.

Objective 6: To recommend an innovative practices model to support female entrepreneurs in Algeria.

5.2.7 Theme 7: Recommendations

Sub-theme 1: It is better to gain funds from personal resources

Respondent 2 stated:

It is better to seek personal contacts for finance rather than asking governmental bodies as they are of no use. If you do not have good networking, you will not win any contract.

This means that in Algeria female entrepreneurs may not get support from any governmental body in terms of finances. For opening a business and bringing innovation, female entrepreneurs must have a good network so they may get appropriate finances to facilitate innovation otherwise they may have to face difficulties in winning any innovation contract.

Respondent 9 stated:

Institutions do not fund the service sector or small businesses, it is better for large organizations; hence, it is better to have personal resources to have funds for innovations. Government institutions do not fund services.

The respondent advises specifically to the service sector that they must not seek financing bodies for help because this resource is appropriate for large businesses that can guarantee refunds. The statement disclosed that service firms are not on the priority list of governmental bodies and female entrepreneurs must focus on having personal funds.

Respondent 6 and 7 highlighted that getting finance is one thing but entrepreneurs should do planning to use the funds effectively. Respondent 16 also suggested having a personal network for gaining funds for innovation.

Gaining funds from personal networks and having strong networking create entrepreneurial environments and support with funds are the facts that are supported by (Lechner and Dowling, 2003); Malecki, 1997; Cappellin and Wink, 2009).

Sub-theme 2: Recruit the right employees or train them

The role of HR manager is to effectively recruit, select and train the employees. The effective training and development program enables companies to increase performance and meet the business criteria.

Respondent 1 stated:

To be innovative in the entrepreneurial world, the female must have trained employees who can help to implement success. The lack of training is a barrier to business progress. The research and development (R&D) should be done before implementing innovative practices and the communication process should be strong to facilitate change.

The statement meant that innovation brings change and take organizations from one level ahead of the current level. Therefore, it is mandatory to train and develop employees while thinking to implement a change successfully. Respondent 10 voiced that coaching should be a continuous process after the introduction of change.

Innovation brings changes that are new to employees and the only way to successfully implement change is to train employees are the facts supported by (Tabet, 2011).

Sub-theme 3: Evaluate the external environment.

Respondent 2 commented that,

External factors play a critical role in implementing innovation practices or can negatively influence. Hence, organizations should focus on evaluating the political and economic climate before making any changes. Further, female entrepreneurs should offer the products that are required by customers; as such innovations come with results. The uncertain political and

economic climate is two of the critical factors to analyse as these factors have a strong influence on the innovation process.

The respondent commented that for having innovations in the business, businesses must focus on market research to extract opportunities and potential threat and barriers. Innovations that can satisfy customer needs can better deliver businesses with organisational profitability. The respondent also highlighted the political and economic environment as having a significant influence on business innovations.

Respondent11 recommended the evaluation of the external environment to come up with better solutions and innovations. Respondent14 recommended conducting external analysis to have innovation; Respondent stated that organisations must observe their competition and conduct R&D to have accurate information.

The external environment plays a critical role in the success or failure of innovation practices is a fact that has been supported by (St-Jean, 2012) and (Michel Bundock, 2013).

Theme satisfied objective 6 by recommending the innovation practice model that can help female entrepreneurs in Algeria. The theme disclosed that female entrepreneurs should have personal networks to have finances rather than relying on governmental bodies. Recruiting the right people can be beneficial for female entrepreneurs. the innovation practices must include the recruitment and hiring of people that best fit the organisational objectives. Female entrepreneurs before innovating must look at the external environment because it helps to identify the gap and building innovation ideas on the factors that can better satisfy customer needs. Innovations satisfying customers have great potential to succeed and bring profitability.

5.2.8 Chapter Summary

The chapter communicates that female entrepreneurs face significant challenges and barriers in the way of their innovation practices that just not include inappropriate funding, training and development of employees, but other external factors as well such as culture, political situations, and competitive environment. The results disclosed that growth expectations, the thrust of adding value for customers and providing unique solutions to customer problems are critical to innovation. The results disclosed finance and lack of training and development as key sources to entrepreneurial success and innovations. Technology and research and development activities are

critical factors that play a significant role in the success of entrepreneurs. The results also disclosed that human capital is a key to innovation but can be a barrier if not trained properly. Results disclosed that skilled and educated people, human collaboration, and networking skills are some of the key factors that contribute to innovations. The results also highlighted cultural, political, and competitive factors that either positively or negatively influence innovations. The research results suggested that for having success in innovations, it is necessary to have personal funding resources, efficiently recruited and well-trained employees, and extensive knowledge of the external environment.

6 Chapter 6: Discussion

This chapter critically analyzes the constructed theme driven from cross-case analysis and thematic analysis in the light of literature review. Multiple themes are being analyzed with the help of constructed literature review to further elaborate the understanding and detailing whether the literature agrees or disagrees with the identified themes. The discussion below further expands the theme.

6.1 Theme 1: Growth Expansion is one of the key drivers of innovation practice

The intense competition and changing customer requirements require businesses to focus on growth strategies. The growth expansion enables the business to reach among the customers and meet the changing needs of customers. The growth expansion is an essential driver for innovation. When businesses intend to move towards growth they look for the adoption of technology. It is found that one of the key benefits of innovation is its contribution to business growth. Innovation can drive to higher productivity and profitability. It is found that Growth expectations are known as the beliefs and concerns that help the business to grow. It is found that the majority of businesses assume that growth expectations of entrepreneurs are considered as one of the essential drivers of the innovation practices.

Bianchini et al. (2018) argued that there are a number of strategies or approaches that could be adopted by the entrepreneurs for growth expansion. The most important strategy might include expansion of location, development of new products, looking for a new partnership, introduction to new marketing strategies, or offering value to the customers. In this regard, Maradana et al. (2017) argued that growth is an integral phase of the business cycle and it is time when businesses owner needs to decide to expand the business to manage the status quo. The literature found that growth expansion offers opportunities and rewards along with risks.

According to Aldrich, (2017), the intent to grow the business requires the business owners to bring in innovation and creativity within the business. It is expansion intent that requires the entrepreneurs to think out of the box and implementing new and better solutions for the firm so that it can grow. Anning-Dorson, (2018), on the other hand mentioned that stagnant business with restricted growth tends to fade away with time. The business environment across the globe has become highly competitive with market segments fragmented and consequently, business entities are required to conduct effective business practices supported with innovation to survive.

Thus it is more likely that the business that innovates tends to live longer. Bianchini, Pellegrino, and, Tamagni, (2018), further added that innovation is the key driver for business growth. However, the intention to business growth is necessary to assure innovation is taking place within the business.

Ignor Ansoff proposed the Ansoff theory for business expansion and growth. Ansoff Matrix model is an essential model used by entrepreneurs while determining the growth expansion strategies. Lacruz and Jääskeläinen (2018) found that the Ansoff Matrix is an effective strategic planning tool that enables the framework to support entrepreneurs, top managers, and executives to devise the strategies for future growth. The framework provides four directions for growth expansion such as diversification, market development, product development, and market penetration. The entrepreneurs have to determine the direction for expansion.

Biemans, and Griffin, (2018), mentioned that the direction of business growth is critical to be selected. The business needs the strategic direction in order to pursue the growth. Without a direction the strategic resources may get wasted along with the time. Nevertheless, it is the first stage for the business to decide where the business intends to grow. Crespo, (2017), further supported the stance that deciding on the direction for the business, it is essential that the business understands its own capabilities and abilities and assure that it is using the existing resources in new and innovative manner to experience growth.

Based on findings of research it is revealed that a total of 3 organizations mentioned that innovation is important for the entrepreneurs to increase value and meet customer satisfaction level. Respondent 1 mentioned that customer satisfaction is an important element of entrepreneurial success and the objective of innovation is to meet the needs of customers. The findings of research supported by Lacruz and Jääskeläinen (2018) where the author mentioned that product development and market penetration are effective growth strategies that support businesses to increase customer satisfaction.

The findings mentioned that respondent6 also agrees that female entrepreneurs use innovative strategies to increase business performance. In contrast, organizations 5 and 6 mentioned that innovation practices are important for long term success and growth in different seasons. In contrast, respondent9 mentioned that delivering humanity is the main reason for innovation. It is also realized that cases revealed that their main motive for innovation was to deliver better

services to the clients either in healthcare sector or the education sector. The intent for business growth and innovation surrounds the customers' value. Therefore the different cases that revealed their intention for business growth through the innovation critically mention of their customers, as well. For example case one mentions that to help children grow and learn better, they implemented innovative solutions.

This statement is supported by Loredana (2017) to effectively operate and survive in a complex business environment the entrepreneurs need to focus on community and green practices. Moreover, organizations 8 and 10 mentioned that innovation practices are important to meet the needs of customers. Tsatsoula (2018) mentioned that innovative and growth strategies help female entrepreneurs to resolve the external business environment issues. Respondent 11 and 12 agreed that the needs of customers are changing with the changes in technology. Khajezadeh et al.(2019) in this regard discussed that the Ansoff matrix includes four growth strategies that could be adopted by entrepreneurs to meet the changing demands and needs of customers. Respondent 14 mentioned that the business needs to create something like business as there are a number of factors that derive business towards growth and expansion. This stance is supported by Cusumano, Gawer, and Yoffie, (2019) who claimed that while the business intends to experience expansion and growth, it needs to focus on number of the environmental factors as well before proceeding to develop a comprehensive strategy. Damanpour, (2017), argued that eventually a business needs to experience growth or fade away if it does not innovate either by entering a new market or by delivering a new product. Both of these factors are associated with the environment, yet an innovative approach is necessary.

Sub-theme 1: Innovation Practices include adding value for the customers

Kleinsmann, Valkenburg and Sluijs (2017) argued that customers are an important part of the business. Their needs and expectations need to be a top priority for the business. The entrepreneurs to successfully enter the competitive and complex environment need to focus on creating or adding value in product. The research findings shows that majority of respondents believes that innovation help businesses to add value for customers. In contrast, some respondents disagree on this theme. These respondents believe that there are also other factors that allow business to add value for customers.

The research findings show that number of respondents accepted that product innovation can help businesses to add value to customers (Helkkula et al., 2018). Respondent also stated that management is facing a number of issues and challenges that drive businesses to adopt innovative solutions. On the other hand, respondent3 mentioned that adding value to the product allows businesses to resolve customer problems. In addition respondent5 mentioned that innovation and services are an additional progression from the existing stage of the products. In contrast, respondent8 disagree and mentioned that innovation practices are related to the development and creation of new products and services that could applaud in the marketing process to developing a positive brand image. This statement is supported by literature, where Barcelo-Valenzuela et al.(2018) found that the product lifecycle requires companies to focus on determining the needs of customers and change the product specification and specification to meet customer needs and expectations. The findings revealed that respondent 11 and 12 believe that innovation is not only being new all-time however it is to offer a different and unique product that meets customer needs. Siakas and Siakas (2016) argued that most organizations failed to survive in a competitive business environment because of a lack of understanding of the meaning of innovation. This theme suggests that businesses need to change the current product strategy with the changes in customer needs. According to Siakas and Siakas (2016) products that bring innovation in the current business environment might not be successful in the future because of constant changes in technology. Demirel, and Kesidou, (2019), on the other hand, mentioned that whatever the business does, it is for the customers. Customers are at the heart of the business organization and every business organization strives to satisfy the customers through different tactics. Eventually the main outcome is to deliver the value to customers. Denieuil, and Madoui, (2016), further added that innovation also delivers value to the customers. This is the reason that different cases have focused precisely on their customers in order to deliver innovation and value to them.

Respondent 11 mentioned that innovation is not required by businesses to introduce a new idea that does not exist before. The Blue ocean strategy disagrees with these findings. According to the blue ocean, a strategy business can create demand in the customer's mind and drive them to purchase the product. This theory reports that product there is less competition or no competition allows a business to earn high profits. However the 4- way customer criteria to add value for customer's theory support the findings that innovation is all about adding value for the

customers' (Siakas and Siakas, 2016). According to my perspective, the organisation needs to focus on customers' needs. Entrepreneurs are able to understand the customer needs they will be able to add the right value to the product. According to Efthyvoulou, (2016), for any business to innovate and expand, it is necessary to know about their customers because a business that does not have any ability to deliver value to the customers cannot survive for long. Eidizadeh, Salehzadeh, and Esfahani, (2017), further added that it is necessary for any business to deliver value to the customers and therefore any strategy or direction, new product or service should add value to the existing customer base and should facilitate the business to grow.

Sub-Theme 2: Innovation is about solving solutions to problems

The increase in the external environment causes current and future problems that will affect the business policies, processes, and products that are performing well. However, it does not mean there is no need for innovation. There is a myth that innovation comes from solving business problems. According to Director IT Innovation R&D at Optum, the market is always transforming businesses that need to determine the problems and develop solutions. Akoum (2016) found that continuous innovation theories help the business to focus on upgrading or improving current technologies, products, and services. Continuous innovation is more than incremental changes. It essentially links to ongoing gradual evolution which occurs in creations, operations, and activities.

The research findings revealed that most of Respondents believes that innovation is an essential practice of delivering the products to the end-users that are easily available for customers. The innovative practices mainly comprise of adopting new solutions to the customers and resolve their pain points. Respondents also mentioned that innovation expertise offers new methods to overcome the issues and help them to differentiate the product from its rivals. The findings are supported by continuous innovation theory which provides an essential approach to bring innovation to each stage of business. However, respondent7 mentioned that adopting the new process and solutions is highly important for the business to survive. Innovation enables businesses to introduce new things in the market.

Garba, and Kraemer-Mbula, (2018), in this regard mentioned that innovation is catalyst to business transformation and business expansion. It not only facilitates in assuring that business is growing but also assures that business remains stable. Garbuio, and Lin, (2019), further added

that through innovation, businesses are able to introduce new products and services for the target audience. The findings from the interview are found to be aligned with the literature, as Guan, et al.,(2019) further added that innovation helps in identifying the issues within the business and by innovating the services or the products, the businesses can easily differentiate themselves with other businesses in the market.

The findings revealed that Algerian female often believe that innovative ideas and strategies are important success factors for the entrepreneurs however the innovation could be planned. Kulikova et al.(2017) argued that continuous innovation provides essential practices and processes to increase business performance. The theory helps Algerian female to effectively and continuously determine the market changes and trends and introduce the product in the market that meets customer needs. Respondent 8 and 9 mentioned that innovation is all about bringing new things into the market. However, Kulikova et al. (2016) disagrees on this point that bringing new things into the market is not important to increase revenue. The author mentioned that technology can support organizations to increase creativity and innovation to meet the changing needs of customers.

Respondent 8 and 9 stated that innovation is about bringing new things to the market that do not exist at all or do something different that has not been done before and continuously developing products. In alignment, Respondent 10 and 12 stated that innovation is about breaking the status-quo; entrepreneurs do not limit themselves to old things, they make progress. Entrepreneurs do not quit, they find solutions to the problems and find ways to remain stable. Female entrepreneurs find opportunities in their surroundings and take the gaps or weaknesses as a chance to innovate things. Respondent 13 also highlighted innovation as a unique approach to develop skills. Respondent 16 stated product innovation as a way of promoting the products in novel manners. Hammershoj, (2017), found out that innovation has different types. Innovation can be in businesses processes, techniques or practices. It can also be in the shape of delivering customer values. Hautamäki, and Oksanen, (2016) further added to the stance that innovation can also be in the shape of improving workforce, updating their knowledge and skills so that they can be highly effective. For example, cases belonging to the school, frequently mentioned that they want the teachers and rest of the staff members to be trained so that their skills could be upgraded and they could actually contribute in delivering high value to the customers.

Consequently, the mindset of entrepreneurs incorporated within the study is found to be highly effective and efficient while discussing the different aspects of innovation.

6.2 Theme 2: Technology defines innovation

Lee et al. (2019) argued that advanced technologies are important tactics to innovate things. In this regard Mills and McCarthy (2016) argued that organizations who are early adopters of technology could be considered an innovative organization. Hence technologies are the key to success in business innovation. Nowiński and Kozma (2017) mentioned that there are theories of technology and innovation, the product-process concept, the concept of technological interdependence, and meta-learning concepts are mainly applied to innovation to strategic management.

The findings of the research indicate that respondent⁴ mentioned that technology brings a drastic change in the organisation therefore it is considered to be innovation. In this regard, Ungureanu et al. (2016) found a positive and significant relationship between technology and innovation. The researchers found that organizations that adopt the technologies have turned to be known as innovative organizations. In addition, Mills and McCarthy (2016) found that technological advancement are innovations as they support organisation to make progress and attract customers as different people will be able to adopt the facility.

The findings show that majority of respondents agree that technological advancements are essential innovations and required to deliver quality care to its customers. Technological advancements could help in replacing human costs. Technological advancements are innovations as they help to make progress and attract customers because more people will be able to use the facility. However, Helkkula, Kowalkowski, and Tronvoll, (2018) claimed that technology is one aspect of innovation. In today's world, innovation is highly linked with the technological features; however, that is not the only case. Technology compliments innovation, yet innovation does not necessary require technology every time. For example case one mentioned that they started to offer different language classes in the educational institute that was not done before. In this case, a simple differentiation resulted in innovation and creativity for the business through which it was able to deliver high quality and high values to the customers. Nevertheless, Iglesias, and Ind, (2020) mentioned that many business entities tend to bring innovation through technology including CRM, SCM, ERP and other technological solutions that reduce errors and

improve accuracy. Thus, it is realized that not every technological feature can be added as an innovation. Innovation is delivering better values to customers through effective manner.

On the other hand, respondents of little organisations reported that Technological advancements are important innovations and necessary to deliver quality care to customers. Technological advancements replace humans and reduce costs. In the year when we have profits, if we can re-invest them in equipment or other then we do. This communicates that Respondent considers technology as innovation and invest in technological equipment as they find a chance. Technological advancement itself is innovation and contributes immensely in improving the organizational services and enhancing customer experience are the research outcomes that are supported by (Damanpour, 2008) and (Miller, 2013). They supported technological advancements as an innovative initiative that organizations take to improve their quality and services to better meet the needs of their customers.

Sub-theme 1: Technology meets the needs of innovation

This theme covers the idea related to the technology that helps meets the needs of innovation. The basic idea behind the theme is to determine the approaches and technologies adopted by entrepreneurs could support in meeting the needs of customers. Pashaeypoor et al. (2016) argued that innovation and technology are independent of each other. In contrast Ungureanu et al. (2016) argued that technology has certain time and limitations that affect business practices. The diffusion of innovation theory argued that the technology adoption lifecycle has different phases. The companies that effectively adopt the new technology more quickly are known as innovation, the visionaries are early adopters, and the pragmatics is the early majority. It lasts the late mover or late majority that are slow in adopting the technology. The theory supports that entrepreneurs need to come up with advanced technology that is not offered by the rivals and gain the first-mover advantage (Mohammadi et al., 2018).

The findings revealed that Technology enables employees to provide an integrated platform that helps employees in exchanging ideas. The result shows that some respondent also believes that technological advancements are critical to enhancing the overall effectiveness and quality of the firm and helps to bring innovations to companies. Respondent mentioned that technological advancements are helping us in innovation and improving our communication and collaboration that is mandatory to be successful in innovation. They are making significant investments in

technology due to our ability to help in the innovation process and training and developing employees. This statement is supported by Pashaeypoor et al. (2016) where the author mentioned that the organisation that has successfully adopted the advanced technology has gained a significant market share and high customer value.

Jabeen, Faisal, Al Matroushi, and Farouk, (2019), in this regard claimed that technology supports and compliments innovation in a better way. Many respondents also believed in the similar fashion. Few respondents believed that through technological features, they are able to provide better outcomes to customers through providing them platform to communication. Similarly, better communication between employees and customers is possible and employee can communicate better with each other thus reducing the errors and improving the business processes. Kazumi, (2017), also added that technological features add value to the business by allowing them innovate and provide them with better opportunities to understand critically analyze their loopholes and replace the weak links and replace them with more precise and accurate processes.

Respondent also mentioned that Technological advancements are critical for fulfilling the further needs of innovations such as for generating technological ecosystems. Making significant investments in technological advancements is the importance for continuous innovation. It's our ambition to make information portals for people. We are operating in the technology sector and believe that only technology can deliver people with their innovation needs. In this regard, the diffusion theory of innovation supports that four important components affect the spread of an idea such as communication channels, innovation itself, time, and social system. Thus the process heavily depends on human capital (Prajogo and Oke, 2016).

Sub-theme 2: Research and development (R&D) is decisive for appropriate technology and innovation

This theme covers the role of research and development in the adaptation of technology and innovation in the organization. The research revealed that the needs and expectations of customers changes with time. The core responsibility of businesses is to conduct market research to determine the needs of customers. Sun (2020) mentioned that based on R&D, the entrepreneurs are expected to deliver a quality product for the customers. In the theoretical economics literature, research and development are often applied to define the conscious choice

of company and individual to invest in commercialization and promotion of new products and services.

Based on the findings, Wolfe (2016) argued that companies often invest in R&D on annual basis to determine the current trends and changes in the market. This finding is supported by literature where Zhu et al. (2019) mentioned that R&D is an effective business activity for collecting the information for innovation and introducing new products. On the other hand, Guerrero-Villegas et al. (2018) argued that a lack of R&D could hinder the entrepreneurs to successfully adopt innovative practices. Similarly, the findings show that the lack of research and development activities could limit the process of innovation adaptation. Thus R&D is important for the application of innovation to access financial and technological requirements. Sun (2020) argued that R&D not only support the business to adopt innovative ideas but also help in determining the gaps and provide opportunities for growth and development. It allows the business to collect that that could be used to compare the performance with rivals.

Here, R&D model of Service Innovation Theory applies. The majority of this study respondents agree that the adaptation of R&D can help the business to adopt innovative solutions. In this regard, Sriram, and Mersha, (2017), mentioned that research and development are two important areas that have enabled business entities to innovate into new products and services. Khoshnevis, and Teirlinck, (2018), further added that R&D practices are continuous and are conducted in order to remove and replace the weak links within the organization and replace them with more appropriate and effective methods and practices. R&D facilitate the business to remain future oriented and work in accordance with the expansion plan while focusing over innovative ideas and regularly checking for opportunities that can assure growth and development for the business in the future. Few respondents also believed the same and claimed that since they lack financial resources and have used their personal sources of funds to finance their venture, therefore they are not able to conduct R&D and if they could get a chance to fund the R&D they can surely expand their business while delivering value to the customers.

6.3 Theme 3: External factors influence innovation practices

This theme is emphasize on the external forces such as political, economic and cultural factors that affect the innovation practices for entrepreneurs in Algeria. There are number of female in Algeria who believes that culture and traditions are the major factors that affect them to become

the innovative entrepreneurs. This Theme is further divided into three sub themes to better understand the impact of each component.

Sub-theme 1: Culture affects the innovation practices among female entrepreneurs in Algeria

Culture plays important role in adaptation and implementation of new process and business. This theme selects the Hofstede cultural dimension theory to better understand the impact of culture on innovation.

Based on the cultural dimension theory analysis it is found that the on power distance the score of country is 80. On individual the score is 35, on masculinity, it is reported as 35 on uncertainty avoidance and it scored as 70 on long-term orientation it is reported as 26 while on indulgence it is reported as 32. It is found that the low score (Feminine) on the dimension indicates that the dominant values within society are caring towards the quality of life. Algeria low score as 35 and therefore known as a feminine society. In this type of society, cultures are focus on working to live better.

According to Knein, Greven, Bendig, and Brettel, (2020), culture and society of a country influence the overall change within the country. There are many countries that are highly adaptive towards the change as well as the new technologies and innovation. However, there are cultures that remain restricted and are slow movers towards the innovation and change. The adoption and adaptability of a country depends on the culture. Koyana, and Mason, (2017), supported this stance and claimed societies that are late adopters of technology tend to resist change.

The findings under this theme show that majority of respondents believe that culture is an important element that affects the adaptation of the best or innovative practice in the countries. The research findings show that Algeria is male dominant society and therefore most of the power and financial structure are under the control of male instead of the female which affect female to become innovative entrepreneurs. This finding is also supported by Hofstede's cultural dimension of Algeria where feminism has scored very low. In addition, finding also shows that various people do not consider female to be talented and competent they believe only males could provide creative solutions. In this regard, Felipe et al. (2017) argued that both males and

females have equal opportunities in the business because both can use their best mental capabilities to support business towards innovation.

The findings from the interview session are found to be aligned with the literature. Leavy, (2018), stated that society plays an important role within promoting innovation in different sectors and businesses. Lee, Hallak, and Sardeshmukh, (2019), further added the ability of the society to accept different genders as business persons and the mindset of society to adopt innovative practices tend to impact the overall business's tendency to innovate.

Reflecting on my views on this theme, theory, and findings, it is found that Algeria needs to encourage female to actively engage and participate in the business program. They should be provided with equal opportunity as males in the country. It is revealed that culture and social trends of the country are quickly changing which creates a positive influence on female entrepreneurship. Abadli et al. (2020) argued that Algerian culture is mainly dominated by the traditional approaches that might not allow female to easily participate in society.

Sub-theme 2: Political forces of Algeria affect innovation practice

This theme intends to cover the importance of the political environment on the adaptation of innovative practice. Warrick (2017) argued that the political environment in Algeria is not stable which creates barriers for female entrepreneurs. This theme could be better understood through the adaptation of the PESTEL analysis framework. It is one of the effective strategic tools that are used to support the business to understand the external forces such as political environment on business performance. The research findings show that there is a relationship between political forces and entrepreneur's adaptation for innovation. The findings revealed that the strict political and government regulation create limitation in success of the female entrepreneurs and does not allow them to adopt innovative practices. However some organisation has different perception about these variables. These organizations mentioned that political environment is supportive for adopting innovation practices but in limited sectors such as healthcare sector where government essentially support to adopt advance medical equipment to deliver quality health services etc. in this regard Samoilikova (2020) argued that government can lower or increase the corporation tax which affect female entrepreneurs to adopt innovative solutions.

According to Lounsbury, Cornelissen, Granqvist, and Grodal, (2019), it is the job of the government to create the environment to foster the innovative business practices within the country. Either the government can implement policies and introduce regulations to further ease the environment for entrepreneurship or the government policies can put restrictions towards the overall environment that caters the need for entrepreneurship. Malik, Abdallah, and Hussain, (2016), further added that it is the government that empowers the women, and then this trend is carried down to the society. If the government puts hold on the women empowerment, the society will follow the suit. Critically, the overall environment and the method by which the government is managing the business environment matters. If the government is not taking the female entrepreneurship seriously, then the society will not it, as well.

Based on my opinion, government and political force impose high power and impact on business performance. To become innovative, businesses need to conduct the PESTEL analysis to understand the level of impact caused by the external forces. The female entrepreneurs should raise their voices so that the government could propose some initiatives in favour of adaptation of innovation by female entrepreneurs.

Sub-theme 3: High competition affects the innovation practice in Algeria

This theme covers the competitive forces that affect the female entrepreneurs in Algeria. Thorstein Veblen's Theory of Business Competition is linked to this theme. This theory effectively focuses on the level of competition in the industry. This theory attracted attention in the context of the business cycle. Veblen effectively categorized the modern business scenario as the competition. This theory states that businesses that develop or innovate could be easily copied by their rivals (Manresa, Bikfalvi, and Simon, 2019). The competitive force affects the market share and number of loyal customers. Moreover, it is considered as the system of pecuniary rivalry and contention due to competition in terms of money. The theory also mentioned that the increased level of competition in the industry mainly derives businesses to adopt new technology. It also derives entrepreneurs to come up with the new innovative solution to chase the rivals.

The research findings show that competition is considered an external force that increases day by day. Respondent mentioned that intense competition has created a challenge for businesses to retain and attract customers. The female entrepreneurs are also affected by the increased

competition level in Algeria in different sectors. The findings also revealed that innovations are crucial to remaining competitive. The competition level is not fair in Algeria for female entrepreneurs. The organisation found that innovation is the only method to beat the competition. For example, when a customer found a new and innovative product they will prefer purchasing from your company instead of rivals. Thus, the statement proved that external force makes innovation practices compelling to them. In this regard Crowley and Jordan (2017) argued that competition allows a business to remain attractive and competitive. On the other hand, Tallman et al. (2018) argued that competition is bad for innovation as it reduced the monopoly and discourages the entrepreneurs from introducing the innovative products in market. Cusumano et al. (2019) supports the idea that unfair competition is considered as major limitation to innovation due to its outside regulatory standards.

The business environment across the globe has become highly competitive. The market segments are becoming highly fragmented. The current business environment is fuelled with rapid development in information and communication technologies. Consequently, every business in order to survive needs to make it certain that it is changing the business processes and is focusing over innovation and creativity to serve the customers. Marginson, (2019), in this regard, high competition fosters innovation and creativity within the industry, to assure that businesses are able to survive and is able to serve the customers in an effective manner. Mohammadi, Broström, and Franzoni, (2017), further added that competition allows business to remain competitive to survive. Monopoly that is one business in the market serving the customers has no intents to innovate and be creative to serve the customers. Nevertheless, female entrepreneurs as driven from the interview findings have realized the fact that the business environment is highly competitive and without innovation they cannot survive and therefore they struggle and strive to assure they are bringing in innovation and creativity within their business.

6.4 Theme 4: Finance is an important factor that influences innovation practices

This theme covers the importance of finance in affecting innovation practice. Manresa et al. (2019) argued that the number of small to medium organizations often failed to become an innovative organisation because of the limited budget and finance. Similarly, entrepreneurs also have limited start-up cost that affects the adaptation of innovative practices. Hence finance is sometimes proved to be the biggest barrier for innovation.

The organizations in Algeria believe that financial stability is important for the success of an organization. The findings show that finance acquisition is one of the main barriers to innovation practices and reported that finance and loan need to effectively utilize to gain maximum benefits. The findings of the study are supported by Auer and Jarmai (2018) where the author mentioned that lack of finances have limited chances of success in a competitive environment because of the financial limitation which influences the adaptation of innovative solutions. On the other hand, Aliev (2018) argued that finance is not the major constraint to innovation. Various small organizations with limited setup have introduced innovative ideas.

Movahedi, and Jalileh, (2017), in this regard argued that finance is one of the important resources that the business can have. Marvel, Davis, and Sproul, (2016), further added that for entrepreneurs, it is essential that they have access to finances so that they can invest in the start-up. Most of the business fails to attract investors and fail to attract the finances required for the businesses. Within Algeria, where the environment is already highly restricted, it becomes difficult for women to get hold of finances from banks thus they face huge issues in starting up their businesses. This is the reason that respondent 1 and 7 claimed that they started their business with their personal finances or borrowed money from friends and family.

Based on my opinion, innovation requires high investment and financial planning. Therefore, various organizations often failed to adopt innovation on time. The first mover's company essentially gains the benefit of being innovative. Financial planning should be properly conducted to successfully adopt innovative ideas (Manresa, Bikfalvi & Simon, 2019).

Sub-theme 1: Due to lack of finance training and development are rare that create hindrance in innovation.

There are the number of the organisation that adopts the innovative practices and technology but failed to implement it in an organisation due to lack of trained and competent staff and lack of support of organisation culture. The effective implementation process requires training and development. The theory of experimental learning found that cognitive and experimental learning are differentiated through the experimental theory of learning which is proposed by C. Rogers. According to this theory, the needs and wants of the learners are mainly addressed through the type of learning. The experience essentially provides personal maturity and enhances learning power with knowledge. The theory mentioned that due to personal involvement the

learner will be able to adopt new technologies and practices quickly. It is suggested that managers in organisations need to demonstrate the significance of innovation and the type of technology implementation. The experimental learning will be used to train staff and increase the competency.

The findings revealed that the number of respondents and female entrepreneurs is ended up with limited or no training and development programs due to its high cost. This statement is supported by Duque-Grisales, et al., (2020) in which the author mentioned that advanced training and development require a high budget and cost. The study found that the lack of training and development is because of financial limitations. In contrast, some respondent mentioned that T&D is crucial to have a skilled workforce and technological advancement. Respondents also stated that most companies use finance to effectively train the employees in managing the innovation. Sartori, Costantini, Ceschi & Tommasi (2018) argued that training and development help the company to increase employee motivation towards the new practices.

Based on my learning, training and development need to be adopted to successfully implement the innovation in the organization. For example, when employees are trained they would essentially contribute to their skills and help the organisation to provide the maximum value to the customers through the use of technology and innovation.

However, Negassi, et al., (2019) believed that financial resources are an important resource if not the only important resource for the business. A business needs to invest in R&D and training and development of employees to upgrade the business and that requires financial resources. Without financial resources it is difficult for a business to survive and conduct important practices that could help the business to expand. Panda, (2018) further added that without financial resource it shall become for new business to develop and expand.

Sub-themes 2: Financial institutions play a critical role in supporting entrepreneurial practices

This theme covers the idea the female entrepreneurs' encountered a lack of financial support from institutes. It is found that most entrepreneurs reported that they did not have proper access the finance and most financial institutes in Algeria do not support financing.

A number of respondents mentioned that financial institutes are an important source of gaining finance to invest in innovative practice. The findings show that after investing the personal amount in a business start-up, the female entrepreneurs might face a shortage of budget to spend on other activities. It is found that most of the organisations supports that entrepreneurs including CNAC completely lack in offering support. Manresa, Bikfalvi and Simon (2019) supported that financial institutes mainly provide the loan to large and high revenue organisation. It is argued that female entrepreneurial businesses and start-ups are often able to gain limited finance which does not support the proper implementation of technology. The organisation mentioned that innovative practices often do not use their finance or are asked from friends and family. Manresa, Bikfalvi and Simon (2018) argued that the organisation should effectively develop the plan to manage its financial activities for the business.

For any country to support its internal infrastructure of entrepreneurship, it is necessary to develop the financial institutional infrastructure. A developed infrastructure can provide loans and financial incentives to young blood that play an important role in building the entrepreneurial environment in the country. Moreover, the need to have financial infrastructure automatically supports the local entrepreneurial system of the country by providing them financial assistance that is required to initiate and launch business start-ups.

According to my perspective, entrepreneurs often need capital for investment. They look for different options such as debt and equity. Hence most entrepreneurs choose 70% debt and 30% equity source for investment. This often requires them to select the best financial institute. However, the lack of support for female from this financial institution needs to overcome to enhance female's ability to become innovative entrepreneurs.

6.5 Theme 5: Human capital is one of the major sources and barriers to innovation

This theme discussed the role of human capital towards innovation. Human capital is referring to the employees of the organisation. It is found that the lack of skilled and competent workers in Algeria might hinder the business to adopt the innovation. In addition, the lack of human capital in Algeria also hinders the adaptation of innovation in business. In this regard majority of organisations mentioned that human capital is crucial for innovative practice and employees could support organisations to introduce something new which is not easy to find.

The human capital theory was mainly proposed by Schultz in 1961 that was later proposed by Becker (1964). The human capital theory mainly recommends that training or education mainly increases the performance and productivity of workers through enhancing the skills, knowledge, therefore, increases workers' future income. The research findings show that employees are an important source of increasing innovation in organisations because of their skills and competency. The theory supports these findings as the human capital theory also found that organisation often focuses on employee's skills and role to adopt innovation. The organisation mentioned that lack of training in positive employee behaviour is the limitation of the adoption of innovation. In this regard, Marginson (2019) argued that organizations should focus on enhancing employee competency to successfully adopt innovative practices in an organization.

According to Plotkin, (2018), human workforce is the most important asset of the organization. Regardless of the opportunity, financial resources, strategies and ideas, if there is no effective workforce to implement the ideas while using the financial resources to acquire the opportunity, everything can be go into waste. Rahbek, (2018), further added that human workforce; these days have become a strategic partner for the firm. However, Rosa, and Sylla, (2018), mentioned that either the workforce can take the business towards development and growth or it can hurt the business badly. The cases incorporated in the study also revealed the similar nature of findings. It is realized that many business train and develop the skills of their employees to assure creativity and innovation. However, few also claimed that employees are the biggest resistance towards the change as well.

This is the reason that many respondents have argued that they have put their employees, teachers, and staff members to adequate training programs so that they skills could be upgraded. Another reason cited for training and development is to keep the employees motivated with high morale. Schmitt, and Bögli, (2005), believed that training helps in establishing close relationships with employees so that they are ready to go extra mile for the business. Once the skills are upgraded, it is easy to bring in the change within the organization.

Sub-theme 1: Skilled and educated employees have a positive influence on innovation.

According to Adom and Asare-Yeboah (2016) trained and skilled employees have certain knowledge and information which is crucial towards the implementation of innovation in the

organization. The recruitment and selection process requires entrepreneurs to select and hire employees who are skilled and trained to increase their performance.

The employee skills matrix is an essential theoretical tool related to this theme. The employee skills matrix is a visual tool that enables an overview of the company's team, skill-base, and guiding management to effectively control and monitor the competency level. It is suggested that female entrepreneurs could adopt the employee skills matrix to determine the work competency and current skill level.

The findings of the research show that skilled employees contain the capabilities to meet their responsibilities more effectively. The organisation mentioned that skilled and competent employees are important for innovation and difficult to find. In this regard, the employee skill matrix can be used by an organisation to effectively assess employee performance in the organization. The research findings show that various organizations support that human resource managers can effectively recruit and select the skilled workforce to reduce training and development costs. The skilled employees can share creative ideas and opinions to support entrepreneurs to determine the innovation needs in the organization. This finding is supported by Fix (2018) where the author mentioned that having a skilled workforce are quick to adopt the changes and innovation. In contrast, a lack of educated and trained staff limit innovation in the organization.

According to Schmitz, (2017), training and development critically assures that the business is investing employees. Employees then are willing to go an extra mile for the business. Another benefit of training and development program is the fact that it increases the overall knowledgebase of the organization where skilled workers dedicatedly work for the business. Once the overall knowledgebase is increased it becomes easy for the organization to innovate or to bring in the change within the organization. This is what has been revealed through the interview as well. Different programs have been initiated for different level of employees to further expand the overall knowledge of the organization.

Sub-theme 2: Human collaboration and team working skills are critical to the innovation process.

This theme elaborates that both collaboration and teamwork includes a group of people performing together to complete the shared objectives. The main difference between team working and collaboration is that teamwork effectively integrates the efforts of individuals and all team members to meet the strategic objectives. In addition, people performing or working collaborating completely the project collectively. The collaborative framework has been proposed to bring together the current activities and suggest the framework for entrepreneurs to enhance the product and service delivery. It is found that the collaboration framework mentions the shared principles and commitment that encourage the common objectives of the collaboration. This theoretical model guides organizations and entrepreneurs to encourage collaboration and teamwork to enhance performance and creativity in the organization.

The findings of the research indicate that number of the organisation believes that teamwork and collaboration are crucial to the effectiveness and success of the innovative practice. Khawam et al. (2017) mentioned that an integrated environment reduces conflict, enhance relationships, and increase creative and innovative ideas in an organization. Majority of the organisation believes that employee coordination and communication through meeting helps most of the employees to be motivated, honest, and informed about the professional and innovation objectives. Stegen and Wankier (2018) argued that teamwork allows different qualified and skilled employees to share their own perspectives about the problem. The team provides a pool of ideas. The research findings revealed that female entrepreneurs in Algeria often do not surround themselves with the people and lack of teamwork could cause various limitations to become innovative.

According to Shabbir, Muhammad and Kassim, (2019), one of the basic features of modern organization is teamwork and collaboration focused on generating precise and effective results for the business. It helps the business by covering the loopholes and by strengthening the overall idea generation abilities. With collaboration, businesses are actually able to draft and work on ideas that bring in the betterment in the organization. Siakas, and Siakas, (2016), also argued that through teamwork allows the business to remain highly effective and efficient while focusing on the opportunities to grow and eliminating the overall loopholes.

6.6 Theme 6: Impact of innovation practices on business performance

This theme defines that innovation is highly important for the success and effectiveness of the business. The sub-theme covers the innovation process to overcome the business challenges and enhance customer satisfaction in the long run.

Sub-theme 1: Innovation helps to overcome challenges and improve customer satisfaction

According to Pashaeypoor et al. (2016), innovation plays a crucial role in increasing customer satisfaction and reducing the challenges. This theme is integrated with the diffusion theory of innovation and blue ocean theory. Rogers proposes that four important components affect the spread of new ideas such as innovation itself, time, communication channels, and social system (Mohammadi et al., 2018). In contrast, blue ocean theory is an effective theory in which an organisation mainly creates the demand and makes customers realize that the product offered by company is their need and they should purchase it. Leavy (2018) found that a blue ocean theory mainly exists when there is potential for increasing profit because of low completion or irrelevant completion. This strategy intends to help entrepreneurs to capture the new demand and make completion irrelevant through introducing the new product with innovative features. It is found that the blue ocean strategy could positively support entrepreneurs to create maximum value for customers and reduce challenges.

In findings number of Respondents supports that customer satisfaction is important for the effectiveness and success of the organization. In addition, innovation is also an essential means to encourage entrepreneurs to increase customer satisfaction which leads to higher profitability and revenue. The research findings show that female entrepreneurs can adopt innovative practices to make sure the return of customers. In this regard, Leavy (2018) argued that customers often look for change and new products because they get bore with old features or products. The adaptation of the blue ocean strategy could support entrepreneurs to effectively develop and increase customer satisfaction.

Sub-theme 2: Innovation improve quality of products and services

Shi et al. (2018) argued that innovation provides a significant opportunity for businesses and entrepreneurs to enhance product quality by introducing new features. The research findings revealed that the quality of product and service is mainly considered as the top priority of the

customers and innovation practices are the essential means to enhance the overall quality of the services and products. The business essentially strives for innovative practice and customer loyalty through enhancing company performance. The product improvement and innovation also helps business to increase customer loyalty. The organisation also highlighted that there is significant and positive impact of innovation on company performance in terms of returns and finances.

6.7 Theme 7: Recommendations

Sub-theme 1: It is better to gain funds from personal resources

This theme provides a recommendation about collecting funds and resources to effectively invest. The findings show that organisation needs to seek personal contacts for finance instead of looking for external sources such as government bodies and financial institutes. Different organizations mentioned that organizations should have personal resources to effectively gain the maximum resources. Dutta et al. (2020) argued that personal funds could be limited to the adaptation of new practices. Therefore entrepreneurs should look for external sources for funds. Talaia et al. (2016) disagree on this opinion and mentioned that business should invest own money to prevent the taxes. Few organizations mentioned that getting finance is an essential thing however entrepreneurs need to develop the proper planning to use funds. Argente et al. (2018) found that receiving the funds from personal networks and through strong networking develop the entrepreneurial environments and encourage funds.

Sub-theme 2: Recruit the right employees or train them

The study found that skilled and trained employees play an important in implementing innovative strategies. Anand et al.(2018) argued that entrepreneurs need to recruit and train employees so they could able to adopt the technology and support in implementing the innovation in organization. There are number of organizations that mentioned that innovation in organisation could bring change and take organisation through one level ahead by the current level. Thus, it is important to provide the training and development program so employees can able to implement the technology and understand the innovation. The research by Katsantoni (2019) supports that innovation could bring changes that are new to employees' therefore

effective training and awareness programs need to deliver to increase competency among employees.

Sriram, and Mersha, (2017), however argued that finding the right employees for the job also depends on the labour market within the country. There are countries with high pay rates and there are countries with cheap labour rate. Moreover, the overall skill set of available workforce also varies from country to country. Consequently, it is essential for the business to focus on recruitment and selection of the employees and make it certain that the business is able to find the right personnel.

Sub-theme 3: Evaluate the external environment.

The external environment theory such as PESTEL analysis suggests that entrepreneurs need to conduct external environment analysis through using the PESTEL framework. Vladoš and Chatzinikolaou (2019) argued that PESTEL analysis is an effective strategic framework or model that support organisation on determine current business environment so that business could develop strategies accordingly. In addition, female entrepreneurs need to provide the products that are needed by customers such as innovative features in existing products or completely new products. It is found that uncertain economic and political environment is the two crucial elements that must be analyzed to determine the future innovative strategies.

The research findings revealed that the assessment of the external environment helps businesses to implement the best possible solutions that are innovative. The findings suggest that to effectively conduct the external environment analysis to have innovation the organisations mentioned that companies could observe their competition and conduct research and development to obtain proper information. Neneh (2016) supported this idea that the external environment plays a crucial role in the failure or success of innovative practices. Sriram, and Mersha, (2017) further added that it is the external environment that influences the business towards the greatest extent. All of the strategies, the marketing tactics, the sustainability and many more are to adhere with the influence of the external environment. The cases incorporated within the study also reveal that the similar findings, for example, case 3 mentions that there are no specific guidelines or authoritative bodies in the country that could help the entrepreneurs specifically female. Moreover, the mindset of customers, policies, ease of doing business, nature of customers, nature of competitors, availability of resources, infrastructure to support

entrepreneurship and many more are some of the factors from the external environment that tend to influence the business venture and its growth and development.

6.8 Summary:

This chapter summarizes the different themes driven from the findings of interview. The discussion is then analyzed through the help of literature review to determine the differences and commonalities. One important aspect revealed is the fact that female entrepreneurs in Algeria do believe that innovation is the key for business growth. Moreover, it is also realized that workforce play an important role within the growth of the business and also act as the biggest resistance towards the change. Nevertheless, the overall environment of the country tends to impact the entrepreneurial environment and either it supports or restricts the growth of entrepreneurs. It is also realized that most of the findings are aligned with the overall literature review.

7 Chapter 7: Conclusion and Recommendation

7.1 Introduction

This is the last chapter of the research that highlighted the key findings of the research and defines the concluding marks that have been drawn from the gathered data and analysis. The chapter includes recommendations for the target audience and defines the ways female entrepreneurship can be improved using innovation practices. The chapter highlights the limitations of the research and also offer suggestions for doing future research.

7.2. Conclusion

The purpose of the research was to investigate the effectiveness of the innovative practices adopted by female entrepreneurs in Algeria and making them a recommendation on the ways they can use innovative practices to enhance their business growth. For the attainment of this goal, the first objective of the research was, *“To conduct a comprehensive literature review to understand the Algerian entrepreneurial environment, female entrepreneurship, and innovation practices in Algeria.”* This objective was achieved by having a detailed review of the existing literature. The findings disclosed that the Algerian environment is still negative for female entrepreneurs due to many reasons. It has been assessed that innovation is not a limited concept to product and process innovation. Innovation is of different types including process innovation, marketing innovation, organisational innovation, technological innovation, and sales innovation. The data disclosed that process and technological innovations are some of the key aspects that took place in the practical world of female entrepreneurship. The best way that female entrepreneurs adopted was the finding of marketing gaps and then building on those gaps. It has been assessed that both breakthrough and incremental innovation has been a part of female entrepreneurship.

The second objective of the research was, *“To understand the purpose of the use of innovative practices in female-owned businesses in Algeria”*. To achieve this objective literature was reviewed and primary data through interviews was also collected from female entrepreneurs belonging to different industries. The data disclosed that innovation has been a part of female entrepreneurial world due to many reasons, but some of the major reasons that encouraged female to include business expansion, organisational growth, adding value for customers, and the

thrust of solving others' problems. One of the key benefits of innovation is the contribution to the growth of businesses. Innovation help entrepreneurs in driving higher productivity and profitability; and female entrepreneurs when intends to move towards growth they look for the adoption of technology. Growth expectations are one of the major reasons for innovation practices adopted by female entrepreneurship. When female entrepreneurs decide to expand the business they rather managing the status quo seek new things. The study disclosed that female entrepreneurs for business growth either seek product development, market development, market penetration through improving existing products and processes, or by diversification.

For business growth, entrepreneurs look at the fulfilment of the needs of customers. The needs and expectations of customers are two of the top priorities for female entrepreneurial businesses. Hence, female entrepreneurs adopt innovative practices that help their businesses in adding value for customers. The study disclosed that customer satisfaction is an imperative element for the success of entrepreneurial businesses and the objective of innovation should be to meet the needs of customers. The research results highlighted that product differentiation and penetration are two of the most effective entrepreneurial innovation practices that female entrepreneurs use for their business development. The innovation practices donate to adding value for customers by adding features to the product or modifying those products that allow businesses to resolve customer problems. Innovations help companies to make the competition irrelevant rather than competing with other firms in the industry. The reason for making the competition irrelevant is that less competition or no competition allows a business to earn high profits

The third objective of the research was, *To explore the factors that influence the innovative practices positively adopted by the female-owned businesses in Algeria.*” For the attainment of this objective primary data was collected from female entrepreneurs through interviews. The findings revealed that social entrepreneurs have always been interested in offering solutions to people's problems. It has been assessed that technological advancements and Research and Development (R&D) have been two of the major factors that supported innovations within female entrepreneurial businesses. The external environment of Algeria is uncertain and may cause current and future problems that may influence the business processes, policies, and products that are performing well. The innovative practices include the adoption of new solutions to the customers and resolve their pain points. The research disclosed that technological

innovations are paramount to increase business performance. Technological innovations can support organizations in increasing their creativity and innovation and meeting the changing needs of customers. Female entrepreneurs seek opportunities in their surroundings and take the advantage of these gaps or weaknesses by considering them as a chance to innovate things.

When discussing the factors that influence innovation practices adopted by female entrepreneurs, technological advancements and Research and Development (R&D) have been considered on the top. The study disclosed that customer's satisfaction and meeting their needs is a major concern of businesses because customers are the biggest sources of their income. Technologies adopted by female entrepreneur's support meeting the needs of customers and resolving the customer satisfaction concerns of businesses. It has been assessed that female entrepreneurs must need to come up with advanced technology that is not offered by the rivals for gaining the first-mover advantage. Technology enables female entrepreneurship to provide an integrated platform that helps employees in exchanging ideas. Technological advancements are crucial for improving the overall effectiveness and quality of female entrepreneurial firms that help to bring innovations to their businesses. Further, human coordination and collaboration have been some of the core factors donating to the success of female entrepreneurs despite having multiple difficulties. Human collaboration is one of the major aspects that contribute to the success of businesses. Human collaboration is a way of bringing innovations to the business. Technological advancements are helping female entrepreneurs in innovation and improving them in enhancing communication and collaboration that is compulsory for becoming a successful and entrepreneurial business. Considering the increasing role of technology in innovations, the study suggested that female entrepreneurs should make significant investments in technological advancements for continuous innovations and growth.

The research also highlighted that Research and Development (R&D) is decisive for appropriate technology and innovation. The results revealed that the needs and expectations of customers change frequently. Market research is paramount for determining the needs of customers. It is expected from entrepreneurs to deliver a high-quality product for their customers. For delivering highlight quality product is not an easy task; it demands conscious choices and informed decision making. The application of Research and Development is mandatory for making conscious choices to invest in the promotion and commercialization of new products and services.

Investment in R&D activities allows female entrepreneurs to determine the current market trends and analyse the market changes for identifying opportunities for innovation. R&D is an effective business activity for collecting information for innovation and introducing new products. Entrepreneurial businesses that lack R&D activities are unable to successfully adopt innovations. In other words, the findings revealed that the lack of Research and Development activities by entrepreneurs limit their process of adopting innovation. Therefore, the research recommends entrepreneurs that they must invest in R&D for the application of innovation to meet the financial and technological requirements.

The fourth objective of the research has been, “*To understand the challenges facing female entrepreneurs in Algeria in the use of innovative practices.*” This objective was reached using primary data collected from female entrepreneurs. The research findings highlighted some of the external factors that influence innovation practices in Algeria adopted by female entrepreneurship. It has been assessed that the economic situation of the country is not good that motivate female to involve in entrepreneurial activities. The increasing unemployment and lower purchasing power of the country is one of the major reasons that push female in Algeria to enter the business world. The second external factor that influences female entrepreneurs includes the male dominating culture of the country. It has been assessed that in the male dominating culture of Algeria, the power and financial structure are under the control of male instead of the female which negatively affect female entrepreneurship and innovation within the country. Findings of the research disclosed that people in Algeria consider that females are not talented and competent. Algerian culture is male dominating and people believe that only males can provide creative solutions to problems. However, some studies disclosed that female entrepreneurs and men should be provided with equal opportunities. The results disclosed that the political environment in Algeria is not stable and one of the major barriers for female entrepreneurship within the country. The findings of the research revealed that the political and government regulations of the country are strict that create limitations in the success of female entrepreneurship and also do not allow female entrepreneurs to adopt innovative practices. Though the political environment of the country contains some policies and proved to be supportive for adopting innovation practices; but, this support is limited to some specific sectors such as the healthcare sector. Competition is a driver of technological innovation; the research unleashes the fact that increasing competition poses a challenge for businesses for retaining and

attracting customers. The findings revealed that female entrepreneurs are challenged by the competitive environment in Algeria and adopting innovative practices is a way to remain competitive. The competitive environment is not fair for female entrepreneurs within the country.

However, it has been observed that Algeria is full of challenges, as the environment of the country is not supported for entrepreneurship. Further, the culture of the country is male dominating; hence, the cultural environment of the country is more challenging for female entrepreneurs compared to male entrepreneurs. It has been assessed that lack of finances is one of the top challenges that female entrepreneurs face in Algeria, though some organisations offer financial support to entrepreneurs this financial support is more for men compared to females. Further, the documentation process of these institutions is lengthy that discourage female entrepreneurs within the country. The administrative culture of the financial bodies makes the process complex that creates delays. The financial bodies do not provide any assistance and lack in taking follow-ups that create challenges for female in Algeria. Even, the financial bodies have been designed to aid people, but the fact is that they are not helpful for people who are zero in finance. It has been assessed that lack of qualified, skilled, and experienced people are also some of the key challenges that female entrepreneurs face when they start their businesses. Finding the right candidate for the business is also amongst the major challenges due to the short of talent. Female just not lack in finding opportunities in Algeria, but they also face challenges in gaining training and development (T&D) opportunities that push female to give up their ideas and hopes. Due to the lack of practical training and development (T&D), female entrepreneurs lack technical competencies and the abilities to identify opportunities and adapt to things. The lack of acceptance is observed in Algerian society for female entrepreneurship. Though the country has realised the managerial skills of female and their abilities to be good decision-maker, the conservative culture is still one of the major challenges for female entrepreneurship.

7.3. Contribution of the Research

7.3.1. Theoretical Contributions

The conceptual framework of this research is a theoretical contribution to the concepts. The research enhances the theoretical understanding of the macro-environmental factors (political, economic, social, technological, and legal) that how these factors positively or negatively

influence the adoption of innovative practices. The research contributed to building the understanding of micro-level factors (such as competitors, suppliers, and customers) and the ways they influence female entrepreneurship.

The research holds theoretical underpinning by highlighting the entrepreneurial attributes that support female entrepreneurs within Algeria and the attributes that must improve to be successful. Innovation practices have a positive influence on entrepreneurial growth and multiple factors influence the adoption of these practices. The lack of a positive social culture of the country, financial support by the government, human capital, and technological advancements are some of the major barriers to the adoption of innovative practices.

Networking skills contain huge importance in the entrepreneurial world and offer immense support to entrepreneurs in terms of adopting innovation practices. The findings contribute to the theory of networking and stated it as a positive skill that female entrepreneurs must adopt to have growth and bring innovative practices to their companies.

The research enhances the theoretical understanding of female entrepreneurs and the factors that influence female entrepreneurs in Algeria. The research contributes to understanding the application of cultural and innovation theories of the real entrepreneurial world. The study enhances the understanding of the ways innovation practices contribute to the success of entrepreneurial businesses and the reasons entrepreneurs adopt innovation. The research also highlights the types of innovations that can be adopted to gain a competitive advantage.

7.3.2. Managerial Contribution

Algeria suffers from a great deficit of relations between the world of academic research and the economic reality of the country. This situation invites the government and scholars to be involved in future projects, concerning the research system which would highlight the reality of the Algerian business and entrepreneurial environment. This research is a contribution to the practical research system of the country as it tints on the real business situation and the entrepreneurial environment of Algeria. The research contains practical applications because it highlights cultural, political, and competitive factors that create hindrance in the way of female entrepreneurship. Though multiple studies have been conducted on female entrepreneurs, the research on female entrepreneur in Algeria was under-research. This research is beneficial for

Algerian female entrepreneurs. The research is beneficial in highlighting the factors that need to be improved to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of female entrepreneurs. The research suggests female entrepreneurs enhance collaboration and coordination with others and develop partnerships to overcome skill development issues. The research contributed that female entrepreneurs should focus on gaining higher education and should be enrolled in entrepreneurial courses and focus on the hiring and selection process to have the best talent. The practical findings contributed that female must not seek governmental support in terms of finances and must utilise their networking skills to have finances for innovation practices. The research contributed that female entrepreneurs should invest in Research and Development (R&D) activities, keep their staff motivated, bring flexibility in processes, should know their competition.

This piece of work contributes, with its comprehensive framework, to the existing literature and theories surrounding female entrepreneurship in Algeria. So far, studies have been separately discussing female entrepreneurship and the adoption of innovative practices. This research overcomes this gap by discussing female entrepreneurship and innovation practices together. This research using a comprehensive conceptual framework reflects on the micro-environmental, macro-environmental, and cultural factors that influence the adoption of innovative practices by female entrepreneurs. The framework also fills the gap by highlighting the factors that can help to boost innovation within female entrepreneurial businesses. The research also discusses the drivers of innovation practices within female entrepreneurial businesses that have not been discussed in the literature widely. However, this study demonstrates the ways innovative practices can help the performance of female entrepreneurial businesses in Algeria. This study through its conceptual framework contributes practically towards female entrepreneurial businesses. It provides the target audience with various critical success factors that can be used to improve entrepreneurial understanding. Therefore, this report is significant for government institutions supporting entrepreneurship, financial institutions, and female in Algeria. The research has a positive impact on the development of female entrepreneurship in the country. The research by highlighting the role of female entrepreneurship in the economic development of the country and highlighting the role of innovation practices can make a huge contribution to the development of entrepreneurial policies at the government level within the country.

The research also assists policymakers in the ways they can improve their political environment for female entrepreneurs because it can help the country in resolving one of the biggest issues of unemployment and poverty. The research is beneficial for female entrepreneurs in highlighting the ways that can help them in creating competitive advantage and adopt innovative practices.

7.4. Recommendation

This section offers recommendations based on the findings of this research. The section has been divided into two major sections. The first segment of this section provides recommendations for female entrepreneurs for improving the adoption of innovative practices. However, the second segment provides recommendations for government professionals or policymakers for improving their practices and provides support for female entrepreneurial activities. Female entrepreneurial activities are necessary to promote the betterment of the country because female entrepreneurship can help the government in achieving its aim of reducing unemployment and poverty.

7.4.1. Recommendations for Entrepreneurs

- Female entrepreneurs in Algeria are facing significant issues in continuing with entrepreneurial activities; they are facing the issues of finding the right talent and also lack entrepreneurial competencies and capabilities. Hence, female entrepreneurs are suggested to enhance collaboration and coordination with others and develop partnerships so they can overcome the issues of skill development (Bernstein and Turban, 2018; Berger et al., 2019; Iglesias and Ind, 2017). Having partnerships can help female entrepreneurs to overcome the financial limitations and the issues of limited human capital (Mosbah, 2014).
- Female entrepreneurs should focus on gaining higher education and should get enrolled in entrepreneurial courses at a personal level as no support is being provided by the government of Algeria (Jebari, 2016; Tahir, 2016). Female entrepreneurs should focus on the hiring and selection process and should recruit talent from the wider talent pool. The entrepreneurial businesses can further train and develop their employees for better adoption and creation of innovation practices (Kleinsmann et al., 2017; Buffart et al., 2020). By getting enrolled in entrepreneurial courses and providing training and

development opportunities to employees, female can overcome the issues of lack of skilled and qualified employees (Stegen and Wankier, 2018).

- Financial constraints are one of the biggest problems for female entrepreneurs within the country. It is recommended that female entrepreneurs must not seek governmental support. They must find alternative solutions for getting funds or having financial support. Making partnership and building networks can be some of the effective practices for gaining finances for businesses (Salto, 2021).
- Further, to enhance innovation at the organisational level, female entrepreneurs are suggested to invest in Research and Development (R&D). R&D will help female entrepreneurs in finding opportunities and making informed decisions to take advantage of these market available opportunities (Wolfe, 2016; Zhu et al., 2016). Innovation practices adopted based on R&D are effective and result oriented. R&D allows companies to bring innovations that can support the development of product and processes that can better meet the demand and needs of customers (Guerrero-Villegas et al., 2018).
- Female entrepreneurs are suggested to have flexibility in their practice and keep the staff informed and motivated with changes required in the business processes (Neumeyer et al., 2019). Flexibility in processes and schedules make the adoption of new things easy and help firms in generating sustainable competitive advantage. Female entrepreneurs should build a culture of teamwork and collaboration. The collaborative organisational culture delivers companies with new ideas and makes the effective implementation of these ideas easy.
- Competition is the least discussed and considered an aspect of Algeria by female entrepreneurs. It is recommended to female entrepreneurs that they look at the competition to have an idea of innovation practices (Distanont and Khongmalai, 2018).

7.5. Recommendations for Government professionals

- The government is already offering financial support to entrepreneurs by these institutions is not playing their role effectively (Ghiat, 2019). The process of documentation is lengthy that discourage entrepreneurs to get funds from these

governmental institutions (Acharya and Pandey, 2019). Further, these institutions are operating in the male dominating society; hence, gaining access to funds is more difficult for female entrepreneurs. The government or policymakers are suggested to design policies that make access easy to these entrepreneurial funds for female entrepreneurs. The documentation process should be easy so female may not consider the time-consuming process.

- The policymakers are recommended to offer training and development programs for female entrepreneurs that can educate them related to entrepreneurial opportunities. The training and development programs must include the content that can help female entrepreneurs in developing necessary entrepreneurial skills. Further, the government should design awareness programs and promote the entrepreneurial culture within the country to enhance entrepreneurial motivation. The government should communicate the benefits of self-employment and opportunities that exist in the country for entrepreneurs (Kleinsmann et al., 2017; Buffart et al., 2020).

7.6. Limitations

The research contains some limitations. One of the major limitations is that the research is solely based on qualitative research. The study is solely based on qualitative data and it is perceived that the qualitative data is dependent on the interpretation of the researcher; hence, the chances of bias are high. Some limitations include the research is limited to female entrepreneurs; the research has its focus on Algeria. The research considers multiple sectors; therefore, the findings may not apply to any particular sector and provide complete assistance to the specific sector.

Other than the mentioned limitations, there were some severe challenges faced during the entire project. First of all, it was of great challenge to extract the precise, accurate and updated information about Algeria. Unlike developed countries the information provided about Algeria over the internet is highly limited or with unauthentic sources of the internet. However, after careful screening of the resources, specific details about the country was extracted, cross checked and then incorporated within the study. Second challenge was associated with the data collection process. Since the objective was precisely related to the female entrepreneurs, therefore it was difficult to get hold of female businesspersons within the country. The issue multiplied due to pandemic that restricted free movements and made people to avoid unnecessary meeting.

Moreover, the entrepreneurs are also very busy in managing the sudden change that the pandemic brought and therefore it become highly complex and critical to contact the relevant personal for sample size and even for data collection. Moreover, at first, it was even difficult to extract the number of female entrepreneurs within the country and then deduce the numbers to assure that they are contactable. Nevertheless, the directory of business from the government agency was used to realize and extract information about the female entrepreneurs within the country. The second stage was to establish contact, however a strategy to extract information step by step, i.e. question by question, telephone, and email were used to acquire data and information from respondent.

Another challenge associated with the data collection was the language barrier. The data collected was in English as well as in Arabic. The Arabic language was then translated in English while assuring that the language nuances are followed effectively and efficiently without changing the context and meaning of the information provided. Nevertheless, the limitations were covered as much as possible without remaining biased and without affecting the information gathered.

7.8. Future Suggestion

For future research, some suggestions are being offered based on the above-highlighted limitations. In future, any specific industry of the country can be considered. The research is limited to Algeria; future research can be extended to other countries. This research is specific to female entrepreneurs; it can be extended to men entrepreneurs. The mixed approach can be used to come-up with unbiased findings.

The study includes limited innovation variables, some different innovation variables can be used to evaluate the innovative practices that are used by female entrepreneurs. The influence of innovation practices on female entrepreneurs can be evaluated to make a better selection of innovation practices. The research highlights the perspective of female entrepreneurs, but future research can be conducted from the perspective of government professionals for highlighting the issues that they face while supporting female entrepreneurs and the measures they are taking to overcome these issues.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: RESEARCH CONSENT FORM

Name of Researcher(s)
Halima Hachelaf
Title of study
"An Investigate into The Effectiveness of The Innovative Practices Adopted by Female Entrepreneurs in Algeria"

Please find below some key points before accepting and attending the interview session. Please circle the either Y/N as per your views.

- I have had the research satisfactorily explained to me in verbal and / or written form by the researcher. **YES / NO**
- I understand that I may withdraw from this study at any time without having to give an explanation. This will not affect my future care or treatment. **YES / NO**
- I understand that all information about me will be treated in strict confidence and that I will not be named in any written work arising from this study. **YES / NO**
- I understand that any audiotape material of me will be used solely for research purposes and will be destroyed on completion of your research. **YES / NO**
- I understand that you will be discussing with the appropriate persons at the University of the West of Scotland. **YES / NO**

I freely give my consent to participate in this research study and have been given a copy of this form for my own information.

Signature:

Date:

Appendix 2: Interview Schedule

Age Group:

- 18-20 years old.
- 21-25 years old.
- 26-30 years old.
- 31-40 years old.
- 41-50 years old.
- 51 and above.

Level of Education:

- High school.
- College.
- University (Undergraduate).
- University (Postgraduate).
- M-Phil/Phd.

Work Experience:

- Less than 2 years.
- Between 2 and 5 years.
- Between 5 and 10 years.
- Over 10 years.

Questions:

- Can you describe, briefly, what do you understand by the term “innovation practices”?
- How did you come across this concept?
- What were the factors your organization considered in the adoption of the innovation practices in your business?
- When did you start the implementation of innovation practices?
- Which kind of practices did you implement?
- Which implementation process have you used?
- How do plan budgets for innovation?

- What types of source of finance are available?
- How did you get to know about sources of finance?
- Which ones do you think are the most convenient for female entrepreneurs in terms of accessibility? And why?
- Which one did you use?
- What challenges did you when using this specific source of finance?
- For which job positions do you consider the skills related to innovation during employees' recruitment?
- What skills/capabilities do you look upon?
- Do you have some specific department/employees to manage/promote innovation practices within the organization?
- How often and how well this specific department cooperate with the rest of the departments?
- Which kind of training did you or your employees require any training in terms of the use of innovation practices?
- How frequently do you organize it? And how long does it last for?
- Did you require additional external expertise to deal with the innovation practices implemented/to be implemented?
If yes, who and why?
If not, why did you opt to take actions internally?
- Which kind of organizations do you often cooperate with?
- How are these collaborations organized? And at which frequency?
- Are you aware of potential collaboration opportunities with universities and governmental organizations?
- Why did you choose to use/reject those opportunities?
- How and how often do you collect and analyse data about the competition around you?
- In which way this data is considered and used during decision making?
- Which challenge/difficulty did you face during the implementation of the innovation practices?
- In which way was the phenomenon considered as a challenge?
- In which way have these challenges impacted your plans and willing to use innovation practices?

- Was the difficulty a one-off obstacle or persistent/continuous one?
- Which actions have been taken to overcome these obstacles?
- Which monitoring tool related/and following to the specific implementation did you use?
- What was your performance indicator when monitoring the impact of the innovation practices implemented on your organization?
- Which change/and at which level did you notice since the implementation of the innovation practices?
- How important was this change?
- What was the actual benefit from resulting from the implementation of the innovation practices for your organization?

Appendix 3: Questionnaire

Tranche d'âge:

- 18-20 ans.
- 21-25 ans.
- 26-30 ans.
- 31-40 ans.
- 41 à 50 ans.
- 51 et plus.

Niveau d'éducation:

- Lycée.
- Collège.
- Université (premier cycle).
- Université (troisième cycle).
- Doctorat

L'expérience professionnelle:

- Moins de 2 ans.
- Entre 2 et 5 ans.
- Entre 5 et 10 ans.
- Plus de 10 ans.

Questions:

- Pouvez-vous décrire brièvement ce qu'est le terme «pratiques d'innovation» pour vous?
- Comment avez-vous découvert ce concept?

- Quels facteurs votre organisation a-t-elle pris en compte avant l'adoption des pratiques d'innovation dans votre entreprise?
- Quand avez-vous commencé la mise en œuvre de pratiques d'innovation?
- Quel genre de pratiques avez-vous mis en place?
- Quel processus de mise en œuvre avez-vous utilisé?
- Comment planifiez-vous les budgets pour l'innovation?
- Quels types de sources de financement sont disponibles?
- Comment avez-vous connu les sources de financement?
- Selon vous, lesquels sont les plus adaptées pour les femmes entrepreneurs en termes d'accessibilité? Et pourquoi?
- Lequel avez-vous utilisé?
- Quels défis avez-vous rencontrés lors de l'utilisation de cette source de financement spécifique?
- Pour quels postes considérez-vous les compétences liées à l'innovation lors du recrutement des salariés?
- Quelles compétences / capacités considérez-vous?
- Avez-vous un service / des employés spécifiques pour gérer / promouvoir les pratiques d'innovation au sein de l'organisation?
- À quelle fréquence et dans quelle mesure ce département spécifique coopère-t-il avec le reste des départements?
- Quel type de formation avez-vous ou vos employés avez-vous eu besoin de formation sur l'utilisation des pratiques d'innovation?
- À quelle fréquence l'organisez-vous? Et combien de temps cela dure-t-il?
- Avez-vous eu besoin d'une expertise externe supplémentaire pour faire face aux pratiques d'innovation mises en œuvre / à mettre en œuvre?

Si oui, qui et pourquoi?

Sinon, pourquoi avez-vous choisi de prendre des mesures en interne?

- Avec quel type d'organisations coopérez-vous souvent?
- Comment ces collaborations sont-elles organisées? Et à quelle fréquence?
- Connaissez-vous les possibilités de collaboration potentielles avec les universités et les organisations gouvernementales?
- Pourquoi avez-vous choisi d'utiliser / rejeter ces opportunités?
- Comment et à quelle fréquence collectez-vous et analysez-vous des données sur la concurrence autour de vous?
- De quelle manière ces données sont-elles prises en compte et utilisées lors de la prise de décision?
- À quel défi / difficulté avez-vous été confronté lors de la mise en œuvre des pratiques d'innovation?
- De quelle manière le phénomène a-t-il été considéré comme un défi?
- De quelle manière ces défis ont-ils eu un impact sur vos projets et votre volonté d'utiliser des pratiques d'innovation?
- La difficulté était-elle un obstacle ponctuel ou persistant / continu?
- Quelles mesures ont été prises pour surmonter ces obstacles?
- Quel outil de suivi lié / et suivant à la mise en œuvre spécifique avez-vous utilisé?
- Quel a été votre indicateur de performance lors du suivi de l'impact des pratiques d'innovation mises en place sur votre organisation?
- Quel changement / et à quel niveau avez-vous remarqué depuis la mise en place des pratiques d'innovation?
- Quelle était l'importance de ce changement?
- Quel a été l'avantage réel résultant de la mise en œuvre des pratiques d'innovation pour votre organisation?

Appendix 4: Case Studies Details

Case Study 1

Overview of Entrepreneur 1

- **Type**

The entrepreneur is the female businesses owner of a school.

- **Age and education**

The interviewee is a 60-year-old professional and passionate French teacher with high-level educational qualifications.

- **Experience**

Overall, she has a working experience of 20 years, which involved teaching as well as other professional experiences. She has been teaching in schools in Algeria and she now owns a private school in Algeria, which has been operating for the last 15 years. She considers teaching as her heart job and has taught in public for a few years. Then, she switched her job and worked in the newspaper 'Le Figaro'. In 1988, she had to leave the country and when she came back, she tried starting her career again in teaching. However, it was not possible. In 1990, the French school closed, and terrorism led to creating fear among people. She was terrified but was always passionate about teaching.

- **Believes**

Being a teacher, she believes that everyone should not be allowed to open a school because of the responsibility and skills it requires. She was disappointed with the fact that even mechanics and hairdressers have opened schools.

- **Motivation**

When she began her career as a teacher in 1999, the schools did not have a legal status yet in Algeria. So, because there were gaps in the legislation, she considered it an opportunity and used

it to open a school for children. At that time, private schools had to be classified as sports organizations in the beginning to open a trade register.

As an entrepreneur, she wanted to avail of an existing opportunity and do something good for the children. A lot of challenges were faced as a result of the regulations, along with teacher training, and children's development needs. Indeed Algeria lacked teacher training, and it was very difficult to find teachers who could do their jobs efficiently. She has seen things evolving and changing with time.

The interview with an entrepreneur disclosed that she contains a lot of passion for her work and prioritises the educational aspect of her business. She describes herself as someone who loves and adheres to new reforms and methods, shaped by her carrier in Algeria and France. Always looking for collaboration, she is a member of the “Algerian private schools” association where a lot of knowledge is shared and programs are put in place to promote knowledge and idea sharing.

- **Challenges**

Some barriers related to the practice of innovation in the organisation have been discussed, which includes mainly resistance from teachers and parents, and lack of training. It has been assessed that the hiring of qualified employees is hard task as the available workforce is either retired teachers, who are too influenced by old practices and would not accept novelty easily, or freshly graduated, who lack in knowledge. Another major barrier that exists to the way of innovation includes government regulations that promotes on the adoption of old practices. Indeed, in 2005, the state ruled and legislated and school that were freely delivering their services saw specification issued and had to abide the law. Since, schools must fit to the rules and were obliged to implement the national curriculum and some specific programs. Lack of finances for the educational sector in the country is another main concern when it comes to innovation and it has been determined that there is no source to get loans for the educational sector; private educational institutions can't accept donations.

Overview of Organisation 1

When discussing the organisation, the interviewee stated that the idea of the organisation generated in a group discussion with some college friends. Algeria lacked a good school system for children, which affected the development of children in many ways. So, they decided to open

a school of their own from scratch. They did not have the required capital to manage things out. So, she turned her own house into a school. She used to live with her parents, but they adjusted. The idea came out to be great and every year than opened an additional level. This was how the school came into existence in her own house, own kitchen, and own garden. She even used her children's desks. For three years, the school functioned in the same manner before she could rent a room and grow her school.

- **How idea took place**

It was a smart idea, which intended to bring a real change to the educational system. She wanted to train children as well as teachers as, according to entrepreneur 1, schools are based on a value system and aim to support the citizens of tomorrow. With time, innovative ideas have been implemented to benefit the students as well as the teachers and the community. Changes are planned to have a positive impact on the students. However, the feasibility of the changes is discussed in terms of finances and costs.

The private school offers diverse programs that are a mixture of both the Algerian national program (taught in Arabic) including history, religious education and the French curriculum (taught in French) including maths, science, and physics in French. The school contains a mechanism of bilingualism that is an innovative feature of this private school. This is meant to help the pupils when they get to university, knowing that higher education is mainly in French. The school does not have any external funding. They have developed a status, so they use their own money.

The organisation is made of an administration team, the management team, and service staff for the kitchen, security, garden, and the teachers. To grow and expand, they have collaborated with foreigners. The school has sent some kindergarten educators with an association of retirees from the field to go around the world and volunteer.

- **Mission and capital requirements**

The mission of the school is to enhance the education system for the early development of children. The vision is to support education and growth in the country. The capital amount of the business was \$370105.88. The school initially made \$462632.35 in revenue and currently, the

school's revenue is \$721706.47 annually. The operating expenses of the company are more than 73% that leaves the company with \$180426.62 annually.

Case Study 2

Overview of Entrepreneur 2

- **Type**

The entrepreneur is a female businesses owner of retail stores that offer painting and finishes services.

- **Age and education**

She belongs to the age group of 41 to 50 and she is a postgraduate. She completed her industrial chemistry degree in 2002.

- **Experience**

She worked in completely irrelevant sectors for five years. She performed her duties in diverse domains and performed the role of quality controller in the pharmaceutical industry, then as a pharmaceutical sales representative, and as a saleswoman of a home appliance company. After five years, she has been commercial assistance for a painting and decoration company. She has developed a passion for this domain and gained immense knowledge that enabled her to get promoted as a manager at the same company.

- **Believes**

As an entrepreneur, the female business owner of the organisation 2 believes that customer satisfaction is highly relevant and that the products must be developed, designed, and changed according to customer needs. According to her, the success of a business relies on persistence and willingness to work and contribute to the creation of something new.

- **Motivation**

The overall idea of a woman creating her own factory in this domain in Algeria is a success in itself that motivated entrepreneur to take a step further and product innovation helped considerably the business in gaining success and is raising the chances of the success of her

factory project. To maximise the expansion projects, the business has also partnered with artists and people working in the building and construction sector.

- **Challenges**

Being a woman, the entrepreneur was facing difficulties during her employment-related to work conditions. Hence, she decided to move forward and thought to become an entrepreneur. It is almost by necessity, as the woman describes, that she started her own business regardless of the warnings on the challenges process this requires. She had developed a passion for painting and decorating products along with a network of suppliers/clients, she decided to have her own store. She gradually expanded and owns a chain of stores. Her ambition was to be specialized as a colourist and have her production of a painting.

Overview of Organisation 2

The organisation which came into existence in 2011 consists of a chain of stores that deal with painting and decoration products. The products offered are new to the market and not easily available to customers anywhere else. The introduction of such stores and the ambition to create a factory - in a culture where female are more prone to operate in clothing, food, health, and education domains - is an innovative concept.

- **How idea took place**

The entrepreneur used Algeria's CNAC program that is meant to help the creation of enterprises and support their growth. However, female entrepreneur 2 felt this organism was mainly a source of finance only as it lacked the promised support, an issue that the entrepreneur herself has risen to the relevant authorities during a seminar related to the CNAC system.

During the interview, it was found out that the business started on a very small scale and that help was required in different domains at the creation stage, indeed, entrepreneur 2 worked in partnership at this stage. Four years later, when the business expanded, they chose to dissolve the partnership.

- **Mission and capital requirements**

The mission of the organisation to offer exceptional quality that exceeds the demands of the customers. The vision is to grow and achieve growth and success in the long run. The organisation used \$462632.35 in the beginning to manage finances and operations. The company in its first year even could not reach the breakeven point and only gained \$423771.23. However, when the company made revenue of DA \$590318.88 in their fourth year, the partners decided to separate.

Case study 3

Overview of Entrepreneur3

- **Type**

Respondent is a female business owner of the private school.

- **Age and education**

She is 39 years old and she holds a graduate degree.

- **Experience**

She had been a teacher for 5 years in a private school then played the role of a principal for 2 years in a private school. She has more than 15 years of experience in the educational field.

- **Believes**

The entrepreneur believes that schools need to continuously focus on innovation and development to meet the changing needs. The educational sector is going through various changes globally. The schools have now become responsible not only for educating students but also participating in their growth and development. The teachers are taking different training courses to enhance their skills and capabilities to play their roles and responsibilities effectively and efficiently. The role of teachers has evolved and developed with time. In consideration, the schools are required to use innovative ideas to design their curriculum and plan activities for children. The integration of extra curriculum activities has become crucial for the development of children.

- **Motivation**

After getting the role of a principal, she observed that she could open her own school and offer some better environment to children; then she moved towards opening her own school. She saw that Algeria lacked schools in certain areas, so she chose an area and built her school. As an individual, she believes in changes and developments with time. She is training herself as well as an educator to learn new teaching methods to ensure the satisfaction of parents and students. Her experience and skills development have helped her in pursuing her goals and becoming a successful entrepreneur in the challenging environment of Algeria. She believes in collaborating with parents to achieve her goals. The open ideas and experience helped in observing the needs of students and parents.

- **Challenges**

Financing has been one of the key challenges for entrepreneur in the way of starting and expanding the business.

Overview of Organisation 3

The private school is from class 1 to class 10 that offers high educational services to its students. The school offers innovative pedagogy and activities; the school offers monthly outings and offers value-added services in terms of bus service that helps to reduce the traffic problems that people locally face. The school includes a video surveillance system for live streaming on the website to gain confidence and enhance transparency. The school stays open and has a holiday club to help parents in keeping children busy during the vacations. The school opens from 7:00 to 18:00 which is rare. The school is always trying to innovate the curriculum and add more activities to facilitate the learning and development of the students as well as meeting the needs of parents.

The school has a canteen for lunch only, which serves the Kindergarten students who require snacks at 10 am. It has also introduced monthly educational outings for students of different age groups. Special classes have also been introduced for children with special needs. The budget is limited so the innovation and changes are proposed and planned accordingly. The curriculum and the contents of the lessons have been modified to meet the requirements of the current education level. The school gives priority to hygiene, safety, and functionality. They also comply with the law and regulations.

- **How the idea took place**

The introduction of infancy for kindergarten was an innovative idea, which gave priority to the needs of the students. The female business owner saw the gap in the services and came with the idea to open school for children. The employees and teachers were involved in the process of innovation as they share unique and innovative ideas.

- **Mission and capital requirements**

The mission of the organisation is to add value to the education sector and support the early education of children. The vision is to take advantage of advanced and modern techniques and approaches to facilitate learning and development. The entrepreneur used only \$323842.65 as investments in the initial phase. The school in its initial year reached to \$360853.23 revenue. Currently, the school is making approximately \$730959.12 in terms of revenue.

Case Study 4

Overview of Entrepreneur4

- **Type**

Respondent is the CEO of a consulting company.

- **Age and education**

She is a post-graduate with an age of 31 to 40.

- **Experience**

She has an experience of 10 years in diverse fields. After working in diverse companies, she joined a consulting company, and then Respondent decided to open its own consulting company. She established the organisation with a spirit of providing research-based advises to the clients.

- **Believes**

She believes in positive ideas about innovation and its needs. She believed in taking risks as an entrepreneur and her long-term thinking and planning helped her in becoming a successful leader. When she started her business, she had not a financial base. She tried to find out contacts

and developed her skills to become versatile. She analyzed the market also listened to the ideas provided by others.

- **Motivation**

She was always passionate about using her skills to do something relevant that motivated her to start her business. She believes in long-term and structured planning. Rather than making money, she focused on building contacts and network. She wanted to register her company to ensure long-term success. As the number of female are taking up roles and participating in the markets, she believes that the competition level is increasing.

- **Challenges**

When she started her business she found out how the female faced issues in availing opportunities in Algeria and how the lack of finance and basic training makes female give up their ideas and hopes.

Overview of Organisation 4

The business is a consulting company that was established in 2012 and now contains 25 employees. The company started with 5 employees and the demand for its services improved that led the business towards expansion. The company provides consultation on managing the enterprises and reflect on new ways in this regard. The idea of the business was based on helping other businesses in managing their strategies and products and also providing consultancy on the ways to approach customers.

- **How idea took place**

The planning and changes are based on long-term thinking and market developments. She believed that small and medium businesses are trying hard to make their place in the industries. As a small organisation of 25 employees, each of them participates by sharing ideas and coming with innovative ideas. To gain success, it is important to capitalise on resources and hire professionals. So, as a consultancy, the interviewee stated that they are analysing the market and providing relevant solutions and ideas related to business success.

The organisation relies on innovative practices as the management gives priority to the current trends to consider the factors that influence information technology. The consulting business provides consultancy related to information technology. The innovative practices have helped in introducing new ways to manage enterprises. Most of the female entrepreneurs in Algeria have started small companies with less than 5 employees. However, the innovative idea of consultation helped in starting up with a bigger team. They innovate on a daily basis in different ways. The changes are brought according to the market changes rather than focusing on long-term decisions. The company has around 25 employees, which has helped differentiating from the large companies. The employees in the company help other employees in managing the work according to the requirements. The innovative practices are managed on a case-by-case strategy, which is treated on a daily basis. The external funding is low and it is relatively easier to attract young professional engineers for different roles. Comparatively, the large organisations easily attract investments and bank loans. However, the small and medium organisations face a tough time in managing their budget and convincing the investors and banks. As entrepreneurs, the female are more structured as they focus on long-term planning. However, their professional network is weak so they rely on formal associations to compete and manage.

- **Mission and capital requirements**

The mission of the organisation is to help other businesses in growing and expanding. The vision is to become the leading consultancy in the country with the highest number of clients. The business initiated on a small scale with an investment of around 2.0 to 2.5 million, which helped in managing the assets, infrastructure, and operations.

Case Study 5

Overview of Entrepreneur 5

- **Type**

Respondent is a female entrepreneur who owns a school that comprises of 200 to 300 employees.

- **Age and education**

She is 39 year old with a high degree education.

- **Experience**

She has professional experience of more than 10 years.

- **Believes**

She believes that in the field of education, innovation is based on the progression of the syllabus and improving the quality of knowledge and information shared. She believes in innovation and the importance of innovativeness. According to her, innovation not only helps in meeting demands but also helps in mitigating the limitations and constraints.

As an entrepreneur, she believes that it is important to meet the needs and demands of customers. In her case, the parents and students are the customers. She believes in taking advantage of technology to enhance the overall quality and effectiveness.

- **Motivation**

Her professional experience helped her in realising the importance of skills development. As she is dealing with the children and their needs, she has been open to ideas and development. She is highly passionate about her role, responsibilities, and trust in her skills and capabilities. She believes in evolution, which helps in playing a role more effectively. She works individually with her team, which helps in improving the quality and ensures that the performance of the school is managed adequately. She is always looking for collaborations with the available associations to improve how the knowledge is shared and how the quality of education is maintained.

- **Challenges**

Overview of Organisation 5

The school consists of around 200 to 300 employees working at different levels and positions. It is based on the idea of innovation and syllabus progression. The school is adopting innovative ideas and technology to enhance the quality of education and make the school a better and safe place for children. It does not consist of any research and development department. However, the school is improving in terms of adopting the technology. They have set up computer systems and software to manage communication and coordination at the school. The school ensures that the

educational material is renewed and enhanced with time as compared to other schools in the vicinity. In the initial phase, the school relied on the basic ability and skills of the teachers. With time, changes have been brought in the processes and activities, which has helped in bringing innovation.

- **How idea took place**

The school does not involve any external funding and the female business owner was using their own money. It started with a small investment based on personal savings, and soon the cash flow maximised by introducing facilities and new services. The school has also collaborated with different organisations to build sports facilities and fields along with renting sports clubs. However, bank loans were used to finance the school equipment. Moreover, the female entrepreneur stated that training is provided to the teachers and their work is reviewed according to the standards. They work on the foundation of skills development so that the teachers and students can learn and grow with time. The theoretical and physical training as the one followed by French teachers did was adopted in the school. They realise their responsibility as they are dealing with children. They have identified how it is important to meet the needs of educational standards, teachers, and parents. They also offer school bus services to the students and teachers so that they can conveniently travel. It is known that with time, the demands of the parents have increased, which has increased the pressure on the school. The school has a parents' association and is labelled as 'Educ France', which is a teaching certification of the French language. To improve the internal processes, the school has improved internal communication by integrating mailing systems and technology. CCTV cameras are used to monitor activities and manage the level of security. The administrative agents are provided with tablets and there are computer rooms for students. The educational platform is created to facilitate

- **Mission and capital requirements**

The school is operating with the mission to support education. The mission of the business is to bring revolutionary changes in the field of education by focusing on innovation and differentiation. The initial investment in the organisation was around \$185053 only, which helped in purchasing the equipment and necessary tools. In the first year of the facility, the school succeeded in generating the revenue of more than \$199302 due to the financial

investment in the area of training and development of teachers. At present, the school is approximately generating \$796194 on monthly basis in terms of revenue.

Case Study 6

Overview of Respondent 6

- **Type**

The entrepreneur is a female business owner of kindergarten.

- **Age and education**

The female entrepreneur selected for this interview was 56 years old and she has a Bachelor's Degree in Law.

- **Experience**

She has exclusively worked in the field of education for the last 9 years. She left her job for 15 years to raise her children. Finally, when she planned to start her career again, she opened a Kindergarten. Later, she owns a group of kindergartens.

- **Believes**

She believes in being passionate entrepreneur who is curious and loves to learn new things. Being at home for a long time taking care of her house and children, the TV shows and programs on radios helped her in learning. She liked reading and heard about different entrepreneurship programs like ANEM, ANSEJ, and ANGEM. However, she did not fit the age requirements for these programs. Intrinsic motivation helped her in achieving whatever she has today. She analysed things and weighed the pros and cons before making any decisions. As she loved children and had faced a tough time managing her children, she decided to open a kindergarten to help other parents, especially mothers. She took training related to early education and worked in the field for 5 years before starting up her kindergarten.

- **Motivation**

When she completed her graduation, she had the skills and right to practice in administration. However, she wanted to take care of her children. In the 1980s and 1990s, she did not have

anyone to take care of her children. There were no kindergartens to help her out, as these facilities were available only for the government professionals. Therefore, she had nothing else to do except for choosing to teach as a profession. She completed her graduation in 1987 but was busy in her personal life. After having three children, she decided to enter the field of education as she could work when her children were in school. In Algeria, part-time work opportunities do not exist. So, most of the female choose education and teaching as their career.

- **Challenges**

The entrepreneur disclosed that she faced significant challenges while collecting financed for starting its school.

Overview of Organisation 6

The Group of Kindertartens consists of around 50 employees and is operating and dealing in Algeria. It is owned by a female entrepreneur who came up with the idea of opening a kindergarten to facilitate children as well as their parents.

- **How idea took place**

The idea was based on the fact that in the 1980s and 1990s, parents found no place to leave their children. To start-up, she inquired about the procedure and completed her training in relation to early education. For the financial aid, CNAC was contacted, which helped in meeting all the financial and formal requirements. The kindergarten is innovating by introducing new facilities, programs, and activities. They are also partnering with organisations using different mediums and tools. Value-added services are also provided to ensure the satisfaction of the students and parents. Every year, the teachers and owners plan new things so that they can keep the parents and children engaged. It is believed that early childhood education is very critical for the children as it has a strong impact on their behaviour and personality.

- **Mission and capital requirements**

The school is based on the mission of supporting mothers in managing their career by providing children with a safe place to learn and develop skills. The vision is to provide a long-term caring environment to the schools and bring changes in the education sector of Algeria.. It was found that 20% of the registration fees were kept aside so that it can be reinvested and the charges and

salaries can be paid. The initial investments involved around \$100,000, which helped in managing the initial processes. However, the adoption of innovative practices and considering the changes in the external environment helped in overcoming challenges and expanding.

Case Study 7

Overview of Respondent 7

- **Type**

The interviewee is a female business owner of an engineering company.

- **Age and education**

She is 35 year old and she is known as a specialized master at the business school.

- **Experience**

She has the experience of a professional consultant in Paris for 4 years. After this, she started her own business for 8 years. She is known as the first person to launch her website and platform. In August 2015, the website was designed to help patients in making their appointments and managing a follow up on their healthcare. She opened the IT Company, which facilitates around 22,000 users. For her brilliant and highly innovative idea, she received an innovation award as well as a start-up award of the year. She also received the ANSEJ project award.

- **Believes**

She believes that innovation is making use of something that existed previously but was used differently. She is a passionate woman who believes in taking initiatives and utilizing innovative ideas. She also believes in changes and evolution, which helped in achieving success and growth.

- **Motivation**

She wanted to make her career in doing something that can support people and show care towards them. She saw that Algeria is undergoing an epidemiological evolution of chronic diseases, which highlighted the importance of healthcare facilities. Therefore, she came up with the idea of developing solutions to help patients to make appointments.

- **Challenges**

The entrepreneur disclosed that funding has been one of the key challenges for them in the way entrepreneurial activities.

Overview of Organisation 7

The IT Company has positioned itself in the field of IT services. It is facilitating the patients in making medical appointments according to their needs. It is a solution-based business, which is based on a less invasive approach. With time, the company has evolved and improved significantly. The application provided by the company helps the doctors in managing the appointment of patients. They do not have to manage patients in their waiting rooms. It also facilitates in building a better relationship between doctors and patients.

- **How idea took place**

The idea was developed to improve the overall healthcare sector of Algeria. In-depth research was conducted and doctors were contacted to find out information. A trial launch was also managed, which helped the doctors in gaining subscriptions. The feedback provided by the patients and doctors helped in bringing relevant changes and developments in the application and technology.

The company consists of a sales team and has focused on building partnerships. To improve the business model, the sales team was dissolved. For the funding, the company contacted ANSEJ. The business started with personal funding. However, with time, investors were required to innovate and improve. When bringing changes and developments, the organisation often faces resistance from the employees. The returns of the company are positive and it has helped in managing the funding processes. The services offered by the company have expanded by gaining feedback and conducting research. The development is continuous and an agile method is integrated. Training is provided to the people as changes are integrated every 20 days. The overall performance is reviewed once a month, which facilitates the decision-making process.

- **Mission and capital requirements**

The company is operating with the mission of supporting people and enhancing the level of care and facilities provided to them. The vision of the organisation is to grow along with the growth

in the IT industry of Algeria. The investments were based on personal savings, which include \$46263.24 only.

Case Study 8

Overview of Entrepreneur 8

- **Type**

The female entrepreneur is the owner of an insurance agency.

- **AGE and education**

She is 32 year old female and she is an undergraduate in the field of accounting

- **Experience**

For 18 months, she did a practical internship in an insurance company. In addition, she has also worked for 12 years in the field of insurance in different companies. In 2013, she started up her own insurance company. In the beginning, she had a license partner, Alliance Assurance.

- **Believes**

She believes that in insurance, innovation can be based on bringing changes and developments in the products. When she started the company, they had basic products like home, profession, and car. However, with time, she explored the market and came up with new products. Most of her products are designed considering the female in Algeria considering how she can help the female in trouble. She got conventions in the field of health and education and was able to diversify her products.

She believed in meeting the changing customer needs so she introduced changes and developments accordingly. She always focused on utilising her experience and knowledge to bring new and innovative products in the market. It is her company, so she has the right to take initiatives, develop, and integrate strategies according to the needs. The field requires hard work along with the effective utilisation of resources. Therefore, she keeps herself business in analysing the market and using her knowledge to facilitate the people in Algeria.

- **Challenge**

The entrepreneur reflected that when she came up with the idea, she did not have the required financial support. Therefore, she conducted research and found out feasible options. However, she almost gave up her project because of the misinformation and bureaucracy. Nevertheless, she took advantage of her network to gain financial support. She believes in learning from mistakes and participating in the learning and development programs. She also believes in sharing her knowledge to facilitate others so that they can contribute to the growth and development of the organisation.

Overview of Organisation 8

The insurance agency is based on the idea of innovation and development. The company has launched many new products like the breakdown services. When designing and developing products, the needs of the female in Algeria are given priority.

- **How idea took place**

Product diversification has helped in gaining competence, growth, and success. The company has signed agreements with different organizations in Tunisia to provide them with breakdown assistance. Tunisia was selected as many Algerians travel to Tunisia for vacations. As they travel by car, the company provides troubleshooting and support for 24 hours. Monthly training programs are developed for the employees so that they can be trained on new products. It helps in managing the marketing and communication processes. Changes are introduced in terms of services while giving priority to the needs of the customers. The company is taking advantage of both product innovation and process innovation. The headquarters is in Algeria and the directors of the company are involved in the decision-making process.

- **Mission and capital requirements**

The organisation is operating with the mission of providing insurance to people belonging to different segments according to their needs. The vision is to support the insurance sector of the country in the long run. In the first year of the business; the company only gained \$23131.52 gross profit. However, currently, the business is generating \$57828.80 gross profit. The company is generating considerable gross profit; but, the company had to pay a significant amount in the area of training and development (T&D). After paying the expenses the business is not able to secure a huge amount that can be donated to further innovations.

Case Study 9

Overview OF Entrepreneur 9

- **Type**

Respondent is a female business owner of a private school.

- **AGE and education**

She is 29 years old; She has grown up and studied in France and holds a master's degree.

- **Believes**

In Algeria, she believes that innovation is carried out on a national level, which involves different tools and means. In the field of education, she believes that innovation can be brought in books and methods of delivering courses. Changes can also be brought by adding value-added services like extracurricular activities and providing bus services to the students and teachers.

- **Motivation**

She is a parent herself so she understands the responsibility associated with the teaching profession. She wondered if she can flourish as a mother while also pursuing her professional career, but faced more challenges. She believed that the opening hours of the existing nurseries made it difficult for the female to manage their personal and professional lives.

Other than this, during the busy work seasons, the kindergartens in Algiers were closed. Therefore, she decided to start up a primary school that can facilitate people. She used her knowledge, education, and expertise to come up with a business that can help parents and meet their needs related to the early education of their children. She focused on meeting the international standards and specifications and planned her work and start up accordingly. She saw the opportunity considering the problems faced by the working female of Algeria as they find it difficult to balance their personal and professional lives. She is also focusing on getting a diploma or personal training, which can help in restructuring the school and targeting more audience.

- **Challenge**

As an Algerian entrepreneur, she faced a lot of difficulties, as female do not easily get acceptance because of the culture and state of mind. She cares about her employees and suppliers, which is often misinterpreted, and require using different postures. As compared to men, the female face more challenges in the business world. As an entrepreneur, she focuses on the message being delivered to the clients and suppliers while communicating. She believes that innovation is something that does not exist at all and would not be in the market yet. Before starting up the school, she conducted research and found out that service providers face more challenges. In Algeria, there was no access to documentation so there was no urban plan to help in structuring the school. She did not even have any guarantee or support from the government.

Overview of Organisation 9

The private school is operating for last 14 years and has 75 employees. The organisation operates with the goal of meeting the needs of children and parents.

- **How idea took place**

In Algeria, there were limited number of nurseries and parents, especially mothers found it very difficult to manage children as there was no after-school care. However, this is a private school, which follows the French program. The school timings are from 07:00 to 18:30 and is open to 19:00. The schedule and late opening was beneficial in attracting parents. The school also remains open in August, which means that is open 12 month in a year. However, it is found that the late closing timings create troubles for the employees. The innovative practices implemented in the organisation are confronted with cultural aspects of the country. The organisation is operating in a highly challenging environment. It is very difficult to differentiate from other organisations, so they differentiate on the basis of schedules. The interests and needs of the children and parents are given priority.

- **Mission and capital requirements**

It is operating with the mission of providing quality education to children and facilitates parents in supporting children. The vision of the organisation is to lead the schools in the education sector of Algeria by using innovative and sustainable ideas. The initial investment involved \$300,000, which was based on personal funding. The entrepreneur contacted her family and friends to support the venture but highly relied on her personal savings.

Case Study 10

Overview of Entrepreneur10

- **Type**

The interviewee is the female business owner of a group of kindergarten.

- **AGE and education**

She is between 40 to 50 years old postgraduate female.

- **Experience**

She has more than 10 years. She completed her studies with a major in marketing in England and started serving a company in Algeria as a marketing assistant. The entrepreneur worked 2 years for the company and moved to another by accepting the senior position of marketing executive. However, after serving the company for 1 year, she realized to put her efforts into doing something worthwhile. She started searching for opportunities and found the idea of kindergarten. She found the idea interesting as it could enjoy childhood life while subsidizing the society as well.

- **Believes**

She believes innovation as adopting things from others and adding the personal touch to the practices. She believes that innovation is useless if the staff is not trained. She believes that innovation must be a mixture of own practices and programs with the adaption of others' pedagogies. The entrepreneur believes that value delivery is one of the major aspects of innovation. She believes that innovation is something that delivers the needs of people. Hence, she introduced some practices that were valued by parents and she is in the continuous process of introducing changes that deliver value to parents.

- **Motivation**

Her motivation was to introduce some changes in her teaching practices and methods that can help children with learning difficulties. She found that timing is an issue for working female;

hence, the institution time was extended. She was focused on answering the queries of people by offering the demanded service

- **Challenges**

The entrepreneur voiced on the lack of training and development activities to prepare entrepreneurs is one of the key barriers to the success of entrepreneurs. The entrepreneur disclosed that in the male dominating culture is a challenge for female as an entrepreneur. However, the country has some bodies to support female entrepreneurs financially, but they are not delivering purpose. Further, the administrative culture of the financial bodies makes the process complex that creates delays. The financial bodies have been designed to aid people, but the fact is that they are not helpful for people with zero finance. It has also been found that finding the right candidate for the business is also amongst the major challenges. There is a short of talent in the country and the pedagogy has no exception.

Overview of Organisation 10

The group is operating for the last 5 years with 25 employees. The group was delivering the services to normal children and children with learning difficulties. The Kindergarten group aims to facilitate female in their activities by assuring them that their children are in safe hands. The facility provides services to children with syndrome and autism. The institution aims to have collaborations with Canadian doctors and professionals for coaching and training the staff.

- **How idea took place**

The group of Kindergarten identified concerns of parents related to the timing of the facility. The group found the market gap as an opportunity and extended its time of operations. The normal schools operate from 8:00 to 17:00, but her institution operates from 7:00 to 18:00. The entrepreneur found the gap that the majority of Kindergarten schools do not offer services throughout the year, which is troublesome for parents. Hence, the school distinguished from rivals by offering 12 months services. She believes innovation as a process of collaboration. The entrepreneur has been a person who finds market gaps as an opportunity to expand on and take advantage. She utilised her knowledge and experience to the facility to bring the most from it. The institution has an intention to operate on weekends as a childcare place. The innovations or

changes at the group are occurring as a result of parents' demand. The institution contains staff who is trained in first aid that separates the institution from other Kindergartens.

- **Mission and capital requirements**

The mission of the group is to offer excellent care and quality educational programs and services to children in the absence of their parents. The initial funds that were invested in the facility were \$231316.18. In the first year the school successful earned 10% of the investment \$23131.62 as net profit. Currently, the business is successfully making \$46263.24 on an annual basis.

- **Experience**

The entrepreneur was experienced and had spent approximately 40 years in the field of medicine. She started her business 39 years ago. She faced difficulties initially, but later she understood the mechanism and the ways clinics could sustain in the industry.

- **Believes**

She believes in change and states it as a fundamental factor of entrepreneurship. According to the entrepreneur, the world is changing frequently so are the demands of people. Hence, it is necessary for companies that they alter their practices with the advanced ones. The change in the business world is prominent that led the entrepreneur to think of different ways. She believes that being unique is not necessary in the medical world to succeed. However, quality provision is core. She considers that innovation does not mean to come up with the services or products that have not been introduced by others. Innovation is new for the business itself no matter it is common to the world. She started with birthing centres, but later she expanded the clinical operations and incorporated surgical facilities as well. She believes in adopting a proactive approach rather than reacting to the situations.

- **Motivation**

The realization of the entrepreneur for the need to change practices and satisfying customers motivated her to become an entrepreneur. The experience taught her lessons, which she deployed to her business, and had been successful in the industry. She came to know that innovations do

not occur in a vacuum, collaboration and partnerships are necessary for bringing something new on the ground.

- **Challenges**

The lack of support from the government kept the clinic from the acquisition of innovative technologies that were available in developed countries. The financial limitations created barriers to the success of the business.

Overview of Organisation 11

The organisations include two private clinics; these clinics were offering birthing services initially.

- **How idea took place**

Later, the political environment encouraged entrepreneurs to include operating rooms in the clinic. The inclusion of operating rooms was an innovation that occurred in the result of an external environmental factor. However, later the entrepreneur realised that the survival of the clinics would be difficult without changing the practices that meet the customers' needs. The culture of Algeria changed gradually and cosmetic surgery became a trend in the medical industry. The variation in industry trends led the clinic to incorporate the changes to keep with the revolution. The clinics expanded its services and started offering medical and surgical services to perform surgical procedures. The clinic did not stay the same and continued to advance its technologies to deliver quality services to the customers. The lack of support from the government kept the clinic from the acquisition of innovative technologies that were available in developed countries.

- **Mission and capital requirements**

The initial mission of the organisation was to deliver quality care to people and enhance the value of care for people by collaborating with people and bringing transformation to services. The business initially spent \$7746.66 in the business and successfully exceeded the breakeven point with annual revenue of \$8795.56. Currently, the monthly profit of the business is \$1832.40 which makes annual \$21988.75.

Case study 12

Overview of Entrepreneur 12

- **Type**

The entrepreneur is the female business owner of an art company who started her business according to her experience in the job field

- **Age and education**

The interviewee has an age of 30 years, she was an undergraduate

- **Experience**

She did a job for less than two years in the field that is related to her sectorial activity. She started her studies in France and Algeria by considering politics as a major subject; but, later she changed her mind and moved to design. She decided to pursue art training and preferred to be specialised in video and image designing.

- **Believes**

The entrepreneur believes in creativity and innovation. She made significant efforts and made remarkable progress in her business. She succeeded in the business world with flying colours by showing her ability to think out-of-the-box. She did not restrict herself and after watching significant growth in the business expanded its roots to other countries. The entrepreneurs showed her talent and creative sides to the world that helped her in expanding the operations and leave her marks in the business world as a successful lady.

- **Motivation**

In 1998, the entrepreneur after experiencing different subjects decided to restore her art activities while avoiding other activities. The art work was the reason of her motivation to enter the field. The entrepreneur has been keen to work in different areas. She has been creative in her journey of entrepreneurship. She did not stop her efforts in serving restricted services to customers. She emerged some creative aspects in her design to demonstrate to her customers that she can offer more than the things that customers order.

- **Challenges**

The entrepreneur told that the disclosed lack of technical competence and the ability to adapt things are two of the key challenges. She stated that the lack of financing sense, lack of training, and governmental support are serious implications for female entrepreneurship. She mentioned that financials, lack of training opportunities, and societal acceptance are some of the core challenges that Algerian female entrepreneurs face in the design and art industry. She also stated that The Company still contains an ability to improve its profitability if the funds are available for training and developing staff.

Overview of Organisation 12

The company was found in 2008 with an undergraduate female entrepreneur. The company has a major focus on art activities.

- **How idea took place**

Following the artistic side, the company started operating as a design agency that also includes graphic designing. The business has not been limited to casual designing elements that were ordered by customers. The business used to offer creative elements in its designs to reflect on the ability to go beyond the services that every other graphic designing company was providing. The company wants to secure a stable condition in the market and extends its services to other geographical areas to strengthen its customer base. The company's actions speak louder than words; the business made a growth at a fast pace and expanded its activities to other countries. The business started entering other countries including London and Paris. Currently, the company contains a range of staff including mediators, artisans, mediators, and designers. Some other office staff includes cleaning staff, cooks, human resource personnel, and administration.

- **Mission and capital requirements**

The mission of the company is to deliver quality and unique services to its customers with the vision of securing a leading position in the market. The company invested \$387.33 in the business and successfully generate revenue of \$503.53 in the first year. Currently, the business is generating \$790.20 on monthly basis.

Case study 13

- **Type**

The interview was conducted with the female who was an owner of an educational course centre.

- **Age and education**

The entrepreneur was an age of 44 years

- **Experience**

She possesses professional experience of 2 years for maintenance of aircraft at Algerian airport. She moved away from her field due to lack of interest. At the age of 28 after marriage, she ceased her professional activities. The main reason for quitting her job was main oriented atmosphere. There were no opportunities for career growth being female. She have five children including one disable little child girl. As the children grew up, she attended different training for changing her routine life. The training was related to female development, neuroscience, feng shui and energies. After death of her daughter, she adhered with association where she was responsible to provide lesson on personal excellence and presentations in different primary and secondary schools.

- **Believes**

The entrepreneur believes in ongoing efforts and does not believe in stopping at any stage of life. She is creative and knows to make her place in the business world. She believes in creativity and delivering people with their needs. She believes that development and training of adolescence girl is highly critical as behaviours and decision taken during this stage can impact the later horizon of life. The adolescence boys are subjected to more autonomy and mobility, however for girls; it is associated with increasing restriction, insufficient freedom for execution of choices and minimal opportunities. In this formative period, it is essential to give relevant tools and training required for economic empowerment of young female.

- **Motivation**

The positive outcomes of and outstanding results of her presentations in different primary and secondary schools motivated her to start her journey of entrepreneurial world. She decided to

begin its entrepreneur journey in the form of start-up of her personal educational outreach course centre.

- **Challenges**

The main issues faced by entrepreneur during deployment of innovation are based on personal apprehension with differentiated nature of work based on offering different courses and activities for girls. The entrepreneur overcomes this obstruction by inviting people to attend different workshop and encourage the staff for explanation about the nature of courses.

Overview of Organisation 13

Outreach course centre is based on the conception of innovation in Algerian context. The target market of this course centre were mainly consists of young adolescent girls. The innovations were centred on specialisation approaches. In educational course centre, different courses, clubs and workshop were offered to adolescent girls. The organisation introduced the initiatives of first aid and commences different types of competition related to brain quiz. The organisation also involves in different radio broadcast for adults and children regarding the leadership. The organisation frequently asked about the pre-solar classes to full the needs of people. The organisation also subscribes different groups on social media.

- **How idea took place**

The idea took place when the entrepreneur got motivation from the positive outcomes of her presentations.

- **Mission and capital requirements**

The main mission of educational outreach course centre is based on commitment, responsibility and possibility to improve the overall awareness of adolescence girls. Personal finances sources were her husband merely. The start-up capital amount was about \$387332.90 and revenue of \$538549.60. Moreover operating expenses are greater as compared to yearly revenue of course centre

Case study 14

Overview of Entrepreneur 14

- **Type**

The interview was conducted with the female entrepreneur of group of private school established in year 2002

- **Age and education**

She is 61 years old in age and has gained a higher educational degree.

- **Experience**

She possess about 30 years of professional experience. Due to marriage and upbringing issues of small children, she quit the teaching activities. She resumes the teaching in private schools when her children grew up. The school owners were doctor and have lower level of knowledge about education. Thus, she decided to open her school by utilising personal source of financing.

- **Believes**

The female entrepreneurs believe that excellent outcomes and reputation is vital for effective teachers. Meeting are often conducted specifically at the end of year for conducting the discussion about relevant solution. The decisions are based on teamwork where employees can engage with each other and provide suggestion. The school staff is sent for the purpose of training specifically in France that last 2-3 weeks. The school was the part of Francophonie that stop their services for ten years. The female entrepreneurship withdraws from the association due to assumption of time wastage. The female entrepreneurs are enthusiastic for effective collaboration for forward progression of school. The few examples are exchange of students and extra-curricular activities.

- **Motivation**

The entrepreneur was highly keen for providing good care and high quality education. The innovation practices in viewpoint of female entrepreneur are based on creation and continuous progress. A large number of push factors were responsible for moving forward. The innovation element of relevant schools are based on pedagogical improvement such as commencement of new system of education, value added service such as effective administration and additional

services for instance simple activities that make the life of parent highly convenient and these factors motivated her to enter the entrepreneurial world.

- **Challenged**

The factors considered by Algerian female entrepreneur are conforming to stringent requirement of licensing and annual inspection visits. Due to this situation, school is highly constrained and adopt a vigilant approach for survival in Algerian private school sector. In Algeria no collaboration is found among state and private sectors that is the element of humiliation.

In practice, the lack of support to female entrepreneurs is observed. Even though the investment by female in Algeria is on rise, nonetheless, female are hampered more than male all the time. The bureaucratic environment for female is unbearable as well as delayed. An Algerian female entrepreneur required more courage as well as strong and irony nerves. A lack of encouragement and recognition is observed from ministries.

Overview of Organisation 14

The group comprises about 130 employees and possesses a post-graduate level of education. The school encourages the students for trying new and exciting things to provide a rigid and solid foundation. The innovative school concepts are based on the vision of development of more responsible and confident individuals that possess aspiration to arrive at their full potential. The school provides a supportive, safer and happy atmosphere of learning where achievements are celebrated in effective manner.

- **How idea took place**

The example of innovative practice deployed by female entrepreneur in establishment revealed that English is introduced as supplementary foreign language in addition to computer science that resulted in excellent outcomes. Each year, school intends to improve its innovation efforts that merely depend on needs and age of children.

- **Mission and capital requirements**

The main mission of this new school is to foster the learning among students. The organisation initially spent \$ 50000.

Case study 15

Overview of Entrepreneur 15

- **Type**

The entrepreneur is the female business owner of a craft workshop.

- **AGE and education**

The age of interviewee is about 40 years and the educational background is related with secondary level in addition to training of “Fine Arts”

- **Experience**

She had 5 years of professional experience as the employees at art workshop. She decided to establish new start-up of craft workshop that provides glass painting, art work, decoration, ceramics and glass work.

- **Believes**

The female entrepreneur believes that creative side is more important for running the business.

- **Motivation**

The rationale behind this decision is based on the fact that it is complicated to work for other specifically in discipline of crafts. Their wages are minimal and never valued really along with extended working hours.

The entrepreneur conducted extensive research on varied mode of financing as she documented herself on ANGEM, ANSEJ and CNAC as well as bank loans. As her age limit exceeded therefor she had to consult with CNAC primarily afterwards, then she utilised her personal finances.

- **Challenge**

The main challenges encountered during financing were related with the slow process, prevalence of bureaucracy and unnecessary documentation. The other challenges are related with

meeting and training with leaders, therefore, she prefer personal source of financing specifically for female entrepreneur.

Regarding the collaboration and association, the female entrepreneur attempted to work with government on specific agencies for example new mosque that contained massive mosaic work. However, this project was distributed to old artisan. It entails that there is lack of opportunities and support particular for young artist.

Overview of Organisation 15

The business of craft workshop aimed to nurture the artistic growth by providing exhibition, workshop and other opportunities for its staff.

- **How idea took place**

The entrepreneur aimed for the extension of cultural enhancement for larger base of community by exhibition of work of artist on different location for emphasising the significance of art world. The female entrepreneur acquired her family skills. The factors considered during launch of something new, availability and feasibility of raw material is taken into consideration.

- **Mission and capital requirements**

The mission of craft shop in Algeria is to offer particular guidance for creation of customer experience that enhances the desire of customer to return back. The business spent \$5000 initially and then the other expenses occurred with time and the financial requirements were filled accordingly.

Case study 16

Overview of Entrepreneur 16

- **Type**

The Algerian female entrepreneur opened an event and communication company in 2012

- **AGE and education**

She is a 60-year-old woman with graduation in marketing.

- **Experience**

She had 20 years of professional experience specifically concerning events and other marketing disciplines. After 10 years in 2011, she resigned from a job because of work atmosphere and stress. She decided to commence her own business as the event agency.

- **Believes**

The effective mode of staff training is based on field work. She is highly keen for enrolment in the MBA program and attends training on the subject of psychology and correspondence. The entrepreneur is keen for collaboration and work in partnership with other cities for working on a different project. She believed that innovation is not much prevalent in the Algerian context

- **Motivation**

The interest and poor circumstances in the professional world for female employees motivated her to step in the entrepreneurial domain.

- **Challenges**

The management of customers in different manner is considered as innovation. The client management system is highly differentiated. The innovative practice example as deployed in automotive events were found to be highly creative and required all time innovation. The example of project was container that transformed by placing glass wall followed by rotation in Algerian square. However, a lack of acceptance is observed in Algerian society. The entire findings of interviews are useful for better realisation of innovation and integration of revolutionary business practices. There is no particular innovation budget and it depends on case to case. Different source of funding are available to female entrepreneurs. The female entrepreneur utilises the CNAC for acquisition of small funds.

Overview of Organisation 16

The event and communication company is highly enthusiastic for presentation of exceptional level of service and amazing events for each client. The business aimed to create a vision for world of business full of connection, meaning and prosperity and providing measurable and excellent outcomes to vendor, employees and customers.

- **How idea took place**

The event and communication company intended to become expert of sales and marketing in order to become the message or communication masters that convey valuable outcomes. These were the factor that gave birth to the idea.

- **Mission and capital requirements**

The mission statement aimed to offer best possible results for customers and convey the factor of word of mouth marketing for its varied services. The organisation initially spent \$55000.